

Pathos

Open Science Impact Pathways

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Cost Benefit analysis of Open Science: synthesis of case studies

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Table of Contents

Disclaimer	4
Abbreviations	5
Executive Summary	6
Introduction	7
1. The scope of the analysis.....	9
2. Impacts pathways	13
3. Which costs and benefits, and for whom?	18
3.1. Costs.....	20
3.2. Benefits.....	24
4. Which impacts beyond CBA.....	25
5. Lessons learnt.....	27
References	30
Annexes.....	31
UniProt Case study.....	31
RCAAP Case Study	31

List of Figures

Figure 1 UniProt structure	9
Figure 2 RCAAP Overall Architecture.....	11
Figure 3 UniProt Impact Pathway Logic	16
Figure 4. RCAAP Impact Pathway	17
Figure 5 Costs and benefits of UniProt in a nutshell	18
Figure 6. Costs and benefits of RCAAP in a nutshell	18

List of Tables

Table 1 Document Revision History	2
Table 2 Costs related to UniProt and RCAAP.....	20
Table 3 Benefits related to UniProt and RCAAP	24

List of Boxes

Box 1 The methodological toolkit.....	7
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Abbreviations

CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
EBI	European Institute of Bioinformatics
EC	European Commission
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EUR	Euros
FCCN	National Scientific Computing
FCT	National Research Funding agency of Portugal
IR	Institutional Repositories
OS	Open Science
PathOS	Open Science Impact Pathways
PIR	Protein Information Resource
RCAAP	Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal
SIB	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
TrEMBL	Translated EMBL Nucleotide Sequence Data Library
UniProt	Universal Protein resource
WTP	Willingness to pay

Executive Summary

This document represents the Deliverable 4.4 of the [PathOS](#) project. It summarises the outcomes of the assessment of two Open Science (OS) resources, specifically **UniProt**¹ (*the Universal Protein Resource*) - a global, expert-curated protein database widely used in biomedical research - and **RCAAP**² (*Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal*) - a national, multidisciplinary repository consolidating Portuguese research outputs.

These resources were selected as case studies to test and refine a Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) framework tailored for Open Science, alongside an impact pathway approach to explore their broader societal and scientific contributions. Understanding the value of OS infrastructures is essential for funders, institutions, and policymakers to make informed, evidence-based investment decisions, particularly in contexts of constrained resources and growing demand for impact accountability.

The assessment reveals that both UniProt and RCAAP deliver substantial net benefits to their respective communities. UniProt provides significant efficiency gains to users by streamlining access to high-quality protein data, supporting scientific innovation on a global scale. Its long-term impact is demonstrated through numerous scientific publications and patent citations, particularly in biotechnology and health sciences, as well as fostering collaborations and start-ups that rely on its curated data. RCAAP plays a vital role in enhancing institutional efficiency and increasing national research visibility. Beyond academia, RCAAP also contributes to broader societal knowledge, with examples of public engagement—such as patients accessing relevant research through the platform—highlighting its wider value. In both cases, the assessment reveals that true value of these Open Science resources goes beyond simple openness; it lies in expert curation, integration, and coordinated management that reduce duplication, increase accessibility, and enhance research impact.

The assessment underscores the flexibility and broad applicability of the CBA framework across diverse Open Science infrastructures, establishing it as a valuable tool for evaluating a wide range of resources. It help reveal efficiency gains and justify investment by comparing diverse costs and benefits, even when these are not immediately obvious. However, future assessments should focus on refining methods to better capture user impacts and long-term contributions, addressing current challenges related to data limitations and attribution.

1 <https://www.uniprot.org/>

2 <https://www.rcaap.pt/>

Introduction

This deliverable summarises the approach used to assess UniProt and RCAAP, along with the key findings from this evaluation. These two Open Science resources differ in scope, content, and objectives and were selected to test and refine the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) framework tailored for Open Science, as proposed by Delugas et al. (2023). The evaluation also examines their broader societal and scientific impacts using an impact pathway approach³, in line with Dekker, Karasz et al. (2023) and Karasz et al. (2024). The assessment relied on a variety of data collection and analytical approaches, including desk research, user surveys, focus groups, publication and patents' citation analysis (see Box 1 for an overview).

Box 1 The methodological toolkit

Desk research: It focused on three different strands of literature to inform the assessment: *(i) Historical and performance analysis:* it related to the history, gradual development, usage, and performance of the resources under assessment, along with their individual components. This review was essential for identifying the impact pathways associated with these resources, mapping the diverse types of stakeholders that potentially benefit (e.g., the scientific community, PhD students, private sector, funding agencies, and government bodies), obtaining primary data (e.g., on costs) and outlining all stakeholders involved in the financing and operation of these resources. *(ii) Impact evidence:* this component reviewed the publicly available evidence regarding the impacts of RCAAP and UniProt, including prior evaluation studies and internal materials (e.g., survey results). The objective was to take stock of existing evidence and build upon it to inform the current assessment. *(iii) Methodological framework:* the literature related to the evaluation of similar Open Resources was consulted to refine and enhance the methodological framework employed for assessing RCAAP and UniProt, ensuring that best practices and lessons learned from similar evaluations were incorporated into the analysis.

Users' online survey: It was addressed to gather deeper insights into user profiles (i.e. age, professional background, etc.), the purposes for which they use the resources (including any other sources used in conjunction), existing alternatives (if any), and primary data on the perceived value of these resources. In both case studies, the user survey was structured in a similar way⁴ and implemented using the EUSurvey tool. A few pilot tests (5-6) were conducted with selected users to gather feedback on the questionnaire's clarity. Overall, 558 responses were collected for

³ A pathway represents the chain of events according to which RI's research-related activities might generate effects on its stakeholders' ecosystem. It entails resources, activity, outputs, outcomes and later impacts. See section 2 for more details.

⁴ Section A – General Information: it investigated respondents' profile (e.g. country of work, professional status, sector of activity, research fields/job details, etc); Section B – Experience with the resources: it investigated on the usage of the resources (e.g. frequency, combination with other sources, etc); Section C – the value of the resource: it included questions investigating the time spent in accessing the resource, processing and work with it as well as the additional time that it would have required to manage agreement, access, process and work with alternatives; Section D – Overall opinion: it collected views on the importance of the resource and examples of innovations developed. In the case of RCAAP, only three sections were present (with the content of section C and D being integrated). A specific emphasis was put on filters to distinguish different use cases of RCAAP/the related Repositories.

UniProt survey (between 26th March and 6th May 2024) and 213 for RCAAP survey (between 12th June and 16th September 2024).

Interviews: in total, 26 interviews were carried out for both UniProt and RCAAP (13 for each case study). For UniProt, the interviews were conducted with selected users from both industry and academia to gather evidence on (i) the purposes for which UniProt is used; (ii) the sources with which data from UniProt are typically combined; (iii) the practices used for the storage of data (locally/ cloud services/Open Repositories, for how long, etc.); (iv) challenges faced by users in accessing or integrating UniProt; (v) the perceived impact of UniProt on users' research outcomes. For RCAAP, the interview process was organised into two distinct rounds. The first round (a total of six interviews) was conducted with users to gain a deeper understanding of how RCAAP (Portal and Institutional Repositories) is used by various user groups, including researchers and administrative staff from institutions operating the repositories. The second round of interviews (in total, seven) was carried out with repository managers from a diverse sample of institutions that cover different repository models. In this round, the focus shifted more toward exploring the internal organisation, benefits and costs associated with participation in RCAAP for the institutions involved. This round was useful to refine assumptions and model costs and their evolution over time at the level of institutions. Overall, in both case studies, the insights gained from these interviews informed the design of the users' survey questionnaire, aided in interpreting the survey results, helped to qualify the impact pathways of these resources better and contributed to fine-tuning the data and assumptions used in the cost-benefit analysis.

Focus groups: For the UniProt case study, two focus groups were conducted to validate and enrich the assessment. The first, on September 6, 2024, focused on validating survey results, while the second, on September 16, 2024, explored willingness to pay via a contingent valuation survey. Participants were selected through contacts provided by survey respondents (243 in total) and direct contacts from the UniProt consortium. Given the non-random selection, findings were treated as qualitative evidence.

For the RCAAP case study, a focus group was held on December 3, 2024 in collaboration with Work Package 3, to gather feedback on the CBA results from diverse stakeholders. The discussion covered the type and depth of benefits and the counterfactual scenario, helping to refine the model and final draft of the case study.

Citation and Patents Analysis: this analysis was performed to complement the findings from the CBA and to explore the long-term impacts associated with UniProt and RCAAP. For UniProt, it was assessed the extent to which the knowledge facilitated by the data provided by UniProt is reflected in new publications and innovations by analysing references to UniProt and its resources in titles and abstracts of patents and academic publications. To achieve this, mentions of UniProt-related terms—such as UniProtKB, TrEMBL, SwissProt, UniParc, and others— were retrieved from OpenAIRE for academic publications and Patstat and Orbis IP for patent data. As for RCAAP, the analysis covered insights on RCAAP-related scientific publications (e.g., number of documents, received citations) with a particular focus on industry-academia collaborations.

Source: Authors

This document summarises the outcomes of this assessment according to the following structure: Section 1 introduces the two resources, highlighting their features as well as the rationale for their selection. Section 2 outlines the impact pathways identified in connection with these resources. Section 3 discusses the findings from the CBA and highlights differences and similarities in assumptions and findings. Section 4 highlights additional potential impacts identified beyond the CBA. Finally, Section 5 offers conclusions and outlines the main challenges encountered during the assessment. **Annexes 1 and 2 of this document include a detailed description of the assessments carried out for each resource.**

1. The scope of the analysis

The assessment focused on two Open Resources—UniProt and RCAAP— each with their own distinctive features, as described below. The rationale for their selection to test the OS CBA framework is also briefly explained.

UniProt

UniProt - **the Universal Protein Resource** - is a freely accessible knowledge base resource that provides details on the biological functions of proteins, with many entries sourced from genome sequencing projects and scientific literature. It is organised into four core databases, including UniProtKB (with sub-parts Swiss-Prot and TrEMBL), UniParc, UniRef and Proteome. It is maintained by the UniProt consortium, established in 2002 and includes the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (SIB), and the Protein Information Resource (PIR). Key features of the database are the following:

- **Integration, standardisation, and up-to-date Information:** UniProt standardises and integrates a vast amount of data from multiple sources, ensuring it is continuously updated. Each protein entry in the database is linked to a tag classification, enabling users to easily recognise the various names associated with that protein in scientific literature. It is a *knowledge base resource*, which means that the users' community actively

Figure 1 UniProt structure

Source: Authors

participates in enhancing the information included in the database by submitting corrections, updates, and annotations as part of their ongoing research efforts.

- **Manual curation and annotations:** The expert curation process is particularly time-intensive and is at the heart of UniProt's distinctiveness. Experts conduct extensive and meticulous curations, which involve selecting, reviewing, and annotating data from scientific publications as well as checking the contributions provided by the scientific community.
- **Cross-References:** The database includes extensive cross-references to other biological databases, allowing users to integrate protein data with other types of biological information.

RCAAP

RCAAP⁵ (*Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal, i.e., Open Access Scientific Repository of Portugal*) is a network of Institutional Repositories (IR) bringing together several Portuguese institutions under a common system. RCAAP provides several services, including free hosting of repositories for the voluntary institutions and a common Search Portal to browse the content of all the repositories at a single point of entry. Data hosting and journals hosting services are also provided⁶, as well as several additional horizontal services, such as technical support and statistics. RCAAP is operated at the central level by the University of Minho and by the Foundation for National Scientific Computing (FCCN) – the digital unit of the National Research Funding agency of Portugal (FCT). The following aspects distinguish RCAAP:

- **Aggregation of Portuguese scientific content:** RCAAP acts as a single-entry point to Portuguese scientific evidence, including documents such as articles and conference proceedings and, to a lesser extent, data. It effectively consolidates scientific outputs from various Portuguese institutional repositories, facilitating access to research that may otherwise be fragmented or not easily accessible (e.g. PhD theses). This feature supports the visibility of Portuguese-language documentation, crucial for local researchers.
- **Cost and expertise pooling:** By providing centralised services such as free hosting for repositories, RCAAP enables institutions to share technical expertise and reduce costs, a crucial aspect in the context of Open Access initiatives.
- **Community contribution and engagement:** RCAAP system encourages active participation from the academic community, fostering a collaborative environment where researchers can easily share their work, thus enhancing the richness of the available content. It is backed by a legal framework mandating deposits to the RCAAP repositories.

⁵ <https://www.rcaap.pt/>

⁶ The CBA was focused on the document Institutional Repositories, as they form the core of RCAAP.

- **Interoperability:** by relying on the OAI-PMH protocol, RCAAP integrates content seamlessly across multiple repositories, ensuring the quality and searchability of aggregated scientific material.

Figure 2 RCAAP Overall Architecture

Source: Authors

Each resource addresses specific community needs but differs in scope, content, goals, and value to the community. The main differences concern the following:

1. **Geographical and Disciplinary Scope:** UniProt is a global resource used by researchers worldwide for advancements in life sciences, particularly in proteomics and genomics. Conversely, RCAAP is a national system that consolidates Portuguese scientific outputs, primarily benefiting researchers, students, and institutions within Portugal (and Portuguese-speaking countries). Additionally, while UniProt focuses on the biological sciences, RCAAP is multidisciplinary, providing access to research across various academic fields, which offers a comprehensive view of national research contributions.
2. **Purpose and Utility.** UniProt is more than just a repository of protein sequences; it provides extensive data curation and annotation. The information is deeply integrated with references to scientific literature, genomic data, variant data, and taxonomies. This integration allows users to save time and resources while retrieving information and conducting research. RCAAP, on the other hand, is a network of Open Repositories aimed at enhancing the accessibility and visibility of Portuguese research. It provides a long-term storage solution for various materials, including documents that would otherwise be very challenging to obtain, such as PhD or Master's Theses. RCAAP's value

also lies in pooling costs and efforts, which enables managing institutions to improve resource organisation and monitor scientific output more efficiently.

The differences highlighted by these two resources allowed for testing the usefulness of the CBA framework for assessing the impact of Open Science in diverse contexts.

Rationale for selection

The decision to select UniProt and RCAAP as case studies for testing the application of the Open Science CBA framework, as outlined by Delugas et al. (2023), was guided by several factors:

- **Availability of data and stakeholders:** Both resources provide accessible data and engage communities of stakeholders, allowing for the collection of detailed input and insights needed for the analysis.
- **Maturity and stability:** Both resources have a long history of development. Launched in 2002, UniProt is based on databases originating in the 1980s and is continually curated by experts from EMBL-EBI, the SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, and the Protein Information Resource (PIR). RCAAP was launched in 2008 and built upon some early Portuguese repository initiatives, such as the RepositoriUM from the University of Minho (Carvalho et al., 2013). The RCAAP project has also undergone gradual evolution and institutionalisation. This maturity and stability facilitated the assessment of long-term impacts and sustainability compared to newer, less-established resources.
- **Wide use and broad impacts:** Studies by Beagrie and Houghton (2021; 2016) found that UniProt is the second most used data source managed by EMBL-EBI, surpassed only by the Ensembl database. This highlights UniProt's central role within the life sciences community, supporting various research disciplines such as genomics, proteomics, drug discovery, and molecular biology. By aggregating content from multiple sources, RCAAP increases the visibility of research outputs from Portuguese institutions. This enhanced exposure can lead to higher citation rates and greater impact for Portuguese researchers, thereby contributing to advancing knowledge within the community and beyond.
- **Cross-sectoral relevance:** While heavily used by academic researchers, UniProt is also a critical resource for the pharmaceutical and biotechnology industries, as well as clinical and healthcare settings. The database supports drug discovery, biomarker development, and many other applications, making it valuable across sectors. Previous assessments (e.g., Beagrie and Houghton, 2021 and 2016; Garcia et al., 2018) have underscored UniProt's role in aiding the development of products and services by both SMEs and larger industry players. The multifaceted use of UniProt suggests its importance across various sectors and enhances its economic and societal impact. While RCAAP primarily targets the academic sector by aggregating Portuguese scientific content, it can also favour broader impacts, such as collaborations between academia and industry and favouring discoverability by the wider public, though these uses remain

fairly marginal. Both UniProt and RCAAP exemplify resources that serve their primary user bases and (to a small extent for RCAAP) extend their benefits to a wider audience, making them ideal candidates for assessing various Open Science impact pathways.

2. Impacts pathways

Starting from the Open Science impact pathways logic described in Dekker, Karasz et al. (2023) and Karasz et al. (2024), an impact pathways framework was developed for each of the two resources under assessment. This framework illustrates how the funding and other resources provided to them (inputs) lead to direct user benefits (outputs and outcomes) and drive wider advancements (impacts) in science, the economy, and society. Preliminary findings from the reconstruction of the impact pathways associated with UniProt and RCAAP can be summarised as follows:

- **Inputs.** Financial resources are crucial for the establishment and ongoing maintenance of both resources. Equally important is the contribution of skilled technical staff, whose expertise ensures that these systems are effectively maintained and continuously adapted to meet evolving users' needs. Both resources rely on these types of inputs. UniProt concentrates them at the central level, and across its community of users. RCAAP mobilise inputs both at the central level (RCAAP itself), but also within each institution, which need administrators, librarians, and to some extent technicians (depending on the chosen hosting model). The provision of these inputs is encouraged by enabling factors (see below).
- **Enabling factors:** these factors are conditions, resources, or background elements that make it possible for the project to succeed. These are not the direct drivers of outputs but the supportive components that create a favourable environment for implementation, progress, and goal achievement. In the RCAAP case, legislation and policies are enabling factors, covering a central role in its operations and mandate to support Portuguese institutions and users. The legislative framework explicitly requires the upload of master's theses and PhD dissertations as well as publications benefiting from the national funding agency support, thereby reinforcing RCAAP's influence within the Portuguese higher education system. In the case of UniProt, legislation was less central; a key enabling factor was the existence of pre-existing platforms from which it emerged. Its success stems more from international collaboration and consensus, which respond to the needs of a diverse global user base while supporting a strong infrastructure for managing complex bioinformatics data at scale.
- **Outputs.** The outputs of RCAAP and UniProt, while similar in their goals of data accessibility, vary significantly in scope and complexity. RCAAP's outputs are designed to enhance the visibility and availability of Portuguese research, focusing on allowing the emergence of different repositories while organising them through a single, central-level portal for searchability. This approach provides value to Portuguese researchers,

academics, and the general public by promoting knowledge sharing within Portugal and internationally. Concretely, documents are typically available online as PDF files. Conversely, UniProt generates outputs that are integrated into international life science analytical tools and databases. This global interoperability allows UniProt data to be used across various research sectors and regions, creating a repository that not only stores data but also interfaces seamlessly with other bioinformatics resources. This integration broadens UniProt's utility beyond academia to industry, supporting applications in drug development, disease research, and other life sciences.

- **Outcomes.** RCAAP allows for efficiency improvements and cost savings, which encompass shared resources and lower operational expenses for Portuguese institutions through centralised repository services. This pooling of resources significantly enhances the efficiency and affordability of managing institutional repositories, thereby bolstering academic productivity and operational effectiveness in Portugal. Users also probably save time in accessing the content available on RCAAP. Additionally, the visibility of research facilitated by RCAAP can foster greater collaboration between academia and industry. In contrast, UniProt's outcomes are primarily centred on achieving efficiency gains for its users. By offering a centralised, Open-Access bioinformatics resource, UniProt allows both industrial and academic users to integrate and analyse data alongside proprietary datasets, which accelerates research, development, and innovation in fields such as healthcare, biotechnology, and agrifood. This global impact manifests in measurable productivity improvements and reduced research costs for academic and private-sector users. Furthermore, UniProt promotes entrepreneurial innovation by enabling the establishment of new companies and collaborations that utilise its Open-Access data to tackle global health and scientific challenges.
- **Impacts.** RCAAP's impacts are more locally focused, with a strong emphasis on academic accessibility, cultural enrichment, and national research visibility within Portugal (and Portuguese-speaking countries). By broadening the reach of Portuguese research outputs, RCAAP not only supports academic and public access to knowledge but also fosters cultural awareness and educational benefits for the Portuguese population. These societal benefits, though challenging to document, include enhanced knowledge sharing and awareness, which contribute to the national economy by fostering an educated and informed public. International benefits are also present, though to a lesser extent than in UniProt. UniProt's impacts are global and extend into scientific discovery, innovation, and economic growth. With applications in drug discovery, disease prevention, and biotechnology, UniProt's data resources support significant advancements in life sciences that contribute to both economic and societal improvements.

The figures below provide an overview of the impact pathway logic (IPL) identified for UniProt and RCAAP. A more detailed description is provided in the case studies enclosed in Annexes.

Based on this comparison, it is clear that while both resources aim to provide open and accessible data for academic and societal benefit, their unique inputs, outputs, outcomes, and impacts reflect their distinct scopes and user bases. RCAAP's national focus enhances Portuguese academic visibility, while UniProt's global reach fosters advancements in life sciences, driving innovation and economic growth on a worldwide scale. These impact pathways underscore the significance of tailored research infrastructures that meet specific community needs while simultaneously supporting broader academic and industry objectives.

The CBA was specifically conducted to assess the short-term outcomes delivered to users by UniProt and RCAAP. For UniProt, these benefits primarily take the form of efficiency gains, which include time and cost savings for users. Similarly, RCAAP generates efficiency improvements for Portuguese institutions through reduced operational costs associated with centralised repository services, as well as enhanced accessibility for users.

For the assessment of long-term outcomes, a broader causal pathways analysis was employed. This method acknowledges that long-term outcomes typically involve a complex range of contributing factors, making it difficult to draw direct causal connections to a single resource. In the case of UniProt, long-term impacts were evaluated through patent and citation analyses, which offer insights into its influence on innovation and research outputs. Additionally, other outcomes, such as the formation of startups, were assessed using qualitative evidence collected from interviews and user surveys. The long-term outcomes of RCAAP are discussed using qualitative and quantitative evidence.

Figure 3 UniProt Impact Pathway Logic

Source: Authors' elaboration **Note:** The scope of the CBA is highlighted in red to mark a difference between the benefits entirely triggered by using UniProt and benefits beyond those captured by the CBA, such as the long-term outcomes highlighted in blue.

Figure 4. RCAAP Impact Pathway

Source: Authors **Note:** While certain elements of this Impact Pathway Logic (IPL) - such as inputs, activities, and outputs - may be directly controlled by the stakeholders involved in RCAAP (sphere of control), others fall outside its direct control (sphere of influence and sphere of interest). The sphere of influence is an intermediate category regarding the degree of control of stakeholders involved in RCAAP (notably depending on the performance and engagement of potential users). The final stage (impacts) remains beyond both the direct control and influence of RCAAP stakeholders. However, impacts are certainly of high interest to funders, policy makers, and hence, the RCAAP community. The scope of the CBA is highlighted in red to mark a difference between the benefits entirely triggered by using RCAAP and benefits beyond those captured by the CBA, such as the long-term outcomes highlighted in blue..

3. Which costs and benefits, and for whom?

The figure below provides an overview of the types of costs (mostly referred to as the input “funding” in the IPL, see Section 2) and benefits (described as short-term outcome “cost savings in the IPL, see Section 2), which were identified for UniProt and RCAAP.

Figure 5 Costs and benefits of UniProt in a nutshell

Source: Authors.

Note: Information regarding setup costs incurred by the provider was missing and, therefore, not included in the CBA. Training and Access costs incurred by users (in red in the Figure) have been estimated but not included in the CBA since users would still face similar costs if UniProt didn’t exist. More details are reported in the case study enclosed in Annex.

Figure 6. Costs and benefits of RCAAP in a nutshell

Source: Authors.

Note: Training and deposit costs (in green in the Figure) were estimated but excluded from the cost-benefit analysis, as they are assumed to cancel out—users would likely have incurred these costs even without RCAAP. Access costs (in orange in the Figure) were also estimated but not included in the analysis due to uncertainty, as many users found it difficult to imagine a scenario without RCAAP and how it would have affected their work. More details are reported in the case study enclosed in Annex.

In line with the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) recommendations for cost estimation (2019), we distinguished between **setup** and **operational** costs associated with these resources. *Setup costs* refer to initial expenditures related to planning, designing, and launching the resource—essentially everything needed to get it off the ground. In contrast, *operational costs* encompass ongoing expenses required to keep the resource functional and up to date. In line with the framework tailored for Open Science by Delugas et al. (2023), we found that both providers and users incur costs in maintaining these resources.

Reconstructing setup costs for UniProt (2001–2002) and operational costs prior to 2017 proved challenging due to data limitations.⁷ Therefore, the analysis focused on the period from 2017 to 2023, for which reliable data were available. Despite these limitations, the CBA approach was applied to assess whether UniProt's benefits outweighed its operational costs during this timeframe, ultimately revealing a net positive impact for users. In contrast, a full-fledged CBA was conducted for RCAAP. Comprehensive data on both setup and operational costs were collected and compared with the estimated benefits, leading to the calculation of a net present value⁸ for the resource.

On the benefits side, we identified key differences between the two resources. For **UniProt**, user benefits are largely driven by efficiency gains, resulting in savings in transaction, access, and labour costs. For **RCAAP**, users benefit primarily from savings related to storage, labour, and access costs⁹.

The following sections provide a more detailed comparison of the key similarities and differences in the costs and benefits of the two resources examined.

⁷ The CBA of UniProt does not include set-up costs due to the lack of access to reliable data on initial investments and several years of operational expenses. This limitation prevented the computation of a full net present value for the project. However, the omission of the set-up costs is unlikely to substantially affect the overall results of the analysis, as these costs are expected to be relatively modest (due to the pre-existing databases) and not significantly different in scale from annual operational expenses. Furthermore, it is the sustained coverage of operational costs that plays a more critical role in ensuring the long-term viability of the resource.

⁸ Net Present Value (NPV) is a financial metric that calculates the difference between the costs and benefits for a project or investment, adjusted so that flows that happen at different points of time are comparable. A positive NPV indicates that the project is expected to be beneficial, while a negative NPV suggests it may not be worth pursuing.

⁹ Though access costs savings were not fully integrated into the CBA model.

3.1. Costs

The table below provides an overview of the costs that were identified with UniProt and RCAAP.

Table 2 Costs related to UniProt and RCAAP

		UNIPROT	RCAAP
Stakeholder involved	Cost type	Description	Description
Provider	Setup	These include costs for office acquisition, legal fees associated with the consortium's formation, and expenses for equipment and personnel dedicated to designing the integrated platform. However, historical financial records detailing these initial expenses were either incomplete or unavailable, making it challenging to quantify them accurately.	<p><u>Repository at CENTRAL level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments and reinvestments (Intangible fixed assets, Computer equipment and software) • Staff costs and other expenditure <p><u>Repositories at INSTITUTIONAL level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments and reinvestments (<i>only for LOCAL repositories</i>) • Staff costs and other expenditures (<i>for all types of repositories</i>)
Provider	Operational cost	They include salaries, travel, equipment, consumables, publications, and overheads.	<p><u>Repository at CENTRAL level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff costs and related expenditure • Training costs • Travel costs • Dissemination • Funding to partner institutions • Other expenses <p><u>Repositories at INSTITUTIONAL level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff costs: (a) Maintenance and technical support staff costs (<i>only LOCAL repositories</i>) and (b) Administration and management staff costs (<i>all types of repositories</i>) • Librarian curation and checks costs (<i>all types of repositories</i>)
Users	Training costs	It refers to the time spent learning how to use UniProt and become an efficient user. Examples include learning how to navigate the UniProt website, how to exploit programmatic access and related code, and understanding which databases contain the information needed.	It refers to the time spent learning to use RCAAP and become an efficient user (specifically to perform deposits).
Users	Access costs	It refers to the time spent in using and working with UniProt resources.	It refers to the time spent accessing and downloading the content available on RCAAP.
Users	Community contribution/Deposit costs	It refers to the time spent submitting updates or corrections to UniProt entries.	It refers to the time spent uploading content to RCAAP (borne by researchers and librarians).

Source: Authors

The same approach was used for both RCAAP and UniProt to estimate provider costs. These costs were retrieved from budget data provided by the organisations managing the resources—namely, the UniProt Consortium and the FCCN RCAAP unit. For UniProt, only operational costs were gathered, as historical financial records related to the initial setup were either incomplete or unavailable. For RCAAP, costs at the level of individual institutions were reconstructed using a sample of interviews with repository managers (distinguishing the different models of repositories). **User costs** were gathered through a dedicated survey conducted specifically for this evaluation. Users were asked to report the time spent learning how to use the resource, integrating it into their workflows, and actively contributing to it (e.g. by submitting corrections, updates, or depositing materials). From a CBA perspective, the time invested in these activities represents an opportunity cost. While it does not involve direct financial outlay, it reflects the value of time that could have been used for other tasks. Two different approaches were used to estimate the monetary value of the time invested by users in these resources. Specifically, for UniProt, information was available on the types of users engaging with the resource. Therefore, the salary equivalent was used to estimate the value of the time they invested. In contrast, for RCAAP, GDP per capita was used as a proxy due to the lack of detailed data on the occupational profiles of its users (using RCAAP to search and download content). Wages were used for user costs linked to training and deposit, in a similar way as for UniProt.

A few considerations arise from the analysis of the costs associated with these resources:

- To accurately capture the costs associated with UniProt and RCAAP, a careful, **multi-perspective approach was necessary**, reflecting the various stakeholders involved in establishing and maintaining these resources. Both UniProt and RCAAP generate expenses for the **providers**—the entities responsible for their setup and maintenance—as well as for the **user communities** that rely on them. Indeed, for UniProt, the ecosystem consists of a consortium that manages the databases, as well as a large academic and private-sector user community that enhances the platform through data contributions, updates, and annotations. The consortium incurs initial setup costs, covering planning, design, and launching UniProt, as well as operational costs associated with keeping the platform functional and current. These include data curation, integration of annotations, adding supplementary information to protein sequences, and website maintenance. Meanwhile, UniProt users bear costs related to the time spent learning to navigate and use the platform, accessing its resources, and contributing to its content through updates and corrections. RCAAP's structure is even more complex, with costs distributed across multiple levels. At the central level, managed by the University of Minho/FCCN, there are general setup and operational expenses similar to those of UniProt (RCAAP Portal, mutualised hosting services for repositories...). Individual institutions that host and manage their repositories also face provider costs, while the user community—especially researchers and administrative staff—incurs expenses notably when uploading content to the Institutional Repositories.

- These resources rely **heavily on labour-intensive processes**. Both UniProt and RCAAP build upon existing materials—such as databases and repositories—with the aim of improving accessibility and researchability. This approach optimises the use of available resources rather than requiring the development of entirely new systems. While it helps to reduce costs associated with building entirely new systems, it requires substantial investment in personnel to organise and integrate existing information. For example, personnel costs for the UniProt consortium represent a significant portion—70.91%—of the total operating expenses, underscoring the labour-intensive nature of the resource. Similarly, at the central level of RCAAP, personnel costs account for approximately 47% of the total expenses for launching and maintaining the resource.
- **Non-recoverable past investment**¹⁰ were found to be a key feature of these resources. Both UniProt and RCAAP build on pre-existing content held by various organisations and operate with a collaborative and interdependent approach. This interconnected nature requires careful attention when identifying the costs associated with these resources, as additional stakeholders may be involved beyond the provider and user communities mentioned earlier. For the purpose of the CBA, the different roles played by third parties within the UniProt and RCAAP ecosystem were carefully considered, and the following methodological choices were adopted in assessing the costs:
 - (i) Past costs related to the datasets on which UniProt was built are considered non-recoverable past investment and therefore not related to this analysis. These costs represent investments that would have been made regardless of UniProt’s data hosting and sharing activities. Similarly, past costs related to the creation of documents hosted by RCAAP IR were considered non-recoverable past investments since they represent investments that would have been made regardless of the existence of RCAAP (e.g., drafting of research papers).
 - (ii) The current costs incurred by researchers and institutions to carry out and publish scientific studies - from which UniProt and RCAAP take data and information - are considered non-recoverable past investment. While these costs are essential for creating the content of the two platforms, they are not part of the UniProt consortium’s and RCAAP direct financial responsibilities. Researchers would still conduct their studies independently of the availability of these two platforms, meaning these costs would have been incurred regardless of the existence of UniProt and RCAAP itself.
 - (iii) Specifically for UniProt (and not applicable to RCAAP), the costs associated with feeding, developing, and maintaining the external databases cross-referenced by

¹⁰ In the CBA jargon, these are known as sunk costs. A sunk cost is an expense that has already been incurred and cannot be recovered or altered by current or future actions. These costs are unrelated to future outcomes and, as such, should not influence subsequent decision-making or be included in analyses of future choices.

UniProt were treated as non-recoverable past investments by assuming that data sharing between UniProt and external databases is reciprocal.

Therefore, the costs included in the CBA of UniProt are limited to those explicitly recorded in the accounting sheets of the UniProt consortium and those attributable to the user community that contributes to UniProt with updates and annotation. For RCAAP, the expenses incurred by both the central system and individual repositories and those related to user deposits were considered.

The **costs incurred by users**—both in RCAAP and UniProt—include the time spent acquiring the necessary skills to effectively use the resource and become proficient users (*training costs*), such as learning how to navigate the UniProt website, using programmatic access and related code, and understanding which databases contain the required information. Additionally, there are costs associated with submitting updates or corrections to the database (*community contributions for UniProt*), uploading material to the repositories (*deposit costs for RCAAP*), and the time spent using and working with the resources (*access costs*). It is worth noting that although estimates for these costs were provided (see case studies in the Annex for details), they were not always fully included in the cost-benefit analysis. Specifically, for UniProt, the costs users face for training and accessing the resource were not included in the analysis. This is because, from a cost-benefit perspective, users would still need to spend time learning and using other similar tools if UniProt did not exist. However, the time users spent contributing updates and corrections to the UniProt database was included since this effort is specific to UniProt's model of manual curation and continuous updates¹¹. For RCAAP, training, and deposit costs were estimated but not included in the model. These costs were assumed to be similar in a situation without RCAAP, so they cancel out when comparing both scenarios. The access costs were estimated for the scenario with RCAAP, but could not be assessed for the counterfactual, due to difficulties of respondents to foresee the situation. However, it can be expected that RCAAP allows substantial access costs savings, by making resources more visible and searchable, so the CBA has a conservative lens (i.e., constitutes a lower bound for the benefits of RCAAP – see below).

Details on the cost estimation results are provided in the case studies included in the Annex.

¹¹ While there are other protein databases available, a notable example being the U.S.-based RefSeq, which provides a comprehensive and curated collection of reference sequences, UniProt remains distinct in its emphasis on manual curation and community contributions. These features differentiate it from more fragmented alternatives, confirming that the associated user-side costs are specific to the UniProt resource.

3.2. Benefits

The table below provides an overview of the benefits that were identified with UniProt and RCAAP.

Table 3 Benefits related to UniProt and RCAAP

	UNIPROT	RCAAP
Benefit	Description	Description
Transaction Cost Savings:	UniProt reduces the time and costs associated with negotiating access to alternative data sources. Easier access to protein data alleviates the need for users to navigate multiple platforms or deal with paywalls, thus streamlining research activities	Not applicable
Access Cost Savings	By centralising a vast array of protein data, UniProt enables users to access integrated information from a single platform instead of scattered resources. This saves time and simplifies data retrieval, especially for researchers who require diverse datasets.	RCAAP potentially reduces the time users spend searching for and downloading content compared to a scenario without it. However, they were excluded from the analysis as a conservative measure due to the difficulty of realistically estimating these time savings.
Labour Cost Savings	UniProt's manual curation and annotation efforts enhance data quality, enabling researchers to conduct more efficient analyses and avoid redundant work.	RCAAP allows to save time and costs through streamlined administration and technical operations, reducing the need for individual management and staff.
Storage Cost Savings	The benefit was deemed too marginal, as it is spread across all company users and represents only 5-10% of storage. It only applies in rare cases where users rely solely on the website or APIs, avoiding local data storage.	RCAAP provides shared technical infrastructure, such as common servers, which translates into lower expenses related to data storage across institutions.

Source: Authors

A comparative analysis of the benefits identified for UniProt and RCAAP shows that **both resources significantly reduce labour time for users**. For UniProt, this accounts for approximately 89% of the total benefits. UniProt strong integration into the life sciences ecosystem ensures data reliability, saving users time on verification and removing the need to justify its credibility to stakeholders. For RCAAP, labour cost savings represent 84% and stem from two main sources: the centralisation of technical staff who manage multiple repositories more efficiently than individual teams at each institution and the simplification of tasks through standardised services (e.g., for the technical set-up of each repository). This setup streamlines management, technical and administrative processes compared to operating institution-specific repositories.

Both services also help users to **save time when accessing information**. UniProt centralises diverse datasets into a single platform, streamlining data retrieval for researchers. Similarly, RCAAP reduces the time needed to locate and download content. However, in the case of

RCAAP, difficulties in precisely quantifying these time savings compared to alternatives led to their exclusion from the analysis as a precautionary measure.

Both resources provide shared infrastructures for data storage, resulting in reduced storage costs for users. Nevertheless, this benefit appears more significant for RCAAP, as it represents a concrete reduction in expenses for institutions relying on common servers (for hosted repositories). In contrast, the impact on UniProt is limited and unlikely to significantly affect the overall cost-benefit analysis. Firstly, evidence indicates that UniProt's storage costs are already shared among all users within an organisation, resulting in negligible individual savings. Secondly, substantial cost savings would only occur if users exclusively accessed the UniProt website or relied entirely on API access—scenarios that have proven to be relatively uncommon.

To estimate these benefits, evidence was collected through user surveys targeting both UniProt and RCAAP. The surveys were similarly structured and applied a common approach that monetises user time savings. This method was found to be well-aligned with the specific characteristics of UniProt and consistent with methodologies used in previous studies (Beagrie and Houghton 2021; Sweeney et al. 2017; Sullivan et al. 2017; Beagrie and Houghton 2014).

The approach followed three main steps:

1. **Estimating Time Savings:** Users were surveyed/interviewed on the time saved in accessing and using the resources, including time spent on transaction activities and integrating information into their work.
2. **Valuing Time:** Average salaries were sourced from platforms such as Payscale, Glassdoor, and the Economic Research Institute. These were then converted into hourly wage estimates using Eurostat and OECD statistics on weekly working hours by sector.
3. **Estimating Benefits:** The estimated time saved was multiplied by the average hourly wage to quantify the benefits.

Overall, these benefits are consistent with those outlined in the cost-benefit analysis framework described by Delugas et al. (2023), confirming that they are characteristic of Open Science resources.

4. Which impacts beyond CBA

As illustrated in the two Impact Pathway Logics (Figures 3 and 4, see Section 2), the impacts of UniProt and RCAAP extend beyond short-term outcomes—such as cost savings captured through cost-benefit analysis—and contribute to the generation of longer-term effects. However, while these impacts are associated with the use of the two resources, their realisation also depends on additional efforts and complementary resources. In other words, they are not directly triggered by the mere availability or use of data provided by UniProt and RCAAP, which

makes their inclusion in the CBA model particularly challenging. To explore these broader effects, additional quantitative and qualitative methods were employed to assess the extent to which the two resources may contribute to them. Without establishing a causal relationship, these analyses could track the wider impacts the two resources contributed to.

These long-term outcomes can be broadly categorised as **cultural, economic, or organisational benefits**. They may include the diffusion of **scientific literacy across society** and the generation of knowledge through the acceleration of scientific research within academia and industry. These processes foster innovation, as evidenced by **creating new goods, services, companies, publications, and patents, and contribute to strengthening collaboration between academia and industry**.

In the case of UniProt, these impacts have been examined through a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. On the one hand, analyses of scientific publications and patent data (including patent families and applications) were carried out to identify references to UniProt, highlighting the most frequent scientific fields of application and the main sectors in which patents are filed. On the other hand, user surveys and interviews offered qualitative insights into UniProt's role in supporting innovation and collaborative research. These sources also pointed to the emergence of startups and spin-offs whose business models depend wholly or partially on UniProt data or the development of new products and services derived from its use.

In the case of RCAAP, long-term outcomes proved more difficult to observe. Anecdotal evidence from interviewees suggested that the wider society could benefit from the platform through increased access to knowledge and cultural enrichment. For instance, patients can access scientific information on their conditions easily through the documents on the RCAAP repositories. In terms of increasing the research productivity, the analysis of publications indicated that the availability of alternative access routes constrained the ability to quantitatively attribute specific impacts to RCAAP. Moreover, only about 40% of the total scientific output of Portugal is available on RCAAP at this stage. Nonetheless, the platform may contribute to enhanced academic visibility, although this effect is supported primarily by stakeholder perceptions rather than formal indicators. Other potential outcomes—such as strengthened collaboration between academia and industry—may occur, but both qualitative and quantitative evidence suggest that such effects are infrequent and difficult to attribute directly to RCAAP.

5. Lessons learnt

The cost-benefit analysis of UniProt and RCAAP has led us to the following conclusions regarding the applicability of the CBA framework, as described by Delugas et al. (2023). When evaluating Open Science resources, it is essential to bear in mind the following challenges:

1. Clearly defining the legal and functional scope of the Open Resource enhances the accuracy and reliability of the analysis. To do so, it is essential to distinguish between resource-specific activities and those that would occur independently of the resource. Focusing on functions and contributions directly tied to the operation and added value of the resources, excluding external or parallel outputs, ensures a more precise and defensible analytical scope.

Open Access initiatives are inherently collaborative, often involving multiple institutions, contributors, and stakeholders. Their boundaries can be fluid or blurred, making it challenging to clearly delineate the scope for analysis or attribution. For instance, in the case of UniProt, this was particularly complex due to its integration of datasets from over 150 external sources, supplemented by extensive contributions from both community members and institutions. For this analysis, the costs and benefits associated with research outputs developed in other linked sources and shared via UniProt were excluded, as these would have been produced and made available in other databases regardless. Instead, the scope was restricted to activities directly linked to UniProt's functioning—namely, the time and effort invested by community contributors in submitting updates, corrections, and annotations—whose monetary value was estimated accordingly. For RCAAP, functional boundaries were defined around the core RCAAP system, encompassing its network of institutional repositories for documents (i.e., excluding data and journal hosting services) and associated support infrastructures and services, such as the RCAAP Portal, usage statistics, training, and helpdesk. As in the UniProt case, the production costs of the scientific outputs made available via RCAAP were excluded from the analysis since these outputs would have been produced irrespective of the existence of the platform.

2. The selection of an appropriate counterfactual requires to account for the absence of direct equivalents and the fragmented nature of potential alternatives. Counterfactual scenarios may need to vary according to different user groups and patterns of use, as the alternatives available, or their plausibility, can differ substantially across them.

Considering the counterfactual scenario ("What if the Open Resource under assessment did not exist?") is crucial for evaluating the added value or, alternatively, potential losses in its absence. Identifying a counterfactual scenario for UniProt proved complex, as no single alternative resource - whether free or paid - replicates its comprehensive functionality and data integration. The likely alternatives would be a combination of Open-Access databases and paid resources, each offering only fragments of the extensive protein data that UniProt provides.

Similarly, in RCAAP's case, the absence of the system would likely result in a scattered landscape of institutional repositories across Portugal. Some repositories may have emerged independently, but their growth would likely be slower, with higher operational costs and reduced visibility of Portuguese research outputs. Both case studies concluded that, while a combination of alternatives might exist, none could match the comprehensive and accurate functionality of the resource under assessment. Stakeholders may also struggle to build counterfactual scenarios or disagree about which ones are more likely than others.

3. It is important to acknowledge uncertainty and potential underestimation in user impact assessments given existing limitations in tracking mechanisms. User metrics often represent conservative lower-bound estimates, and understanding user diversity requires supplementary methods like targeted surveys that may have representativeness constraints.

Open Science resources, by nature, generally do not track their individual users. The only feasible way to monitor usage is by recording the IP addresses and geographical locations of devices accessing these resources. However, this approach has limitations in accurately determining the exact number of users impacted by the resources' costs and benefits. For instance, multiple users may share a single IP address (such as researchers within the same institution), and conversely, a single user might access the resources from multiple IP addresses (using different devices, connecting from various locations, or through an Internet Service Provider that employs dynamic IP allocation). Additionally, unique IP addresses can include automated access from robots or spiders. To address this challenge, certain adjustments were made based on the recorded IP addresses for both RCAAP and UniProt. Even with these adjustments, it is important to acknowledge that the estimated number of unique users may still be underestimated. This is because multiple indirect users might benefit from the open knowledge disseminated by primary users. Consequently, the user estimates should be considered a lower bound. It also implies that the profiles of users (beyond their number) can only be assessed through ad-hoc surveys, which may not be fully representative.

4. Performing this type of analysis can be particularly valuable in contexts where efficiency gains are not immediately apparent or easily quantifiable. By systematically comparing the costs incurred and benefits generated, often across diverse and interdependent components, a CBA provides a structured framework to reveal the added value and economic impact of Open Science resources. This approach helps stakeholders appreciate efficiency improvements that might otherwise remain obscured, thereby supporting informed decision-making and justifying continued or increased investment.

CBA framework enabled the estimation of the net socio-economic value of UniProt and RCAAP by quantifying the efficiency gains they generate primarily in terms of time saved, an intangible and often difficult-to-measure benefit. This was assessed alongside the costs associated with

their establishment and ongoing operation. For UniProt, the analysis shows that over 70% of its total operating costs are personnel-related. At the same time, approximately 89% of its benefits derive from labour savings, underscoring the value of expert curation and data integration in reducing researchers' time and effort. Each user gains between EUR 3,513 and EUR 5,475 annually, significantly more than the time and effort they invest in contributing to the platform's updates. Similarly, the analysis of RCAAP demonstrates that the centralised coordination of institutional repositories delivers notable efficiency gains, especially in labour and storage cost savings. While most operational costs are borne by individual institutions, RCAAP's shared infrastructure reduces duplication and streamlines operations within the Portuguese research ecosystem. RCAAP's overall benefits exceed costs by at least 33%, reinforcing the case for continued investment.

5. The value of the assessed Open Science resources extends beyond mere openness; it is significantly enhanced by the integration, expert curation, and coordinated management of data from multiple sources. This integration ensures consistency, reduces duplication, and improves accessibility, thereby increasing the overall effectiveness and impact of the resource for diverse user communities.

While Open Access is a common feature for both UniProt and RCAAP, their economic and scientific value mainly stems from how they address specific needs. UniProt's primary added value lies in its highly interoperable, curated, and integrated structure. It not only provides access to biological data but organises it with high-quality standards, linking to numerous databases and bioinformatics tools. This enables users to obtain accurate, comprehensive information, supporting complex research and accelerating discovery. In contrast, RCAAP serves as a centralised and coordinated platform within the Portuguese Open Science ecosystem. Acting as a national infrastructure, it aggregates, organises, and uniformly provides access to research outputs from multiple institutions, boosting the visibility and dissemination of Portuguese scientific production. This centralisation reduces fragmentation and duplication, enhancing the overall efficiency and collective value of the research ecosystem.

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UniProt Case study

RCAAP Case Study

Pathos

Open Science Impact Pathways

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Cost Benefit Analysis of Open Science: UniProt case study

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Table 1 Document Revision History

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Authors' contributions:

Erica Delugas (CSIL) carried out the overarching analysis, data collection, and draft of the report. Gelsomina Catalano (CSIL) provided overall methodological guidance, contributed to the structuring, content, and revision of the draft, and ensured alignment with the overall CBA methodological framework. Silvia Vignetti (CSIL) provided methodological guidance and comments on the drafting to improve quality. Alessandra Caputo (CSIL) performed the citation and patent analysis and drafted Section 4 of the report. Dimitris Pappas (Opix) contributed to citation and patent analysis by extracting publications and data on patents. Erika Balsyte and Despoina Sousoni (ELIXIR) contributed to data collection, interview schedules and coordination with the UniProt team. Izabella Martins Grapengiesser (Technopolis Group) contributed to the design of the Impact Pathway of UniProt, Section 2 of the report.

Table of Contents

Disclaimer	7
Abbreviations	8
Executive Summary	9
Introduction	10
1. UniProt: a catalogue of proteins.....	11
1.1. The database.....	11
1.2. Using UniProt: how, who and for what.....	15
2. UniProt impacts pathways	22
3. Cost-Benefit Analysis.....	27
3.1. Setting the analysis	28
3.1.1. Scope of the analysis.....	28
3.1.2. The counterfactual scenario	29
3.1.3. Users' population.....	31
3.2. Costs.....	34
3.2.1. Provider costs	36
3.2.2. Users costs	38
3.3. Benefits.....	44
3.3.1. Transaction cost savings	46
3.3.2. Access cost savings.....	49
3.3.3. Labour cost savings.....	52
3.4. Overall results	55
4. Benefits beyond CBA.....	59
4.1. Publication analysis	60
4.2. Patent analysis	66
4.2.1. Findings from narrowed patents' analysis	66
4.2.2. Findings from extended patents' analysis.....	72
4.3. Other enablement benefits.....	78

5. Conclusions and lessons learnt	80
5.1. Conclusions	80
5.2. Lessons learnt	82
References	85
Annexes	88
1. Methodological toolkit	88
2. Interviews carried out	94

List of Tables

Table 1 Document Revision History	2
Table 2 Types of data that are usually part of the same data pool as UniProt	22
Table 3 Costs related to UniProt	35
Table 4 UniProt operational costs	37
Table 5 Transaction cost savings – estimation results	48
Table 6 Access cost savings – estimation results	52
Table 7 Time savings – estimation results	54
Table 8 Labour cost savings – estimation results	55
Table 9 Overview of results for the total user population	56
Table 10 Average user costs and benefits, user cost per person	57
Table 11: List of interviews.....	94

List of Figures

Figure 1 Assessing the value of UniProt: the methodological toolkit.....	10
Figure 2 Roots to UniProt and its current developments	14
Figure 3 Unique visitors tracked by year	17
Figure 4 Country of unique visitors that accounts for at least 1%.....	17
Figure 5 UniProt users’ professional status.....	18
Figure 6 UniProt users’ primary research field and sector of activity	19
Figure 7 Survey respondent by main role in their organisation	20
Figure 8 Services and products developed with UniProt	21
Figure 9 Final users of products and services developed with UniProt.....	21
Figure 10 UniProt Impact Pathway Logic.....	26
Figure 11 Costs and benefits of UniProt in a nutshell	27

Figure 12 Hypothetical counterfactual of UniProt	30
Figure 13 UniProt users by profiles.....	33
Figure 14 Time spent per year to attend training courses provided by UniProt.....	39
Figure 15 Number of training sources attended by users provided by UniProt.....	39
Figure 16 Time spent in training organised by user’s organisations.....	40
Figure 17 Number of users attending training organised by their organisations	40
Figure 18 Time spent in hands-on practice with UniProt.....	41
Figure 19 Time spent in accessing, integrating, and working with UniProt data	42
Figure 20 Time spent on average to submit an update or a correction to UniProt.....	43
Figure 21 Number of community contributions by year.....	44
Figure 22 Transaction time savings per week	47
Figure 23 Access frequency	49
Figure 24 Access time savings per week by alternative.....	51
Figure 25 Weekly labour time savings	53
Figure 26 Distribution of respondents by weekly time across selected activities.....	54
Figure 27. Number of publications referencing UniProt or one of its datasets over time (2003-2022)	61
Figure 28 Combination of databases mentioned together.....	62
Figure 29 Distribution of publication by mentioned resource and year.....	63
Figure 30 Distribution of Field of Science (FOS)	64
Figure 31 Distribution of SDGs-related publications by UniProt resources used and SDGs	66
Figure 32 Number of citing patents over time (2002-2021).....	68
Figure 32 Distribution of patents by resource and year	68
Figure 33 Patent document jurisdiction	69
Figure 34 Patents’ technological fields citing UniProt resource.....	70
Figure 35 Network of patent citations	71
Figure 36 Evolution of knowledge creation from UniProt to patents	72
Figure 37 Number of patents over time (1988-2022).....	73
Figure 38 Evolution of patents by resource and year.....	74
Figure 39 Patent document jurisdiction	75
Figure 40 Technological fields of patents mentioning UniProt resource.....	76
Figure 41 Evolution of knowledge creation from UniProt to patents	77
Figure 42 What if UniProt did not exist?	78

List of Boxes

Box 1 UniProt structure	11
Box 2 What if UniProt did not exist?	30
Box 3 Estimating training time and users	39

Box 4 Patent applications, families, publication67
Box 5 Examples of products and services developed using UniProt data79

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Abbreviations

ADS	Archaeology Data Service
API	Application Programming Interface
BADC	British Atmospheric Data Centre
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
EC	European Commission
EBI	European Bioinformatics Institute
ELIXIR	A distributed infrastructure for life-science data
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
ESDS	Economic and Social Data Service
EUR	Euros
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GO	Gene Ontology
IP	Internet Protocol
IP2L	Internet Protocol to Location
NCBI	National Centre for Biotechnology Information
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OS	Open Science
PathOS	Open Science Impact Pathways
PIR	Protein Information Resource
PSD	Protein Sequence Database
SDGs	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
SIB	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
TrEMBL	Translated EMBL Nucleotide Sequence Data Library
UniProt	Universal Protein Resource
UPI	Unique Protein Identifier
USD	United States Dollar
WTP	Willingness to pay

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the assessment of UniProt (*the Universal Protein Resource*), a freely accessible and expertly curated database providing comprehensive protein sequence and functional information. The evaluation combined a tailored Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) to measure short-term, quantifiable impacts with an impact pathway approach to capture UniProt's broader scientific and societal contributions over time.

Focusing on the period from 2017 to 2023, the CBA considered both operational costs incurred by the provider and the costs borne by the user community to update and maintain the resource. The benefits identified were primarily related to efficiency gains for users, measured in terms of time saved and reduced effort compared to a scenario without UniProt. These benefits include savings in transaction costs, such as the time and effort required to negotiate access to alternative data sources; savings in access costs, due to faster retrieval of information made possible by having integrated data available on a single platform rather than across scattered resources; and savings in labour costs, resulting from more efficient analyses and the avoidance of redundant work, thanks to the improved data quality provided by UniProt's manual curation and annotation. The analysis estimated that each user gains between EUR 3,500 and EUR 5,500 annually, demonstrating substantial net benefits.

Beyond these immediate efficiency gains, UniProt supports long-term scientific innovation and knowledge creation. From 2003 to 2022, over 15,000 scientific publications referenced UniProt, particularly in medical and health sciences, contributing to sustainable development goals such as good health and zero hunger. The resource's influence extends to industry as well, with more than 183,000 patent documents between 1988 and 2022 citing UniProt-related data, mainly in biotechnology and pharmaceuticals. Qualitative evidence further highlights UniProt's role in fostering collaborations between academia and industry, supporting start-ups and spin-offs that depend heavily on its data.

This assessment underscores the challenges of evaluating open science infrastructures. It is difficult to precisely estimate user numbers and define counterfactual scenarios, and attributing costs and benefits in a collaborative ecosystem adds complexity. Despite these hurdles, the analysis clearly shows that UniProt delivers significant net value through time savings and improved data quality, while also contributing to long-term research advancements and societal benefits. These findings reinforce the importance of ongoing support for open, community-driven scientific resources like UniProt.

Introduction

This case study focuses on the impact assessment of **UniProt**, a freely accessible knowledge base that provides protein sequence and functional data to the scientific community and industrial users. The assessment applies a cost-benefit analysis approach in combination with an impact pathways approach.¹ The study employs a range of data collection and analytical methods, as shown in Figure 1 and detailed in Annex 1. Quantitative evidence was primarily used to carry out the cost-benefit analysis, while qualitative evidence helped to uncover the mechanisms underlying the causal pathways associated with UniProt and to provide a more nuanced interpretation of the outcomes identified in the impact pathway logic.

Figure 1 Assessing the value of UniProt: the methodological toolkit

Source: Authors

The findings of this assessment are structured as follows: Section 1 introduces UniProt and its use. Section 2 details the impact pathways that have been identified in the exploitation of UniProt. Section 3 presents the findings from the cost-benefit analysis. Section 4 explores

¹ A pathway represents the chain of events according to which RI's research-related activities might generate effects on its stakeholders' ecosystem. It entails resources, activity, outputs, outcomes and later impacts. See section 2 for more details.

additional impacts evaluated through other methodologies (e.g. citation and patent analysis, interviews and focus groups). Lastly, Section 5 offers conclusions and highlights the main challenges encountered and lessons learnt during the assessment.

1. UniProt: a catalogue of proteins

1.1. The database

UniProt - the Universal Protein Resource - is a **freely accessible knowledge base resource** that provides protein sequence and functional information, with many entries sourced from genome sequencing projects. It includes extensive details on the biological functions of proteins derived from research literature. It is organised into **four core databases**, including UniProtKB (with sub-parts Swiss-Prot and TrEMBL), UniParc, UniRef and Proteome (see Box 1 for more details).

UniProt data are updated roughly every eight weeks, leading to around six releases annually, with its expansion showing no signs of slowing down. UniProtKB – one of the most widely known and utilised datasets, contains over 250 million entries², showing significant growth from the 80 million entries recorded in 2014³. This extensive dataset now requires around 1 petabyte of storage space.

Box 1 UniProt structure

UniProt includes **four** core databases:

(1) **UniProtKB (UniProt Knowledgebase)**: it provides sequence data and associated functional information, including taxonomy, protein variants, relevant citations, and associated human diseases. Users can access this supporting data directly from the protein entry or explore separate, themed databases. For instance, users can either view cross-references for a

² As of the latest release, 2025_01

³ UniProt Consortium (2015)

specific protein within its entry or browse a comprehensive database of cross-references. As of the latest release 2025_01, UniProtKB includes 253,206,171 entries for sequences. It consists of two datasets:

UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot: it is a manually annotated, non-redundant protein sequence database. It combines information extracted from scientific literature and biocurator-evaluated computational analysis. It provides all known relevant information about a particular protein (e.g. functions, structures, post-translational modifications, interactions, etc.). Annotation is regularly reviewed to keep up with current scientific findings. The manual annotation of an entry involves a detailed analysis of the protein sequence and of the scientific literature. Annotated entries undergo quality assurance before inclusion into UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot. As of the latest release, 2025_01, UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot contains 572,970 sequence entries.

UniProtKB/TrEMBL: it consists of automatically annotated entries that have not undergone manual review. It was introduced in response to increased dataflow resulting from genome projects, as the time- and labour-consuming manual annotation process of UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot could not be broadened to include all available protein sequences. It contains sequences from Protein Data Bank, gene prediction (e.g. Ensembl, RefSeq and ENA), and structures predicted with AlphaFold2. As of the latest release, 2025_01, UniProtKB/TrEMBL contains 252,633,201 sequence entries.

(2) **UniParc (UniProt Archive)** is a comprehensive and non-redundant archive of all protein sequences from the main publicly available protein sequence databases⁴, including those outside UniProtKB. Proteins may exist in several different source databases and in multiple copies in the same database. In order to avoid redundancy, UniParc stores each unique sequence only once. Identical sequences are merged, regardless of whether they are from the same or different species. Each sequence is given a stable and unique identifier (UPI), making it possible to identify the same protein from different source databases. UniParc contains only protein sequences with no annotation. Database cross-references in UniParc entries allow further information about the protein to be retrieved from the source databases. When sequences in the source databases change, these changes are tracked by UniParc and the history of all changes is archived. As of the latest release, 2025_01, 833,496,420 sequences are provided by UniParc.

(3) **UniRef (UniProt Reference Clusters)** provides clustered sets of sequences from UniProtKB and selected UniParc records. This helps compress sequence redundancy and speed up sequence similarity searches. Specifically, it provides three resolutions for faster similarity searches: UniRef100, UniRef90 and UniRef50⁵. As of the latest release, 2025_01, 728,048,531 clusters are available in UniRef.

⁴ A complete list of the source databases is available here <https://www.uniprot.org/uniparc> and <https://www.uniprot.org/help/uniparc>

⁵ UniRef100 combines identical sequences and sub-fragments with 11 or more residues from any organism into a single UniRef entry. UniRef90 is built by clustering UniRef100 sequences such that each cluster is composed of sequences that have at least 90% sequence identity to, and 80% overlap with, the longest sequence in the cluster

(4) **Proteome**⁶: a proteome is a set of proteins thought to be expressed by an organism. UniProt Proteome portal provides protein sequence sets obtained from the translation of completely sequenced genomes. UniProt proteomes may include both manually reviewed (UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot) and unreviewed (UniProtKB/TrEMBL) entries. As of the latest release, 2025_01, 843,388 entries are available on the UniProt Proteome portal.

Source: Authors based on <https://www.uniprot.org/>

This knowledge base is maintained by the UniProt consortium, established in 2001 and includes the [European Bioinformatics Institute](#) (EMBL-EBI), the [Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics](#) (SIB), and the [Protein Information Resource](#) (PIR)⁷. The financial sustainability of UniProt is ensured through the combined efforts of its consortium members and financial backing from several national research institutes⁸. In 2024, funders invested approximately 14.4 million USD to finance UniProt's operations, with the majority of the funds allocated to cover personnel costs.⁹

The database as we know it today (see Box 1 above) was established by the UniProt consortium in 2002 to fulfil the need for a centralised repository of protein information, which was increasingly in demand within the scientific community. However, it is built upon earlier databases that date back to 1984. The Figure below highlights UniProt's most important milestones achieved between 1984 and 2024.

(the seed sequence). UniRef50 is built by clustering UniRef90 seed sequences that have at least 50% sequence identity to, and 80% overlap with, the longest sequence in the cluster. Source: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/online/courses/uniprot-quick-tour/the-uniprot-databases/uniref/>

⁶ <https://www.uniprot.org/help/proteome>

⁷ EBI, located at the Wellcome Genome Campus in Hinxton (UK), hosts a large number of resources of bioinformatics databases and services. SIB, located in Geneva (Switzerland), operates the ExPASy (Expert Protein Analysis System) servers, which serve as a central hub for proteomics tools and databases. PIR, hosted by the National Biomedical Research Foundation (NBRF) at the Georgetown University Medical Centre in Washington, DC (USA), is the successor to the oldest protein sequence database, Margaret Dayhoff's Atlas of Protein Sequence and Structure, first published in 1965

⁸ UniProt is supported by the National Eye Institute (NEI), National Human Genome Research Institute (NHGRI), National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute (NHLBI), National Institute on Aging (NIA), National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases (NIDDK), National Institute of General Medical Sciences (NIGMS), National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH), and National Cancer Institute (NCI) of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) under grant U24HG007822. Additional support for the EMBL-EBI's involvement in UniProt comes from European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) core funds, the Alzheimer's Research UK (ARUK) grant ARUK-NAS2017A-1, the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC) [BB/T010541/1] and Open Targets. UniProt activities at the SIB are additionally supported by the Swiss Federal Government through the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI. PIR's UniProt activities are also supported by the NIH grants R01GM080646, G08LM010720, and P20GM103446, and the National Science Foundation (NSF) grant DBI-1062520.

⁹ See Section 3.2 Costs for further details.

Figure 2 Roots to UniProt and its current developments

Source: Authors' elaboration on information provided by UniProt consortium **Note:** In 1984, the University of Geneva received the Atlas of Protein Sequence and Structure from NBRF, which is currently known as PIR, and started curating the first release of Swiss-Prot (1986). In 1998, the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics was created. Until 2001, EMBL-EBI and SIB together curated Swiss-Prot and TrEMBL (Translated EMBL Nucleotide Sequence Data Library, established in 1996 because sequence data was being generated at a pace that exceeded Swiss-Prot's ability to keep up and most data had not been experimentally characterised) as a form of collaboration between the two institutes, while PIR produced the Protein Sequence Database (PIR-PSD). These data sets coexisted with different protein sequence coverage and annotation priorities. After the launch of UniProt in 2002, PIR maintained the PIR-PSD and related databases, including iProClass, a database of protein sequences and curated families, while the other resources were officially merged to originate the core resource of the consortium, UniProtKB.

UniProt is not the only protein database in the world; there are other similar databases in the US with which UniProt collaborates. One such example is RefSeq, the NCBI Reference Sequence Database¹⁰, which provides an integrated, non-redundant, and well-annotated collection of reference sequences for genomes, transcripts, and proteins. What distinguishes UniProt and makes it a unique resource are the following features:

- **Integration, standardisation, and up-to-date information.** UniProt effectively standardises and integrates a vast amount of data from multiple sources, ensuring it is continuously updated. Each protein entry in the database is linked to a tag classification, enabling users to easily recognise the various names associated with that protein in scientific literature. The scientific community actively participates in enhancing the information included in the database by submitting corrections, updates, and

¹⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/refseq/>

annotations. To preserve the database's integrity, curators quickly review these contributions to verify their accuracy and correctly link them to the appropriate entries.

- **Interoperability.** UniProt data can integrate and work with a variety of other biological databases, software tools, and bioinformatics resources. Its standardised data format and protocols enable the effective exchange and share protein information with different systems, allowing the combination and cross-reference of UniProt data with other platforms. For instance, UniProtKB users can link out to 183 other resources (UniProt Consortium 2023). This feature also translates into a high level of credibility and trustworthiness among researchers and professionals.
- **Manual annotation and expert curation.** The expert curation process is particularly time-intensive and is at the heart of UniProt's distinctiveness. Experts conduct extensive and meticulous curations, which involve selecting, reviewing, and annotating data from scientific publications. In fact, despite the vast number of papers published annually, only 2-3% of those indexed in PubMed are relevant for UniProt curation (Poux et al., 2017), highlighting the careful selection required. For this reason, single researchers or organisations would not be able to achieve the same quality by manually annotating the protein sequences.

1.2. Using UniProt: how, who and for what

UniProt is accessible through its website, with data freely available for download and consultation without the need for user registration. FAIR principles guide UniProt data (Wilkinson et al. 2016), and in line with Open Science principles, UniProt guarantees a high level of openness to its resources, allowing any person to access all the databases without barriers. For instance, a user survey by Beagrie and Houghton (2021) highlights UniProt as the third most accessed resource among EMBL-EBI resources, following Europe PubMed Central and Ensembl, with Ensembl Genomes ranking fourth.

UniProt resources can be accessed in several ways, depending on the user's usage and expertise. The website offers a simple user interface that allows for searching proteins by choosing the database and typing the name of a protein. There are also more specific tools such as BLAST, Align, Peptide Search, and Retrieve/ID mapping for expert users¹¹. From the website, users can download data via File Transfer Protocol in the format they need; also, they can opt for the SPARQL endpoint, which is based on a query language for RDF, allowing any user to query UniProt databases and personalise queries depending on their specific needs.

¹¹ BLAST is provided for sequence similarity searching. The 'Align' tool allows to align two or more protein sequences using the Clustal Omega programme. The 'ID mapping' tool allows to submit a list of identifiers to retrieve the corresponding UniProt entries or to map them from or to an external database. The 'Peptide search' tool allows to submit short peptide sequences of at least 3 residues and find all UniProtKB sequences which have an exact match to the query sequence.

Finally, UniProt provides several application programming interfaces (APIs) to query and access its data programmatically.

UniProt enhances access to its services by offering a variety of free training opportunities through its platform. These include online courses like the UniProt Quick Tour, which introduces users to navigating the website and understanding the types of data available. Recorded webinars guide users through accessing and analysing data in UniProt, making these sessions particularly useful for students and early-career researchers. EMBL-EBI and SIB also offer on-demand training modules that allow flexible learning at one's own pace, as well as face-to-face and offsite training for a more interactive, hands-on experience.

UniProt database is used by several thousands of scientists and practitioners around the world every day, and its website records approximately 800,000 unique visitors (Lussi et al., 2023). By tracking IP addresses and IP2 locations of devices¹² over the last five years, the average number of unique visitors has been about 9 million annually (Figure 2).¹³ Notably, there was a significant increase in visits in 2020, reflecting the COVID-19 effect. United States (24%), China (16%), and India (8.5%) have been registered as the first three countries where UniProt data are used to access the website, while these figures slightly change also considering the programmatic access (Figure 3 below).

Within this framework, however, it is difficult to translate these figures into an actual number of individual users. Moreover, analysing UniProt usage going beyond the geographical distribution of UniProt users requires additional assumptions. As outlined in Annex A.1.2, we first applied a methodology developed by Beagrie and Houghton (2021) to estimate the average annual number of users. We then leveraged the results of the user survey described in Annex A.1.3 to further investigate the characteristics of the user population.¹⁴

¹² An IP address (Internet Protocol address) is a unique numerical label assigned to each device connected to a computer network that uses the Internet Protocol for communication. IP2Location is a technology that allows for identifying the geolocation of an IP. Between unique visitors and real users there might be large discrepancies. For instance, multiple users may share a single IP address (e.g., researchers from a single university), and a single user might have multiple IP addresses (e.g., when accessing from different locations, using various devices, or when their ISP uses dynamic IP allocation).

¹³ Due to legal requirement, UniProt has a data retention policy of five years.

¹⁴ The survey sample was not based on a probability sampling methodology. However, following several discussions with the UniProt consortium and through comparative analyses by country and field of work/research of respondents to geographical location of the web traffic data and previous data on publications and patents, we consider the sample distribution sufficiently robust to provide a meaningful description of the overall user population. On this basis, it is also deemed suitable for application in the cost-benefit analysis. Further details are provided in Annex A.1.3.

Figure 3 Unique visitors tracked by year

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt consortium data. **Note:** Browser-unique visitors are tracked with Google Analytics, while Browser and Programmatic unique visitors are tracked by using Meter software, which tracks IP addresses and IP2 locations. The Browser data – blue line - was made available for the period 2017-2023, but for the sake of comparison, the figure shows the same years.

Figure 4 Country of unique visitors that accounts for at least 1%.

Source: Authors elaboration on UniProt consortium data. **Note:** Browser-unique visitors are tracked with Google Analytics, while Browser and Programmatic unique visitors are tracked by using Meter software, which tracks IP addresses and IP2 locations. The figure shows the average percentage share over the period 2019-2023.

As revealed by the users' survey (see Annex 1.3), almost 70% of UniProt users work in universities (54%) or research institutions, including PhD students (13%), while one-fifth are employed in industry (20%).

Figure 5 UniProt users' professional status

Source: Authors' elaboration on users' survey data. **Note:** The figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample is composed of 273 respondents working in the academic sector, 100 in the private sector, 21 in the public sector (excluding public universities and research centres), 69 are PhD students, 32 undergraduate or graduate students, 7 work in the nonprofit sector (e.g., charities or NGOs), and 8 declared a different professional status.

These users operate in the vast and interconnected ecosystem of life science, especially in the field of bioinformatics. For instance, in healthcare, bioinformatics applications range from disease diagnostics and prevention to epidemic monitoring, personalised medicine, and the development of drugs, vaccines, and treatments. In farming and agriculture, bioinformatics deals with crop and breed development and pest and pathogen control, contributing to global food security (Martin et al., 2021). Previous studies have identified key research fields where UniProt is most frequently mentioned, specifically in the areas of biochemistry and molecular biology, biotechnology, computational biology, computer science, and genetics (The UniProt Consortium, 2015). In terms of patent filings, ELIXIR has identified that UniProt is most mentioned in the sectors of Chemistry, Human Necessities (including health, food, and environmental technologies), and Physics and Electricity.¹⁵ Consistent with fields where UniProt is often referenced in academic literature, the user survey (see Figure below) shows that most respondents from academia identify biotechnology, molecular biology, and bioinformatics as their main research areas. In the private sector, users are primarily involved in the pharmaceutical and biomedical technology industries.

¹⁵ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/patents>

Figure 6 UniProt users' primary research field and sector of activity

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figures show the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The top pie shows academic workers by primary research field. The "Other" category mainly relates to biochemistry, biomedical sciences, and biological science in broader fields. The subsample size is 373 observations. The bottom pie shows workers employed in the private sector, public administration, and non-profit sector. The "other" category involves biotechnology, genetics, life science, higher education, and virology. The subsample size is 136 observations.

Respondents occupying roles outside core research roles, both within and outside academia, are primarily bioinformaticians, directors and managers, and wet lab researchers (Figure below).

Figure 7 Survey respondent by main role in their organisation

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows respondents' percentage distribution mode. The subsample size of the top chart is 373 observations, while the subsample size of the bottom chart is 136 observations.

UniProt data are used for various purposes beyond purely scientific research. Based on the users' survey results (Figure 8), the most common service enabled by UniProt is conducting analysis and modelling, with 32% of respondents using a data pool that includes UniProt data and 6% relying solely on it. The second most frequent activity, reported by 26% of organisations, is the provision of databases or tools based on a data pool that contains UniProt, while 7% develop these tools based exclusively or nearly exclusively on UniProt data. Although less widespread, around 11% of organisations license databases or tools based on a data pool that includes UniProt, with less than 4% depending exclusively on it. Additionally, users develop algorithms and software made available through Open Access, with 21% employing datasets that incorporate UniProt and 4% primarily using UniProt data. The datasets that are typically part of the same data pool as UniProt tend to be Open Data, particularly in genomics

(approximately 60%) and structural biology (about 8%). Certain data types, like human-sensitive or controlled-access data, are exclusively available under restricted or paid access (Table 2). These products and services are primarily developed for research centres (28%), universities (28%), private companies (13%), and other organisations (Figure 8).

Figure 8 Services and products developed with UniProt

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample size is 509.

Figure 9 Final users of products and services developed with UniProt

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample size is 509.

Table 2 Types of data that are usually part of the same data pool as UniProt

	OPEN	PAID
None	2.6%	47.9%
Genomics	59.5%	15.5%
Proteomics	54.4%	20.4%
Gene expression	25.3%	13.2%
Structural biology	67.6%	17.1%
Literature	68.4%	15.3%
Metabolomics	10.4%	6.1%
Ontologies	27.7%	4.3%
Chemistry	17.1%	8.3%
Imaging	9.2%	4.9%
Systems biology	31.8%	7.3%
Human-sensitive / controlled access data	-	4.1%
Assay/drug screening data	-	8.1%
Others	4.7%	0.8%

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The table shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample size is 509.

2. UniProt impacts pathways

The free exploitation of UniProt data generates numerous effects relevant to its users (both academics and private users), a wider community of stakeholders, and the economy and society at large. The spreading of these effects undertakes different pathways, each entailing resources, activity, outputs, outcomes and later impacts. Following the impact pathway logic for Open Science described by Dekker, Karasz et al., 2023, we provide – in what follows – a description of how funding and resources made available to UniProt (**inputs**) translate into direct benefits for users (**outputs and outcomes**) and advancements (**impacts**) in science, the economy, and society.

The actual materialisation of UniProt's impact pathway also depends on **enabling factors**, which, in this case, include the long-standing tradition of curation of the individual databases that constitute UniProt, as well as the commitment of its founders to maintaining the project's openness. Enabling factors are conditions or elements that facilitate the implementation and success of the UniProt project, supporting the mechanisms through which it is expected to achieve its intended outcomes. As discussed in Section 1, what we now recognise as UniProt is rooted in around 20 years of work by researchers at SIB and EMBL-EBI who, in collaboration with PIR, began in 1984 to develop Swiss-Prot and later TrEMBL, building on the Atlas of Protein Sequence and Structure from NBRF. Without their continuous efforts prior to the establishment of the UniProt consortium, UniProt would not exist today in its current form. At the same time, the openness of the project is consistently ensured by the commitment of its diverse founders, who require UniProt—and all other ELIXIR resources—to adhere to Open Science principles.

The essential *inputs* for driving UniProt's impacts are the availability of research funding to establish and sustain its the operation, along with skilled staff and a well-established consortium to manage and coordinate these databases. These elements enable a series of activities that are fundamental to UniProt's exploitation. Such activities include the development and maintenance of UniProt data resources, the creation of tools for data users, the establishment of networks among data users and producers, the development and implementation of international standards, and the provision of training and support (e.g. through Helpdesk) for users. These activities yield specific *outputs*, such as making data open and easily accessible, integrating data into analytical tools and software, ensuring that data is equally accessible and usable by both industry and academia and achieving high integration within the life science ecosystem.

Any potential users, including those from industry and academia, can openly explore, extract, and analyse the vast array of data contained within UniProt resources, as well as benefit from the training activities offered. The exploitation of these resources generates several *short- and long-term outcomes* depending on the users and their specific applications.¹⁶ In the short term, both industry and academic users can expect improved work efficiency due to the time saved in collecting, integrating, and analysing the data needed for their research, which are all integrated within UniProt. Over time, this virtuous cycle is expected to boost innovation outputs in the industry and enhance academic productivity by reducing duplicated research efforts. For industry, UniProt's Open Data can be integrated with proprietary data, enabling companies to accelerate innovation, enhance existing products and services, or develop new ones, resulting in cost savings, increased productivity, and higher turnover. In academia, researchers use Open Biodata to generate new knowledge in life sciences, often resulting in a greater number of research outputs, including publications. Academic researchers may also collaborate with industry on new projects using Open Data, facilitating knowledge spillovers between sectors. Another long-term outcome is the creation of start-ups and spin-offs. Open Research Data present challenges in direct market utilisation due to the specialised expertise required for data manipulation, interpretation, and analysis. Consequently, new companies often emerge to bridge this gap by preparing and processing complex data. For example, Garcia et al. (2018) highlight the rise of European SMEs that base their business models on Open Data from public

¹⁶ Short- and long-term outcomes specifically related to UniProt fall within the categories of indicators developed and reported in the PathOS [Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook](#). For example, in terms of economic impact, the indicator 'cost-savings' includes short-term outcomes—such as time savings—which are also considered in the cost-benefit analysis of UniProt. Similarly, the indicator 'innovation output' encompasses what the IPL identifies as long-term outcomes, including new publications, patents, or less easily traceable innovations such as new products (see Box 5, Section 4 for concrete examples of products and services developed), as well as new start-ups generated by entrepreneurial ideas inspired by the use of UniProt resources. In a similar vein, academic impact indicators can be linked to collaboration intensity, citation impact, or research quality. On the societal side, the long-term outcome of 'increased knowledge and awareness in the general public' can be connected, for example, to uptake in education—since UniProt resources are frequently used to develop training materials—or to uptake by policymakers and in medical practice.

bioinformatics databases provided by ELIXIR.¹⁷ The global diffusion of UniProt resources in the life science ecosystem is anticipated to help address significant global challenges in science, the economy, and society (*impacts*). From an academic perspective, UniProt is expected to accelerate scientific discovery and enhance the quality and ethics of research outputs. Economically, by providing essential data that underpins the development of new products and technologies, UniProt is anticipated to increase the level of innovation within the industry. Its Open Access nature reduces barriers to entry for smaller companies and fosters a competitive environment that drives economic growth. Additionally, UniProt contributes to addressing societal and public challenges by enabling academia and industry to collaborate and advance faster in life sciences through innovation in key sectors, such as healthcare, by enhancing drug development, speeding up vaccine trials, and accelerating the early detection of diseases.

While certain elements of this Impact Pathway Logic (IPL) - such as inputs, activities, and outputs - may be directly controlled by the UniProt Consortium, others fall outside its direct control. Despite this, the consortium can still have an indirect influence through engagement with users and stakeholders. The final stage—impacts—remains beyond both the consortium's direct control and influence. However, impacts are certainly of high interest to funders, policymakers, and hence, the UniProt Consortium.

The **pathways from inputs to outputs, outcomes, and impacts** associated with UniProt can be **complex and dynamic**. They involve multiple steps and incorporate non-linear linkages, conditions, and enabling factors that all contribute to the process. When assessing these impacts, it is essential to recognise that their realisation depends on a combination of direct actions and the broader context in which these actions occur. For this reason, while the long-term outcomes are connected to users leveraging UniProt resources, they can be only partially attributed to UniProt, as additional inputs are necessary for their full realisation. For instance, in the causal chain from investing in UniProt to launching a new startup that provides data and services based on UniProt for companies in the agrifood sector, new inputs such as private investments and public funding would ultimately be needed to successfully launch the startup. The direct link between UniProt and the startup lies in the genesis of the entrepreneurial idea, which arises from individuals in the sector who identify a market gap. The same holds true for publications and patents, which require further efforts from researchers beyond simply accessing and using UniProt data. In the research process, additional data are often required, which may be obtained through other financial inputs, such as funding for research assistants or other resources. Therefore, patents and publications themselves cannot be considered direct benefits that can be compared to the costs associated with UniProt. Instead, they result

¹⁷ In particular, the case studies analysed by Garcia et al. (2018) focused on seven European SMEs, with four out of the seven relying on UniProt. The study proposed three different archetypes of companies: i) customising, which repackage, customise, and add value to existing public data resources, including software; ii) aggregating, which collect and aggregate Open Data from public resources and integrate it with proprietary data for industry clients; and iii) enabling, which specialise in supporting clients in finding the specific software tools and datasets they require.

from a broader research effort that encompasses multiple inputs and resources beyond UniProt alone. Wider and broader impacts are more complex to monitor as they materialise much further along the causal chain from the initial exploitation of UniProt resources. These impacts also involve a broader audience that extends beyond the direct users of UniProt. Consequently, tracking and attributing these wider effects is challenging, given the longer timelines and the involvement of various additional factors and stakeholders.

This case study investigates some of UniProt's impacts by integrating a CBA perspective¹⁸ with an impact pathways framework. Throughout the rest of the document, elements of the IPL will be referenced to explicitly highlight the links between the two. **The CBA was employed to specifically assess the impacts that are clearly and directly attributable to UniProt**, focusing on assessing the short-term outcomes it generates for its users, such as time and cost savings (Section 3). **The long-term outcomes are explored within a broader pathways contribution analysis**, recognising that such outcomes often involve multiple influencing factors, and a direct causal link to UniProt cannot always be established. Specifically, UniProt's long-term outcomes were tracked through patent and publications analyses, while other outcomes, such as the emergence of startups, are identified through more qualitative sources of evidence like interviews and user surveys (Section 4).

¹⁸ The cost-benefit analysis adopts a micro-economic perspective. This means that indirect (i.e. on secondary markets) and wider effects (e.g. induced impacts or effects on other categories of stakeholders, or economies) are often excluded from the analysis. The choice is to avoid that the analysis relies on assumptions whose reliability is difficult to check as well as any risk of double counting.

Figure 10 UniProt Impact Pathway Logic

Source: Authors

Source: Authors' elaboration. **Note:** The scope of the CBA is highlighted in red to mark a difference between the benefits entirely triggered by using UniProt and benefits beyond those captured by the CBA, such as the long-term outcomes highlighted in blue.

3. Cost-Benefit Analysis

The cost-benefit analysis (CBA) has been used to assess the short-term outcomes – as illustrated in the IPL for UniProt – generated by using UniProt resources on a specific group of stakeholders, such as its users, focusing particularly on measurable effects.

The analysis was guided by the CBA framework specifically tailored to the assessment of Open Science by Delugas et al. (2023). Although this framework proposes a full-fledged CBA to determine the net present value¹⁹ of an Open Resource, conducting such an analysis was not feasible for UniProt. Challenges arose in reconstructing the costs associated with the setup phase of UniProt (years 2001-2002) and the operational costs (OPEX) prior to 2017 (as explained in Section 3.2.1 below). Consequently, the analysis focused on the period from 2017 to 2023, during which reliable data were available. Despite these limitations, the CBA approach was employed to evaluate whether the benefits of UniProt outweigh the costs of its operation over this period. This comparison highlighted the 'net' benefits that UniProt provides to its users.

The figure below provides an overview of the types of costs (mostly referred to as the input “funding” in the IPL, see Section 2) and benefits (described as short-term outcome “cost savings in the IPL, see Section 2), which were identified for UniProt. Nevertheless, before diving into the specific costs (Section 3.2) and benefits (Section 3.3) associated with UniProt, along with the results of this assessment, a brief overview of the key assumptions underlying the analysis is provided below.

Figure 11 Costs and benefits of UniProt in a nutshell

Source: Authors

¹⁹ The net present value refers to the discounted value of all estimated benefits, net of the costs, of a project over a specified period.

Note: OPEX refers to operational costs. The items highlighted in red in the Figure have not been included in the CBA calculation. Information regarding setup costs was missing, while different assumptions were made for training and access costs (users' costs). The reasons are detailed in section 3.2 below.

3.1. Setting the analysis

The elements of the causal chain illustrated in the IPL require a thorough discussion in order to be translated into CBA elements. To ensure a comprehensive and relevant analysis of the costs and benefits of UniProt, discussions of the following aspects were considered:

- legal and functional boundaries of UniProt;
- the counterfactual scenario (What if UniProt did not exist?);
- the population of users affected by the costs and benefits associated with UniProt.

Although these are common issues in a CBA analysis, their treatment is not straightforward when assessing an Open Science resource like UniProt, which is indeed a knowledge-based Open Resource building on pre-existing datasets. Some methodological assumptions were needed to frame the analysis effectively, drawing on discussions with the UniProt consortium and insights gathered from user surveys, interviews and focus groups. These assumptions are briefly outlined in what follows.

3.1.1. Scope of the analysis

As shown in the IPL (Section 2), UniProt researchers engage in activities such as data curation, tool development for data users, network building among data producers and users, as well as training and support. These efforts result in several outputs, including open and integrated databases that provide extensive protein sequences and functional information, all open and accessible through the UniProt website. However, openness is not the only inherent feature of UniProt; other characteristics can be identified. UniProt databases build upon pre-existing datasets and are tightly linked to over 150 external databases, which often also link back to UniProt. The protein sequences available in UniProt come from various external institutional repositories and contributions from the broader UniProt community. In other words, UniProt's Open Resources are seamlessly integrated with existing databases within the biodata ecosystem. The primary role of UniProt researchers is to assign identification numbers, store data, and curate manual annotations to enhance data quality. While UniProt's contributions are well-defined, it is crucial to identify the scope of the CBA.

As a first step, a clear delineation of the UniProt boundaries, in legal and functional terms, is needed to accurately identify the associated costs and benefits. While determining the legal boundaries is relatively straightforward and aligns with the UniProt consortium, defining the functional boundaries is far more complex, given such an integrated ecosystem of biodata.

The main difficulty lies in distinguishing where UniProt's costs and benefits end and those of other platforms or the external researchers and institutions that generate the underlying data begin. This is a common issue with Open Resources, especially in the biosciences, where data is continuously exchanged, integrated, and enhanced by various contributors from different sources.²⁰ The added value comes through curation, annotation, and the collaborative effort that extends beyond the platform itself.

One might consider partially including the cost of research outputs developed in external linked sources and shared by UniProt as part of the benefit attributed to UniProt. However, extending the project's boundaries beyond the UniProt Consortium would not be appropriate, as most of the research shared on UniProt would have been produced regardless and is available in other databases anyway. **The unique value of UniProt lies not in the mere sharing of original research data but in its ability to integrate this data into a cohesive ecosystem that supports further scientific discovery.** This integration process, facilitated by the curation and annotation performed by UniProt researchers, is where the true benefits emerge.

Therefore, for the purpose of our assessment, in addition to resources provided by the UniProt consortium, we considered only the activities of the UniProt broader community, such as the time and effort spent by users to submit updates, corrections, and enhancements to the data functionally related to the database. These contributions add significant value and are considered part of UniProt's broader ecosystem (as discussed in Section 3.2 on costs), even though they originate from outside the UniProt consortium.

3.1.2. The counterfactual scenario

Following the CBA perspective, the analysis was addressed to compare the benefits obtained from the exploitation of UniProt with its costs by using **an incremental approach**. This entailed **a comparison between two different scenarios: one having UniProt and the other one where UniProt does not exist** (known as the counterfactual scenario)²¹. This approach enabled us to pinpoint the 'net' benefits generated by UniProt. In the context of UniProt and, more broadly, when evaluating knowledge-based Open Resources, determining what would have occurred in the absence of such resources is not straightforward. At first glance, one might think that a paid or Open Access resource offering similar data could serve as a counterfactual since UniProt primarily acts as a repository for pre-existing information. However, evidence gathered from user surveys, interviews, and focus groups (see Box 2 below) indicates that these alternatives—whether paid or Open Access— typically offer only fragmented pieces of information. Collecting and recreating the entire set of data would require a significant amount

²⁰ These inherent characteristics of Open Biodata resources can be more broadly understood within the framework of the governance of digital knowledge commons (Frischmann, Madison, and Strandburg, 2014; Hess and Ostrom, 2011; Ostrom, 1990).

²¹ See Florio 2014 and 2019, Delugas et al 2023 for a more detailed discussion on the concept of counterfactual.

of time and effort (bearable only by large institutions, not individual users) and would still not achieve the same quality and level of detail offered by UniProt.

Box 2 What if UniProt did not exist?

Survey results revealed that it is not credible to assume a unique and fully comparable alternative to UniProt. This is because the choice of alternative heavily depends on factors such as the field of research, specific projects, organisational context, etc.

As illustrated in the figure below, only a small percentage (8%) of UniProt users surveyed indicated they would have accessed the same data through a paid, closed-source option. A modest proportion (11%) of users stated they would have been able to independently recreate and gather the same data. In contrast, over half of the respondents (53%) reported that they would have obtained the data from another Open Resource. Additionally, 37% of respondents indicated that they would not have been able to carry out their research activity without UniProt. Consistency checks on individual responses and logical flow control across the survey revealed some inconsistencies in how participants answered this question²².

This finding is further supported by semi-structured interviews and focus groups. Participants emphasised that the choice between paid or public sources is likely influenced by the funding mechanisms of institutions. Universities, which rely on grants that may be intermittent, might prefer Open Access resources or recreate data themselves from original publications. In contrast, private companies, which often have stricter time constraints but softer budget constraints, might opt to pay for access if possible.

Overall, **users agreed that there is no alternative offering the same breadth of knowledge, quality, and level of integration as UniProt.**

Figure 12 Hypothetical counterfactual of UniProt

²² For example, 15% of respondents who declared they agreed with having "no alternative" also expressed agreement with an alternative to UniProt that allows them to have the same quality data, while 8% of respondents did not agree with any of the alternatives.

Note: The Figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The alternatives were not presented as mutually exclusive. The sample size is 447. **Source:** Authors' elaboration on UniProt user survey.

Source: Authors based on survey results, interviews and focus groups

The value of UniProt, as perceived by users, lies not just in sharing protein information but in its ability to integrate protein sequences identified in the literature with an extensive body of functional information. This integration minimises redundancy and enhances connectivity with other databases, significantly increasing the utility of UniProt. It organises and refines protein data, annotates individual protein sequences, and links fragmented literature sources. For instance, the tag classification of a protein allows users to immediately identify the different names associated with that protein in the literature, while PubMed references within UniProt provide instant access to relevant background literature across various fields. Also, UniProt provides manual annotations to sequences that are considered original contributions that are not available elsewhere. These annotations result from the intensive work of UniProt researchers in collaboration with external research groups, achieving a quality that is difficult for individual users or even single institutions—whether private or public—to match.

Consequently, **meaningful comparisons regarding the implications of UniProt's absence should only be made with platforms that offer a similar level of integration.** Otherwise, the counterfactual scenario would reflect only a fraction of UniProt's capabilities. **Based on the evidence collected, it was assumed** that for the purpose of this analysis, **no single alternative** (whether closed/paid or recreating the resources) **provides the same level of integration and detail as UniProt.** The counterfactual scenario depends on the specific information users seek and consists of a combination of these alternatives. In this sense, **the results of the CBA indicate the net benefit of using UniProt compared to relying on multiple resources**, without specific implications for the use of a particular set of UniProt data available in closed form or openly provided by a different source, which would require a different analytical setup.

3.1.3. Users' population

While the IPL treats the UniProt user population as an implicit component of the causal chain, it is a key element in the CBA, as users are directly affected by the impacts arising from the use of this resource. The IPL primarily highlights the various spheres of impact—academic, economic, and societal—within which UniProt users operate. In the following discussion, we examine the challenges inherent in identifying UniProt users, particularly given its status as an Open Resource.

UniProt is an Open Database, and as typically occurs for Open Resources, its usage is monitored by tracking the web traffic and recording the number of unique visitors (unique IP addresses) visiting UniProt databases, as outlined in Section 1.2. However, as largely discussed in the literature (e.g., Ross et al. 2024; Beagrie and Houghton 2021, 2016; Fomitchev, 2010), there can be significant discrepancies between unique visitor counts and actual users over time. For instance, multiple users may share a single IP address (e.g., researchers from a single university), and a single user might have multiple IP addresses (e.g., when accessing from different locations, using various devices, or when their ISP uses dynamic IP allocation). Additionally, the unique visitor counts can include automated activities from robots or spiders. This distortion has implications for the CBA, complicating the task of determining how many users actually benefit from UniProt. To address this issue, we adapted the methodology proposed by Beagrie and Houghton (2021) to estimate the number of users of EMBL-EBI resources. The details of the assumptions and calculations we used to estimate the number of UniProt users are outlined in Annex 1.2.

Our calculations lead to an average number of users per year of about **107,000 in the period 2017-2023**.²³ Based on these estimates, we further divided the user population potentially affected by UniProt's benefits into two groups: academics and private-sector users. This division allows for more detailed considerations regarding the value of benefits accruing to these two different profiles. To estimate the number of users in each group, we relied on the survey results and assumed that approximately 67% of the total user population consists of academics, while around 20% are from private companies. Given the short timeframe of the analysis, these proportions are assumed to remain constant.

²³ Following the approach of Beagrie and Houghton (2021; 2016), our user estimate accounts for approximately 5% of the total number of researchers in the life sciences—representing the potential user base of UniProt—and should therefore be interpreted as a lower-bound estimate. See Annex 1.2 for further details.

Figure 13 UniProt users by profiles

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt consortium data and UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the estimated number of users by year over the period 2017-2023. The academic sector includes both workers and PhD students. Private users account for respondents working in the private sector. The difference between the total users and the sum of the users in the subsample includes workers from the public sector (excluding universities and research institutes that fall within the academic sector), non-profit sector workers, and a share of other workers that do not fit perfectly into the other categories. Within the category of primary users, undergraduate and graduate students, who account for 6% of the total, according to the survey results, have been excluded. This choice was made after considering the many assumptions required to model their use of UniProt resources to obtain a robust estimation of their benefits.

It is important to note that the estimated number of users may not accurately reflect the entire population accessing information provided by UniProt. The estimates represent the primary users of UniProt—those who can be directly traced through access to the resource. As an Open Resource, UniProt encompasses a variety of secondary users who can be challenging to track. These secondary users may consist of two types:

- *Cross-Referenced Users:* those who benefit from UniProt data that are incorporated into other free and open repositories (cross-references). For instance, UniProt supplies data to the Gene Ontology, which collects UniProt GO annotations and disseminates them to numerous downstream users. In return, UniProt integrates the Gene Ontology and annotations produced by other GO Consortium members. This reciprocal exchange of data is crucial for the advancement of biomedical science, as the entire ecosystem depends on data sharing and reuse. For cost-benefit analysis purposes, these secondary users are considered balanced or "cancelled out" by reciprocal inputs.
- *Dependent Users:* those who access services provided by the primary users accessing UniProt database resources. Unlike the first type of secondary user, benefits accruing to these individuals are incremental and not balanced by reciprocal input. Although efforts

were made to trace these secondary users through interviews and surveys, ²⁴ obtaining a complete picture is impractical due to the large number of primary users globally. In the context of the cost-benefit analysis, this means that our estimation achieves only a lower-bound estimation of the total UniProt user population, which can be identified as the primary layer. Additional qualitative considerations about these secondary users are discussed in Section 4 and explored through other methodologies.

3.2. Costs

Following the IPL framework, one might assume that the costs in the UniProt CBA refer solely to what is labelled as “funding” under the input category. While this constitutes a significant portion, identifying all the costs associated with an Open Resource like UniProt necessitates careful consideration due to the involvement of multiple stakeholders in putting efforts into maintaining the quality of the resources.

The UniProt ecosystem includes not only the consortium that manages the databases—referred to as the “provider” in the CBA terminology—but also a vast community of users and the scientific community that contributes data, annotations, and updates, which are subsequently shared and integrated into UniProt. In line with Delugas et al. (2023) and Catalano (2024), we considered both the costs incurred by the provider, the UniProt consortium, and those incurred by the users.

Regarding the provider costs (i.e. the “funding” reported as input in the IPL), as in any traditional CBA, we categorised them into setup costs and operational costs. Setup costs refer to the initial expenses associated with planning, designing, and launching UniProt—essentially everything required to get it off the ground. In contrast, operational costs encompass all expenditures linked to activities such as curating data, integrating annotations, adding supplementary information to the protein sequences obtained from original sources, maintaining the website, and executing all activities that allow UniProt to remain functional and up to date. All the figures related to the provider costs were made available by the UniProt Consortium, which provided all the balance sheet data they could retrieve.

The costs incurred by users, which are not explicitly stated in the IPL and arise in the process of using UniProt’s outputs, encompass the time spent acquiring the necessary skills to use UniProt’s databases, accessing and working with data, and contributing to its content by submitting updates or corrections. These costs were instead estimated by assigning a monetary value to the time users invested using UniProt and providing updates and corrections based on their responses in the user survey.

²⁴ According to the user survey, about 50% of respondents indicated that they share processed data, software or tools based entirely or partially on information gathered from UniProt with secondary users.

The Table below provides an overview of the different types of costs attributed to both the UniProt consortium and users. More details about these costs and the approach used to measure them are provided in Sections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2, respectively.

Table 3 Costs related to UniProt

STAKEHOLDER INVOLVED	COST TYPE	CATEGORY	SOURCE
Provider	Setup	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Salaries Office Equipment Legal Overheads 	These costs were not available
Provider	Operational cost (outlays and in-kind)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Salaries Travel Equipment Consumables and publications Overheads 	Balance sheet of UniProt
Users	Training costs	It refers to the time spent learning how to use UniProt and become an efficient user. Examples include learning how to navigate the UniProt website, how to exploit programmatic access and related code, and understanding which databases contain the information needed.	Estimated on the basis of data provided by UniProt consortium on training participation, evidence collected through the user survey and secondary data on salaries and hours worked by country and sector.
Users	Access costs	It refers to the time spent in using and working with UniProt resources	Estimated on the basis of evidence collected through the user survey and secondary data on salaries and hours worked by country and sector.
Users	Community contribution costs	It refers to the time spent submitting updates or corrections to UniProt entries.	Estimated on the basis of data provided by the UniProt consortium on contribution sent by year, evidence from the user survey, and secondary data on salaries and hours worked by country and sector.

Source: Authors

As described in Section 1, UniProt builds on pre-existing information held by various organisations and operates with a collaborative and interdependent approach. This interconnected nature requires careful attention when identifying the costs associated with this resource, as additional stakeholders may be involved beyond the provider and user communities mentioned earlier. For the purpose of our analysis, we carefully considered the different roles played by third parties within the UniProt ecosystem, and the following methodological choices were adopted in assessing the costs²⁵:

- Past costs related to the datasets on which UniProt was built are considered sunk costs²⁶. These costs represent investments that would have been made regardless of UniProt's data hosting and sharing activities.
- The current costs incurred by researchers and institutions to carry out and publish scientific studies – from which UniProt takes data – are considered sunk costs. While these costs are essential for creating the data that UniProt curates and integrates, they are not part of the UniProt consortium's direct financial responsibilities. Researchers would still conduct their studies independently of UniProt, meaning these costs would have been incurred regardless of the existence of UniProt itself.
- The costs associated with feeding, developing, and maintaining the external databases cross-referenced by UniProt are also treated as sunk costs. While one might argue that the benefits derived from these cross-references are not fully accounted for on the cost side, attempting to precisely estimate these expenditures based on rough data could introduce even greater bias. Treating these costs as sunk is seen as a more reliable approach, given that data sharing between UniProt and external databases is reciprocal.

Therefore, the costs included in the CBA analysis are limited to those explicitly recorded in the accounting sheets of the UniProt consortium and the costs attributable to the user community that contributes to UniProt with updates and annotation.

3.2.1. Provider costs

UniProt Consortium incurs two types of costs: setup costs and operational costs, which are described below.

SETUP COSTS

Setup costs refer to the expenses associated with establishing UniProt as a unified knowledge base. These include costs for office acquisition, legal fees associated with the consortium's formation, and expenses for equipment and personnel dedicated to designing the integrated platform. However, historical financial records detailing these initial expenses were either

²⁵ In line with similar assessments. See for instance Beagrie and Houghton 2016; 2021.

²⁶ A sunk cost is an expense that has already been incurred and cannot be recovered or altered by current or future actions.

incomplete or unavailable, making it challenging to accurately quantify the setup costs required to establish UniProt. It is important to note that at the time of UniProt’s foundation, the research group was already based at the EMBL-EBI headquarters and the University of Geneva, and what is now known as UniProtKB (see Section 1.1) was curated by the joint EMBL-EBI and Swiss-Prot teams. This suggests that office and equipment expenses were likely recorded as an in-kind setup contribution (the operational costs do not include any expenditures related to office expenses; see below).

OPERATIONAL COSTS

Operational costs encompass all in-kind contributions and expenditures required to run and maintain UniProt after its initial setup phase. The primary categories of these costs include salaries, travel, equipment, consumables, publications, and overheads. Challenges in reconstructing historical costs from 2003 (the first year of operation) to 2013 have arisen due to archival limitations. Estimating the value of in-kind contributions has proven particularly difficult, as these contributions can fluctuate over time and may apply to any of the cost categories (e.g., senior personnel time, IT infrastructure and related operational costs, high-spec laptops, associated hardware, and computer supplies). The proportion of in-kind contributions relative to total costs varies by category, ranging from less than 1% to fully covering the cost category. The table below shows the costs for the period 2017-2023 (reflecting the period for which data on the number of users are also available; see section 3.1.2 for details).

Table 4 UniProt operational costs

CATEGORIES	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Staff costs	11.4	11.5	11.5	9.1	9.9	10.4	9.8
Travel	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.04	0.1
Equipment	1.1	0.9	1.0	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.5
Consumables and publications	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.02	0.05
Overheads	2.4	2.2	3.1	1.9	2.1	2.3	2.0
Total Operational Costs	16.1	15.6	16.6	13.2	13.9	14.8	13.6

Source: Authors’ elaboration on UniProt Consortium balance sheets data. **Note:** Figures are expressed in 2024 EUR million and cover the period 2023-2017. Original data were provided in USD (referring year) and included both outlays and the value of in-kind contributions.

3.2.2. Users costs

User costs refer to the expenses that users incur both when learning to use UniProt and during its actual usage. Including these costs in the model is crucial to avoid overestimating the benefits users derive from the platform. These costs can be divided into three main categories:

- A. **Training costs:** Time spent learning how to use UniProt.
- B. **Accessing costs:** Time spent accessing UniProt resources, processing data, integrating it into workflows, and conducting research and work activities.
- C. **Community contribution costs:** Time dedicated to actively contributing to UniProt by submitting updates and corrections.

From a cost-benefit analysis perspective, the time invested in these activities represents an opportunity cost. While it does not involve direct financial expenditure, it reflects the value of time that could have been devoted to alternative tasks. The following sections detail how these costs were collected through the user survey and how their monetary value was estimated and incorporated into the CBA.

A. TRAINING COSTS

The first type of user cost relates to the time spent learning how to navigate and use UniProt. Users have several avenues to acquire the skills necessary for the effective use of this platform, including specific training sessions offered by UniProt, which often target particular functionalities. Additionally, some organisations provide training for new employees, while a significant portion of the learning curve is addressed through regular daily practice.

Overall, the user survey indicates that only a small percentage of users (around 10%, regardless of the training type) participate in training sessions, with these individuals often being primarily academics or students (see Box below). This suggests that formal education typically equips individuals with the skills needed to use UniProt effectively. Furthermore, nearly all respondents who have not undergone formal training reported being able to teach themselves how to navigate UniProt through a trial-and-error method using available resources. These findings from the survey were reinforced during semi-structured interviews, which revealed that professionals in the life sciences generally learn the basics during their formal education and typically do not require additional training. Instead, they experience a field-specific learning curve based on experimentation. The interviews also indicated that many job roles in informatics and big data analytics do not necessarily demand extensive prior knowledge of UniProt.

To estimate these costs, we gathered data on the time users invested in training through a survey, categorising it into three groups: (i) training sessions provided by UniProt, (ii) training conducted by the users' organisations, and (iii) hands-on practice. Additionally, to assess these costs, we needed to determine the number of users participating in these training courses. For

this purpose, we relied on data provided by UniProt, as well as information from the users' survey (see Box 3 below for details).

Box 3 Estimating training time and users

(i) Time spent in pieces of training provided by UniProt: Evidence from surveys highlights that the time spent attending the training offered by UniProt is between 30 minutes and one hour. To identify the magnitude of this cost, we relied on the share of users declaring to participate in the different training sources provided by UniProt, either in person or online (see Figure 14). These sources are online tutorials, workshops, webinars, recorded webinars, and YouTube videos.

Figure 14 Time spent per year to attend training courses provided by UniProt

Source: Authors elaborations on UniProt users' survey.

Note: The figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: *On average, how much time do you spend each year on online courses, webinars, etc., provided by UniProt?* The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

Figure 15 Number of training sources attended by users provided by UniProt

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt Consortium data

(ii) Time spent in training conducted by the users' organisations: The distribution is the same as the time spent attending UniProt courses. This time investment is assumed to be a one-time occurrence per user, as, typically, organisations that deliver courses do it for newly hired

personnel. To identify the number of these users, we assume that the share of respondents declaring to have attended training at their organisation was a good approximation of the total number of new users approaching UniProt each year.

Figure 16 Time spent in training organised by user's organisations

Source: Authors elaboration on UniProt users' survey.

Note: The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. This cost is assumed to be a one-time occurrence. Respondents were asked to answer the following questions: *Have you ever received training to use UniProt at your organisation? If yes, how long did it take to complete the training provided by your organisation?* The sample size is 37 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

Figure 17 Number of users attending training organised by their organisations

Source: Authors elaboration on UniProt users' survey.

Note: The number of users is obtained by considering the share of users declaring to have attended a training session in their organisation. The share corresponds to 10% of the total users (presented in Section 3.1.3 above), 8% of the total academic users, and 5% of the total private users.

(ii) Time spent in hands-on practice:

The modal distribution of responses from users indicates that the duration of hands-on practice typically ranges from 30 minutes to one hour. The number of users is assumed to be equivalent to those participating in training sessions at their organisations, as it follows the same logic that

this primarily occurs for newly hired employees.

Figure 18 Time spent in hands-on practice with UniProt

Note: The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: "Based on your experience, how much hands-on practice is necessary to achieve the skills required to efficiently access and use UniProt data?" The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students. **Source:** Authors elaboration on UniProt users' survey.

Source: Authors elaboration on UniProt users' survey and data from UniProt Consortium data

To express the value of the time invested in training in monetary terms, we used the salary equivalent for the time invested as a proxy, as detailed in Annex 1.4. Overall, the average annual training costs were estimated to be 66 EUR per new user. However, for the purposes of the CBA, we assumed that these costs would have been incurred in a counterfactual alternative scenario. Consequently, they are considered null in the analysis.

B. ACCESSING COSTS

The second type of user cost relates to the time spent accessing and downloading data from the UniProt platform in various ways, the time needed to integrate that data into workflows, and the time spent on work and research activities involving UniProt.

Similar to the training costs, the time invested in these tasks was collected through a user survey. The data gathered indicates that user responses are predominantly concentrated in the shortest time range, with less than 15 minutes typically required to access the data, regardless of the access method. Integration of the data takes longer; however, approximately 85% of respondents reported spending between less than 15 minutes and 1 hour on this task. In terms of working time, the survey shows a more varied distribution, with around 24% of respondents at each of the two extremes. This variation arises from the specific ways in which UniProt resources are utilised, which depend on factors such as the type of data accessed and the nature of the research being conducted. For example, usage patterns differ by field: bioinformatics tends to involve intensive data use, whereas drug development experiments vary in data requirements depending on the experiment's phase (see Figures below).

Figure 19 Time spent in accessing, integrating, and working with UniProt data

Working time spent with UniProt data in a week

Source: Authors elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The top chart shows the distribution mode of respondents for a single access, while the bottom chart refers to the time spent in a week. Users' respondents were asked to answer the following question: How long does it take to (i) access the most frequently used UniProt resources, considering the average time for one access; (ii) process the data gathered and integrate it into the workflow, also considering the average time for one access; and (iii) work with the most commonly used resources, based on the average time spent over a week of work. The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

To express the value of the time invested in accessing and using UniProt in monetary terms, we used the salary equivalent for the time spent as a proxy, as outlined in Annex 1. Overall, these costs were estimated to be 23 EUR per user per access and 32 EUR per user per week. For the

purposes of our analysis, this cost was not empirically computed because it has already been incorporated into the time savings calculated from the benefit side²⁷.

C. COMMUNITY CONTRIBUTION COST

Community contribution costs refer to the time and effort users invest in maintaining, improving, or enhancing UniProt resources. From a CBA perspective, even though community contributions are voluntary, they require a certain level of effort, expertise, and resources from users that could have been allocated to other tasks. Therefore, these costs are considered an opportunity cost. They are not limited to the initial phase of using UniProt, as they occur throughout its usage. Consequently, they are classified as operating costs linked to the maintenance of UniProt resources and their continuous updates.

Similar to the training and accessing costs, evidence of community contribution costs has been gathered from user surveys. Responses indicate that the time spent submitting an update or correction to UniProt is typically less than 15 minutes.

Figure 20 Time spent on average to submit an update or a correction to UniProt

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. Respondents were asked to answer the following questions: *Have you ever submitted any updates or corrections to UniProt data? If yes, how long does it take to prepare and submit the update or correction? Please refer to the average time if you are a regular submitter; otherwise, think of the last time you did it.* The sample size is 77, which corresponds to approximately 16% of the respondents declaring that they have contributed at least occasionally to UniProt by sending updates or corrections. Undergraduate and graduate students are excluded.

²⁷ The benefits associated with UniProt (see Section 3.3) are estimated based on time savings, which must be offset by the time each user spends using UniProt to derive the "net" time savings. When conducting the CBA for resources like UniProt, it is essential to include the time spent using the resource as a user cost in the model, as omitting this could result in an overestimation of time savings. In our case, the empirical model does not account for this time because the user survey directly gathered estimates of how much additional time users would require with a hypothetical alternative to UniProt. As a result, the time savings were already reflected in the survey responses.

The number of annotations, protein sequences, and updates/corrections submitted were provided by the UniProt Consortium (see Figure below). Survey results indicate that the contribution rates vary among different user groups: while academic users represent nearly 69% of those who reported submitting at least one contribution, only 22% come from the private sector. This disparity in contribution rates can be attributed to several factors, including the time constraints or non-disclosure issues faced by private sector workers, as well as the greater propensity for patenting within the private sector.

Figure 21 Number of community contributions by year

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt Consortium data. **Note:** The figure corresponds to the total number of annotations, protein sequences, updates, and corrections sent by users.

On average, users spend slightly less than one hour to submit a contribution to UniProt, which is estimated to have a monetary value of approximately 28 EUR per contribution. The total annual cost of these community contributions was calculated by multiplying the value of a single contribution by the total number of contributions made each year. For the entire user population, the average annual cost of community contributions is approximately EUR 7,000. When breaking this down further, the cost for users in the private sector is about EUR 1,000 per year, while for those in the academic sector, it is around EUR 4,000 per year.

3.3. Benefits

As discussed in Section 2, a closer examination of the outcomes and impacts detailed in the IPL of UniProt, only **the short-term outcomes are measured with a cost-benefit analysis approach**. These **primarily consist of efficiency gains**, such as the time saved by users in collecting, integrating, and analysing the data needed for their research. In line with the CBA Open Science framework described by Delugas et al. (2023), we identified three types of efficiency gains associated with UniProt:

- the time saved in carrying out negotiations to access the Open Resources as compared to a closed alternative (transaction cost savings)
- the time saved in accessing the integrated and harmonised information within UniProt as compared to accessing individual information sources (access cost savings)
- the time saved in streamlining daily research and work activities as compared to a situation where additional work of integration should be carried out by individual users (labour cost savings).

Following Delugas et al. (2023), another potential short-term outcome is a saving in data storage costs. These savings refer to the costs avoided by users due to the free access to UniProt, eliminating the need to store data locally or on other systems. In the case of UniProt users, the benefit was considered too marginal for several reasons. Firstly, it is a company-level benefit that might become infinitesimal when attributed to a single worker since it is potentially shared by all users of the company. In fact, the avoided cost of the local storing of data would be proportional to the share of space otherwise occupied by UniProt, and according to interviews, it often represents around 5–10% of the total data stored. Secondly, it would materialise either when users only consult the UniProt website—which is extremely rare and would represent a very small saving in terms of avoided data storage—or when users entirely rely on APIs to access and use the UniProt data, meaning they do not need to store anything²⁸.

To incorporate these efficiency gains in the cost-benefit analysis, we used the value of the stated time savings from the survey as a proxy for the efficiency gains experienced by users. We also considered alternative estimation methods, such as the avoided costs method and willingness to pay through a contingent valuation survey, but we found them impractical for the assessment of UniProt²⁹. The approach of monetising the time saved by users was found to align better with the unique characteristics of UniProt as well as with the approaches used in similar studies (Beagrie and Houghton 2021; Sweeney et al. 2017; Sullivan et al. 2017; Beagrie

²⁸ According to the user survey, the majority of respondents (51%) indicated that their companies use a local system for data storage. Under the 'other' category fell a smaller fraction using a mixed system that combines both their own cloud solutions and locally stored data and those users entirely relying on APIs for their data processing and analyses. The cost savings would involve only the very small fraction of UniProt users. However, according to interviews, the API business model is not without costs, since the company would need personnel to develop and maintain the system (hardware and software), which might result in costs much higher than the savings generated by avoiding paying for cloud services or maintaining local data storage.

²⁹ Applying the avoided costs method would require information on the market price of an alternative to UniProt. However, this methodology was not feasible due to a number of several reasons. First, there is no a unique alternative to UniProt (see Section 3.1.2 for more details). Additionally, there is a scarcity of information regarding (any) fragmented alternatives that do exist. Conducting a contingent valuation survey to gather users' willingness to pay was deemed infeasible, as it may not produce robust results in this particular case. Indeed, eliciting stated preferences must follow a strict and complex protocol to be considered reliable (Johnston et al. 2017). In this instance, randomising a representative sample of users was not possible due to the unknown size of the actual UniProt user population, as there is a lack of tracking. Furthermore, accurately capturing true preferences through contingent valuation necessitates a realistic hypothetical context, an assumption that does not hold true since Open Science is a foundational principle of UniProt.

and Houghton 2014). Overall, it is a widely accepted and straightforward approach for evaluating benefits within the context of cost-benefit analysis (e.g. transport sector).

The application of this approach involved three main steps (see Annex 1 for more details):

1. Estimating the time saved: We assessed the amount of time saved concerning transactions, access, and labour activities compared to alternatives. This information was gathered from the users' survey³⁰.
2. Estimating the value of time: We differentiated the value of time based on the roles and countries of users. Data on yearly salaries was retrieved from sources like Payscale, Glassdoor, and the Economic Research Institute.³¹ They were converted into hourly rates using Eurostat and OECD statistics on weekly hours worked by sector of activity.³²
3. Estimating the benefits: After calculating the average hourly salaries per role, weighted by country, we multiplied the average hourly salary by the estimated time savings to determine the overall benefits.

In the section below, we provide a more detailed explanation of the rationale for including these efficiency gains in our analysis, along with the results of their estimation.

3.3.1. Transaction cost savings

When accessing UniProt resources, users are not required to create an account, nor do they need to engage in discussions about usage types or organisational needs before accessing the data. UniProt's data adheres to FAIR principles and allows for various methods of utilisation, making the data adaptable across multiple fields within the life sciences ecosystem. This openness significantly reduces the time users would typically spend navigating copyright agreements, conducting ad-hoc negotiations for access to specific data, or managing other research-related protocols. As a result, the opportunity cost associated with this saved time translates into the first short-term outcome generated due to using UniProt resources, namely transaction cost savings for users.

³⁰ Respondents to the survey were asked to answer the following question: How much additional time you would have needed in a week for i) making ad-hoc agreements to be allowed to access the data from another entity; ii) finding, accessing the data (and/or tools with equivalent functionality) from another open source and integrating them within the workflow; iii) finding, accessing the data (and/or tools with equivalent functionality) from a paid source and integrating them within the workflow; and iv) recreating the data, yourself / your team; v) performing the work or research tasks in a week without UniProt.

³¹ The social cost of labour is typically distinct from observed salaries. Actual wages can be biased due to distortions in labour and product markets, such as the presence of minimum wages, high unemployment rates, and the existence of informal or illegal sectors. However, for skilled and highly skilled workers who have previously been engaged in similar activities, the shadow wage can often be assumed to be equal to or close to the market wage (EC 2014).

³² Specifically, the country average was employed for the private sector, while public sector and academic sector worked hours were used to calculate the hourly salary of users working in these sectors. All currencies were converted in 2024 EUR prices.

Evidence from the user survey shows that the transaction time saved varies based on the types of data accessed within UniProt, as well as user and organisational characteristics. Many respondents noted that the bargaining time could extend to weeks, if not months, depending on the context. The choices of respondents predominantly fall into three categories of times (see Figure 22): less than 1 hour, 1 to 3 hours, and more than 3 days. This distribution underscores the significant variability in transaction times. However, a substantial portion of responses was categorised as "not applicable," which emphasises the challenges users face in identifying suitable alternatives to UniProt. This finding highlights the unique role that UniProt plays in providing accessible data without the lengthy negotiations typically associated with data access in other platforms.

Figure 22 Transaction time savings per week

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: How much additional time would you have needed in a week to make ad-hoc agreements and be allowed to access the data from another entity? The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

The evidence gathered from users' surveys and interviews suggests the need for a cautious approach in estimating transaction cost savings. Several factors were identified that contribute to the risk of overestimating this benefit:

- This benefit is more relevant to the organisation where users are employed rather than to individual users themselves. It is unlikely that UniProt users would directly bear the cost of negotiating access to a particular data repository or knowledge base. Instead, researchers primarily benefit from avoiding asking their organisation to handle the contracts required for database access, searching for potential alternatives, or completing the administrative steps in submitting a purchase request.
- Multiple users from the same organisation would share this benefit. Therefore, attributing the full benefit to every UniProt user might lead to an inflated estimate of the number of individuals experiencing this efficiency gain.
- The exact number of potential alternatives that each user might need to negotiate with remains uncertain.

- The effort involved in negotiations is generally time-consuming the first time an organisation engages with a new database or platform. However, this effort tends to diminish over time, as processes like automatic renewals often reduce the need for repeated negotiations.

To ensure accuracy and avoid overestimation, we based our calculation on the following assumptions:

- The time saved has been monetised for all new users and across subsamples of new users accessing UniProt.³³
- The benefit generated during one week of work is considered to represent the time saved from negotiating a single UniProt alternative.
- The benchmark for the time spent in a year negotiating a single alternative is assumed to be one full week of work.
- The benefit is applied to a single alternative per new user.

Based on these assumptions, transaction cost savings are measured as the time saved over a year by avoiding negotiations for accessing a single UniProt alternative, which equates to approximately one week of work. For all new users, the average time savings attributed to avoiding these negotiations amounts to about 5.6 hours per new user each year, which translates to a monetary value of 148 EUR per new user per year.

When analysing the subsamples of private and academic users, the amount of time saved remains relatively consistent across the two groups. However, the key difference lies in the value of time, which is notably higher for private-sector users. Specifically, the value of time saved for private sector users is almost 100 EUR higher than that for academic users, reflecting the generally higher salary levels in the private sector compared to academia.

Table 5 Transaction cost savings – estimation results

USER SEGMENT	HOURS SAVED / PER NEW USER	EUR / PER NEW USER	AVG N. NEW USERS	AVG ANNUAL TOTAL BENEFIT
All users	5.6	148 EUR	10,075	1,276 EUR thousand
Private sector users	6.0	210 EUR	2,113	379 EUR thousand
Academic sector users	5.4	120 EUR	7,202	741 EUR thousand

Source: Authors' elaboration of UniProt users' survey and UniProt consortium data. **Note:** All users also include individuals working in public administration, the non-profit sector, and other users. Students are excluded. The average number of users is calculated over the period 2017-2023, and the average total and per person annual benefit is calculated.

³³ The number of new users was estimated by considering the share of users declaring to have attended a training session in their organisation. The share corresponds to 10% of the total number user (presented in Section 3.1.3 above), 8% of the total academic users, and 5% of the total private users.

3.3.2. Access cost savings

As outlined in Section 1, UniProt serves as an integrated platform that consolidates extensive protein sequence and functional information from multiple sources into a comprehensive database. The short-term outcome of this process is access cost savings, which materialise from different channels. The integration eliminates the need for users to navigate through multiple databases individually, saving both time and, in many cases, subscription fees. UniProt's structured organisation further amplifies these access time savings by providing advanced search tools and user-friendly interfaces, enabling users to quickly identify specific proteins and their related data. This approach is significantly more efficient than accessing various sources with differing search functionalities. Additionally, UniProt's regular updates ensure that users always work with the most current and accurate data, reducing the burden of manually verifying the accuracy of the information. However, accurately quantifying these access cost savings requires careful consideration of the following aspects:

- Access cost savings are closely tied to the frequency of UniProt access, which gathers information and integrates the data into workflows. This is because those who access it only a few times per year might save more time per session compared to those who access it more frequently due to the differing ways they utilise UniProt. The user survey (Figure 23) found that 49% of users access UniProt weekly while 26% daily. Only a quarter of respondents indicated that they were accessing UniProt monthly or less than once per month.

Figure 23 Access frequency

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

- Not all interactions with the UniProt platform involve downloading and integrating data into research workflows. Insights from user interviews and discussions with the UniProt team responsible for monitoring web traffic indicate that users engage with UniProt in

diverse ways. Researchers access the platform for various purposes, which depend on factors like the method of accessing and storing UniProt data (e.g., downloading vs API usage), organisational policies on data update frequency (e.g., annual updates), and the specific type of information needed for their research projects. Often, the UniProt website is accessed for quick consultations to obtain specific data points required for particular research tasks. Even users who have previously downloaded extensive datasets via FTP or programmatic access frequently return to the website to retrieve targeted information. This highlights that while bulk data downloads are common, users still rely on the web interface for its efficiency in providing quick, precise answers, making it a valuable resource for both routine checks and in-depth data integration.

- For frequent users, distinguishing between access cost savings and labour cost savings (see Section 3.2.2) can be challenging. By definition, these users regularly engage with UniProt and frequently consult the website for their research needs. As a result, they may find it difficult to clearly differentiate between the time saved in accessing data and the time saved in performing daily research tasks, such as gathering information from the website and integrating that data into their workflows.
- Access time savings vary based on the alternative being considered. As discussed in Section 3.1.2, no single resource serves as a perfect counterfactual to UniProt; different alternatives may exist depending on the specific information the user is seeking. Survey results reveal that when comparing access to UniProt with the alternative of "recreating the data," the largest time savings are reported, with approximately 40% of respondents indicating that this would save them at least one day per week. In contrast, when comparing UniProt with an "Open Access resource," around 47% of respondents estimate savings of less than three hours. Additionally, a significant portion of respondents (about 38-39%) selected "not applicable" for both paid resources and the option of recreating the data.

Figure 24 Access time savings per week by alternative

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: *how much additional time would you have needed in a working week for i) finding, accessing the data (and/or tools with equivalent functionality) from another open source and integrating them within the workflow; ii) finding, accessing the data (and/or tools with equivalent functionality) from a paid source and integrating them within the workflow; and iii) recreating the data, yourself / your team (Please consider only the time strictly necessary to collect and reconstruct the data in the same format you access UniProt resources).*

To ensure accuracy and avoid overestimation, we based our calculation on the following assumptions:

- Access time savings are monetised by weighting the value of time against the frequency of access, recognising that access frequency may vary based on the user's professional role.
- To avoid double counting benefits already included under labour cost savings (see Section 3.3.3), we assign a zero value to users who access the platform weekly or daily. For users who access UniProt monthly or less frequently, the weekly access savings are multiplied by a frequency factor corresponding to the number of weeks during which the benefit is realised.

The results of the time-savings monetisation are reported in Table 6. On average, UniProt saves users approximately six hours per week, which is 176 EUR per week. A user accessing UniProt monthly saves 2,115 EUR per year, while those accessing a few times per year save 529 EUR. The average value of the benefit is higher for those working in the private sector (246 EUR per week) compared to those working in the academic sector (149 EUR per week).

Table 6 Access cost savings – estimation results

	HOURS SAVED PER WEEK	EUR PER PERSON	AVERAGE ANNUAL BENEFIT PER PERSON		AVERAGE N. USERS	AVERAGE TOTAL BENEFIT
			ACCESS MONTHLY	ACCESS LESS THAN ONCE PER MONTH		
All users	6.8	176.3 EUR	2,115 EUR	529 EUR	25,567	39.87 EUR million
Private sector users	6.7	245.6 EUR	2,948 EUR	737 EUR	5,647	12.82 EUR million
Academic sector users	6.8	149.6 EUR	1,795 EUR	449 EUR	17,285	22.91 EUR million

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey and unique visitors user data provided by the UniProt consortium. **Note:** All users also include individuals working in public administration, the non-profit sector, and other users. Students are excluded. The average number of users is calculated over the period 2017-2023, and the average total and per person annual benefit is calculated.

3.3.3. Labour cost savings

The last short-term outcome generated by using UniProt is saving in labour costs. This arises from various daily activities related to conducting work and research tasks. UniProt helps researchers by reducing the time spent interpreting data and cross-referencing multiple sources. By minimising redundancy and providing a unified view of protein information, UniProt enables users to avoid the duplication of efforts often required to reconcile conflicting data from different databases. UniProt includes references to PubMed and other scientific literature, allowing users to access background information and research articles related to specific proteins without the need for further searches. The high level of integration of UniProt into the life sciences ecosystem ensures a high degree of reliability, saving users the time required for data verification and eliminating the need to justify UniProt's credibility to clients or stakeholders.

Users' survey revealed that the most common amount of time saved in performing their work, thanks to UniProt, is more than three days of work per week (about 19%, see Figure 25).

Figure 25 Weekly labour time savings

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: *how much additional time would you need to perform your work or research tasks in a week without UniProt?*

A key challenge in quantifying this benefit was determining the appropriate time frame to consider for each respondent. While employees generally work an average of 48 weeks per year, excluding bank holidays, time off, and weekends, assuming that all users interact with UniProt data at the same intensity year-round would likely result in an overestimation of this benefit. Interviews revealed that individuals working in data-intensive companies or research roles may spend a significant portion of their time on data analysis, management, or tasks facilitated by UniProt, such as research design or literature reviews. In contrast, other users might only utilise UniProt at the initial stages of their research design or for specific tasks that do not encompass their entire workload. Following a conservative approach, some assumptions were made on the maximum amount of time that users might spend during a year working with UniProt. We rely on additional information retrieved from the user survey, namely the time spent by respondents each week on various activities (Figure 26). UniProt users, on average, dedicate a significant share of their weekly time to data analysis and management, while activities such as literature review and software development are less frequent.

Figure 26 Distribution of respondents by weekly time across selected activities

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

To ensure accuracy and avoid overestimation, we based our calculation on the following assumptions:

- Two scenarios were identified based on the typology of activities. The lower bound considers time spent on data analysis and management, while the upper bound includes these activities plus literature review and software development.
- In the lower bound scenario, users are assumed to spend 13 hours per week on activities such as data analysis and management. In the upper bound scenario, this increases to 29 hours per week, including literature review and software development.
- Assuming 48 working weeks per year, this translates to approximately 16 weeks per year for lower-bound activities and 24 weeks per year for upper-bound activities. These factors are then used to calculate the labour cost savings per person per year.

Table 7 Time savings – estimation results

	HOURS SAVED PER WEEK	TOTAL HOURS SAVED PER YEAR - LOWER BOUND	TOTAL HOURS SAVED PER YEAR - UPPER BOUND	AVERAGE N. USERS (2017-2023)
All users	9	146	219	100,549
Private sector users	8	135	203	21,084
Academic sector users	10	153	229	71,879

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey and unique visitors data provided by UniProt consortium.

Note: All users also include those individuals working in public administration, the non-profit sector, and other users

who do not fall into either of the two subsamples: academia or the private sector. Students are excluded. The average number of users is calculated over the period 2017-2023.

Table 8 Labour cost savings – estimation results

	EUR/WEEK PER PERSON	ANNUAL LABOUR COST SAVING PER PERSON – LOWER BOUND	AVERAGE ANNUAL BENEFIT - LOWER BOUND	ANNUAL LABOUR COST SAVING PER PERSON – UPPER BOUND	AVERAGE ANNUAL BENEFIT- UPPER BOUND
All users	243 EUR	3,884 EUR	332.17 EUR million	5,825	524 EUR million
Private sector users	319 EUR	5,098 EUR	91.43 EUR million	7,647	144.23 EUR million
Academic sector users	189 EUR	3,031 EUR	190.03 EUR million	4,547	29.39 EUR million

Source: Authors’ elaboration on UniProt users’ survey and unique visitors data provided by UniProt consortium.

Note: The average annual benefit is calculated over the period 2017-2023.

3.4. Overall results

The Table below summarises the estimated operational costs and benefits for UniProt in a typical reference year. These are presented according to two scenarios—upper and lower bounds—which primarily differ in the calculation of labour cost savings (see Section 3.3.3).

A few important considerations arise from these results:

- Personnel costs incurred by the UniProt consortium account for a significant share (70.91%) of the expenses required to operate this resource. This highlights the unique nature of UniProt, which necessitates a larger investment in personnel.
- Labour cost savings are the most substantial of the three efficiency gains considered in this analysis, while transaction savings result in the least amount of savings and impact the smallest proportion of users. The efficiency gains from labour time savings stem from the ongoing efforts of the UniProt Consortium to enhance the accessibility of UniProt data, improve interoperability, and manually annotate the sequences contained in Swiss-Prot. This sustained effort has contributed to the high level of integration that UniProt resources now enjoy within the life sciences ecosystem. It is also closely linked to the evolving nature of such Open Resources, which have increasingly fostered collaboration and interdependence with other Open Resources over time.
- By comparing the estimated costs and benefits associated with UniProt, it is evident that the benefits significantly outweigh the costs. Specifically, each user experiences **a net benefit ranging from 3,513 EUR** (based on the lower bound estimation) **to 5,475 EUR** (upper bound estimation) in a year. However, it is crucial to interpret these results

accurately; focusing solely on operational costs when assessing benefits may lead to an underestimation of the historical costs incurred over the years. These historical investments, while currently impossible to retrieve or estimate, have played a vital role in generating the current benefits users experience.

Table 9 Overview of results for the total user population

ALL USER POPULATION	LOWER BOUND	UPPER BOUND
COSTS		
Total annual average Operational Costs	14,664,728	
<i>Total staff costs (EUR)</i>	10,403,892	
<i>Other OPEX</i>	4,260,836	
<i>Travel (EUR)</i>	135,377	
<i>Equipment (EUR)</i>	1,455,562	
<i>Consumables and publications (EUR)</i>	69,465	
<i>Overheads (EUR)</i>	2,600,433	
Total USER costs (EUR)	7,381	
<i>Community contribution costs</i>	7,381	
TOTAL COSTS	14,672,109	
BENEFITS		
<i>Transaction cost savings</i>	1,276,382	
<i>Access cost savings</i>	39,870,241	
<i>Labour cost savings</i>	332,166,024	524,000,142
TOTAL BENEFITS	373,312,647	565,146,765
TOTAL NET BENEFIT PER USER	3,567	5,475

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey and unique visitor data provided by UniProt consortium. **Note:** The table reports the average annual values calculated over the period 2023-2017. All values are expressed in 2024 EUR. For total user costs, only the value of community contribution costs was included in the analysis. As explained in Section 3.2.2, training costs were considered negligible compared to alternative scenarios, while access costs were factored into the calculation of access cost savings on the benefit side to avoid duplication and thus were excluded from the total user costs.

It is important to stress that the above results derive from valuing the benefit brought about by UniProt by means of the perceived time saved by users in transaction, accessing and labour activities. Nevertheless, an alternative perspective is to consider the time invested in learning how to use UniProt, in accessing it and in contributing to its update with submissions and corrections (presented as user costs in Section 3.2) - as a proxy of their minimum willingness to pay for such resource (revealed preference as compared to a stated preference method). Essentially, by choosing to invest their time in using UniProt, users demonstrate its value to them.

The minimum willingness to pay for UniProt, estimated using this approach, ranges from 534 EUR (in the lower bound scenario) to 770 EUR (in the upper bound scenario) per user per year.

Notably, these values vary depending on the user's profile. For private users, the willingness to pay ranges from 704 to 1,017 EUR, while for academics, it ranges from 422 to 609 EUR. These differences underscore the different value of the working time across sectors and the different composition of the population attending a large share of the training, specifically for academics, which dedicate much more time in training and submitting contributions compared to private users, although at the very beginning of their career when their salaries are much lower. These differences underscore the varying value of working time across sectors and the differing composition of the population attending a large share of the training, particularly academics, who dedicate significantly more time to training and submitting contributions compared to private sector users, even at the very beginning of their careers when their salaries are much lower. This estimation represents the minimum direct value that UniProt has for its users.

When comparing the costs incurred by users with the efficiency gains they achieve by utilising this resource, we found that the benefits exceed the costs by a factor of seven. In cost-benefit analysis terminology, this is referred to as the benefit-cost ratio³⁴ (see the Table below).

Table 10 Average user costs and benefits, user cost per person

		TOTAL AVERAGE USER COSTS	TOTAL AVERAGE USER BENEFITS	B/C RATIO	USER COST PER PERSON
All users	Lower Bound	53.7 EUR million	373.3 EUR million	7.0	534 EUR
	Upper Bound	77.4 EUR million	565.1 EUR million	7.3	770 EUR
Private users	Lower Bound	14.8 EUR million	104.6 EUR million	7.1	704 EUR
	Upper Bound	21.4 EUR million	157.4 EUR million	7.3	1017 EUR
Academic Users	Lower Bound	30.4 EUR million	213.7 EUR million	7.0	422 EUR
	Upper Bound	43.8 EUR million	316.0 EUR million	7.2	609 EUR

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey and unique visitor data provided by UniProt consortium. **Note:** The Table presents estimates of all costs incurred by users and the user benefits. The benefit-cost (B/C) ratio is calculated by dividing the "Total Average User Benefits" by the "Total Average User Costs." All values represent the average over the period from 2017 to 2023. To determine the user costs per person, we divide the total costs by the average number of users during the period considered. All values are expressed in 2024 EUR.

³⁴ Please note that the benefit-cost ratio shown in the table reflects the user's perspective, as it only considers the costs and benefits directly impacting users. In a typical social CBA analysis, this indicator is calculated by taking into account all costs and benefits, including those incurred by the provider (such as setup and operational costs). In this case, a comprehensive analysis was not possible due to the lack of information regarding the setup costs.

Evidence from the focus groups contributed to validating our results. The time savings estimated from the user survey were largely confirmed by the participants in the first focus group. The mechanism that triggers these significant time savings certainly relies on the integration of protein data with all other information. However, more importantly, it is attributable to the massive manual annotation efforts by UniProt researchers, a task that could not be accomplished by other existing organisations, even with the support of AI technologies. The second focus group was involved in a thought experiment to assess participants' willingness to pay for UniProt, resulting in a minimum consensus WTP of 1,000 EUR per user per year.

Although this quantitative amount is far from being statistically representative of the user community, the minimum amount that individuals declared they were willing to pay prompts two main reflections. Firstly, it provides us with a lower bound of the annual benefit a person might derive from using UniProt. Secondly, the participants did not emphasise a low valuation of UniProt in their reasoning. Instead, they justified their choices based on considerations of equity and fairness. They pointed out that many students rely on UniProt during their studies and would be unable to afford access if it were not freely available. Likewise, researchers from less rich countries or small companies might be unable to afford high costs, even though they would be willing to pay more. Moreover, academics often exhibit a lower WTP due to financial constraints and uncertainty regarding their research grants over time.

Our results also align with other studies investigating the socio-economic value of Open Resources. In the evaluation of three researcher data centres - Economic and Social Data Service (ESDS), the Archaeology Data Service (ADS), and the British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) - Beagrie and Houghton (2014) show that users reported substantial improvements in research efficiency, with benefits ranging from 2 to over 20 times the cost of operating the data centres. Similarly, Beagrie and Houghton (2021) estimated that the use value of EMBL-EBI amounted to approximately EUR 6.5 billion³⁵ per annum, which is 49 times the total operational costs. Their contingent valuation stood at approximately EUR 1.5 billion³⁶ per annum, 11 times the total costs. Similarly, Technopolis (2021) reviewed the impacts of EMBL experimental services, estimating a value of around EUR 17.5 million per year. To make the magnitude of our estimation of net benefit per person more comparable, we recalculated figures based on data reported in two studies. According to Beagrie (2014), the estimated efficiency gain per active user for the three data centres ranges approximately from EUR 2 thousand to EUR 12.3

³⁵ £5.5 billion, converted with an exchange rate of GBP/EUR at 1.18 in the year 2021. retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/procedures-guidelines-tenders/information-contractors-and-beneficiaries/exchange-rate-infoeuro_en

³⁶ £1.25 billion, converted with an exchange rate of GBP/EUR at 1.18 in the year 2021. retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/procedures-guidelines-tenders/information-contractors-and-beneficiaries/exchange-rate-infoeuro_en

thousand.³⁷ In Beagrie (2021), the efficiency gain per user for EMBL ranges from a minimum of approximately EUR 6.7 thousand to EUR 28.8 thousand.³⁸ In Technopolis (2021), the estimated value per external user is approximately EUR 8 thousand.³⁹ Overall, this evidence strongly suggests that Open Resources generate substantial net benefits.

4. Benefits beyond CBA

As shown in the UniProt IPL, the benefits of using UniProt resources extend beyond short-term outcomes, such as the efficiency gains—like time and cost savings—measured through the CBA (Section 3). These benefits may reach further, encompassing what the IPL identifies as *long-term outcomes*, also referred to as *enablement* benefits in Delugas et al. (2023). While they are linked to the use of UniProt, their occurrence also depends on additional user effort and resources, making it challenging to attribute them solely to UniProt, unlike the short-term outcomes. Therefore, the following discussion focuses on describing the characteristics of the IPL long-term outcomes that were, to some extent, measured either quantitatively or qualitatively in the framework of this evaluation. These benefits are all tied to the generation of knowledge. Essentially, UniProt contributes to accelerating scientific research and innovation in various forms, thereby facilitating the creation of new knowledge.

To investigate the long-term outcomes of knowledge creation that can be quantitatively tracked, we carried out publication and patent analyses (Sections 4.1 and 4.2). These analyses showed how the knowledge enabled by UniProt's data contributes, at least to some extent, to the creation of new publications and innovations. To this end, we retrieved information on publications and patents that mentioned UniProt or its resources in their text. More specifically, the following keywords were searched in the titles and abstracts of academic publications published between 2003 and 2022 and in the title, abstract, description, and or claims of patent publications⁴⁰: UniProtKB, UniProt, TrEMBL, SwissProt, Swiss-Prot, UniParc, UniRef, UniRef100,

³⁷ In pound: £1.6 thousand to £9.7 thousand, converted with an exchange rate of GBP/EUR at 1.26 in the year 2014. retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/procedures-guidelines-tenders/information-contractors-and-beneficiaries/exchange-rate-infoeuro_en This was calculated by dividing the total efficiency gains—£68 million to £112 million for ESDS (with 18,098 users), £13 million to £58 million for ADS (11,020 users), and £10 million to £58 million for BADC (5,959 users)—by their respective numbers of active users.

³⁸ In pound: £5.7 thousand to £24.4 thousand, converted with an exchange rate of GBP/EUR at 1.18 in the year 2021. retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/procedures-guidelines-tenders/information-contractors-and-beneficiaries/exchange-rate-infoeuro_en. This was calculated considering a total of 450,000 users and total efficiency gains between £2.6 billion and £11 billion.

³⁹ The report states an average of annual external user of approximately 2,200 from academia and industry.

⁴⁰ See below for details on the timeframe used for the patent analysis.

UniRef90, and UniRef50.⁴¹ The data sources used were OpenAIRE for publications and Lens⁴² and Orbis IP⁴³ for patents.

Two approaches were used to analyse patents. The first narrowed the search to UniProt-related keywords in titles and abstracts of patents filed after the establishment of UniProt, i.e., between 2002 and 2021, while the second extended it to the full text, including descriptions and claims, of patents filed since the creation of Swiss-Prot, i.e., between 1988 and 2022. The narrower approach identified fewer patents than the extended analysis (44,747 vs 78 distinct patent families), but it highlighted the higher value of UniProt resources by focusing on cases where UniProt plays a central role in innovation. Although no causal conclusion can be drawn solely from this analysis, the explicit mention of UniProt in titles and abstracts suggests a strong reliance on its resources, reinforcing its significance in patented discoveries. For completeness, findings from both approaches are detailed in Section 4.2.1 (narrowed analysis) and Section 4.2.2 (extended analysis). Together, these analyses provide a comprehensive view of UniProt's contribution to innovation.

Finally, a segment of innovation can only be discussed qualitatively, as it remains difficult to quantify due to the absence of systematic evidence, unlike cases where innovation can be traced through new publications or the creation of patented goods and services. To this end, we gathered evidence of the most common of these *enablement* (i.e. the establishment of collaborations, contributing to the establishment of spin-offs and start-ups, and enhancing production processes) through the users' survey and interviews (Section 4.3).

4.1. Publication analysis

Between 2003 and 2022, **6,737 publications** referenced UniProt or one of its datasets in the title or abstract while the number raise up to 15,202 if the search is extended to the full text.⁴⁴ As shown in the Figure below, the number of publications has steadily grown over this period, underscoring the platform's increasing significance in scientific research. When UniProt was launched in 2003, 114 publications were published referencing UniProt. In 2022, the number of new publications referencing UniProt had risen to 515, reflecting UniProt's expanding influence

⁴¹ The list of keywords were discussed with UniProt Consortium and reflects the one previously used by EBI-EMBL to analyse UniProt's impacts. Further information are available at https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1aEmSQR9DGOIZmHALuQV9mLv7Mw9Ppkin#scrollTo=ZWtNO2K7QjS_&uqiifier=1

⁴² <https://www.lens.org/>

⁴³ <https://login.bvdinfo.com/R1/OrbisIntellectualProperty> for which CSIL has a licence.

⁴⁴ Publications referencing UniProt or one of its resources were retrieved implementing the following steps: 1) downloading the dump of OpenAIRE data (version December 2023), 2) indexing the data in an in-house ElasticSearch engine at OPIX. It consisted in lowercasing and stemming the text and organising the data based on the fields provided in the OpenAIRE dump, 3) replicating the same analysis for each search term and retrieve the results from the database.

as a trusted source of protein data. A sharp peak occurred in 2020, with 565 articles published, likely due to the surge in global scientific activity spurred by the COVID-19 pandemic, as researchers sought reliable protein data for developing treatments and vaccines. After this pandemic-driven increase, the number of publications referencing UniProt gradually returned to pre-2020 levels.

Figure 27. Number of publications referencing UniProt or one of its datasets over time (2003-2022)

Source: Authors' elaboration

Among UniProt's various databases, UniProt as a whole was the most frequently mentioned between 2003-2022, appearing in 3,601 distinct publications. Following this were Swiss-Prot, with 2,575 citations, and UniProtKB, with 1,119 mentions. In contrast, UniParc was the least referenced, with only 19 publications.⁴⁵ Notably, most publications (87.5%, or 5,893) mentioned only one database, while a smaller percentage (12.5%, or 844 publications) referenced multiple UniProt resources. Of the 844 studies that mentioned more than one database, the most frequent combinations were Swiss-Prot and UniProtKB (270 publications, 32.0%), UniProt and UniProtKB (245 publications, 29.0%), and Swiss-Prot and TrEMBL (238 publications, 28.2%), and Swiss-Prot and UniProt (210 publications, 24.9%). These combinations reflect how researchers often rely on different databases within UniProt to complement their research needs. Figure 27 shows the combination of databases mentioned together. The combination of databases mentioned together in some studies reflects the different strengths of each resource. For example, combining Swiss-Prot and UniProtKB may indicate that researchers are using Swiss-Prot for high-confidence annotations while also leveraging the broader UniProtKB for its extensive unreviewed protein data when exploring uncharted or high-throughput areas of research.

The way researchers mention UniProt databases has evolved over time (see Figure 28). Mentions of UniProt as a whole have grown, reflecting its role as a unifying platform that caters to both manual and high-throughput research. Researchers are increasingly acknowledging the integrated nature of protein data. As scientific research grows more interdisciplinary and data-

⁴⁵ Note that since in some cases the same publication mentioned more than one dataset, the number of publications by mentioned dataset might be double-counted.

driven, many prefer to reference UniProt as a comprehensive resource rather than focus on specific sub-databases, especially when the study involves large-scale data analysis across multiple datasets.

Figure 28 Combination of databases mentioned together

Source: Authors' elaboration

Conversely, Swiss-Prot citations have decreased, likely due to increased familiarity with the integrated UniProtKB, the broader resource that emerged from the merger of Swiss-Prot and TrEMBL. Additionally, this shift may also reflect changes in protein research, where large-scale,

automated data analysis has become more prevalent, favouring the more inclusive UniProtKB, which contains both reviewed (Swiss-Prot) and unreviewed (TrEMBL) entries.

Nonetheless, many researchers still choose to mention Swiss-Prot independently, likely due to its reputation for high-quality, manually curated entries. Swiss-Prot remains a go-to resource for investigations requiring manually curated data, such as studies on enzyme functionality, disease mechanisms, and protein-protein interactions. In fields requiring precise, validated data—such as structural biology or pharmacology—researchers may prioritise Swiss-Prot for its reliability, even though it is technically part of the larger UniProtKB. In other words, researchers in these areas may be cautious about relying solely on automated annotations and prefer the rigour of Swiss-Prot’s expert-reviewed content.

The minimal citations for UniParc (19 publications) likely stem from its specific use case. UniParc stores protein sequence data without annotation, making it valuable primarily for sequence tracking and database integrity rather than for immediate biological insight. This narrow use case may explain its lower citation rate compared to the more comprehensive, annotated resources such as UniProtKB and Swiss-Prot.

Figure 29 Distribution of publication by mentioned resource and year

Source: Authors’ elaboration. **Note:** Publications mentioning more than one resource are fractionalised.

Publications citing UniProt databases span a wide array of fields of science⁴⁶, including agricultural and veterinary sciences, engineering and technology, medical and health sciences, natural sciences, and even social sciences (see Figure 30). This breadth highlights UniProt’s versatility as a data source that is critical not only for life sciences but also for interdisciplinary studies where biology intersects with other domains. Given UniProt’s focus on proteins, it is

⁴⁶ The Field of Science classification is defined in the Frascati Manual (<https://unstats.un.org/wiki/download/attachments/101354089/FOS.pdf?api=v2>). Within this project, the publications mentioning UniProt, or its resources, were classified according to the Field of Science taxonomy using the SciNoBo algorithm as described in Kotitsas et al (2023).

unsurprising that the medical and health sciences represent the largest share of publications. Proteins are fundamental to understanding the molecular basis of diseases and the development of new therapies. Within this field, developmental biology is a key area as researchers investigate the roles proteins play in cell differentiation, organ formation, and tissue regeneration.

Figure 30 Distribution of Field of Science (FOS)

Source: Authors' elaboration

Out of the 6,737 publications citing UniProt, a significant proportion—1,962 publications or **30.8%**—are directly related to the **United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**⁴⁷ (see 30⁴⁸).⁴⁹ This substantial share highlights the growing recognition of protein data's crucial role in addressing global challenges and the increasing integration of bioinformatics and protein research into multidisciplinary fields focused on global development.

Among the SDG-related publications mentioning UniProt, the majority are aligned with SDG 3 (“Good Health and Well-being”), which accounts for 62.9% of these studies (see Figure 31). The strong association between UniProt-related research and SDG 3 is understandable, given the centrality of protein science to medical and health research, as highlighted also in Figure 30. Proteins are fundamental to understanding disease mechanisms, drug development, vaccine research, and therapeutic innovations (Niazi and Magoola, 2024; Jin et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2023), all of which are critical components of SDG 3. The recent surge in health-related research, especially during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, further amplifies this trend. UniProt's extensive protein sequence and functional data provide researchers with the foundational information needed to explore pathogen-host interactions, immune responses, and biomarker identification, which are pivotal in improving global health outcomes.

The second largest group pertains to SDG 2 (“Zero Hunger”), comprising 20.6% of the SDG-related publications. The significant proportion of publications addressing SDG 2—which focuses on ending hunger, achieving food security, improving nutrition, and promoting sustainable agriculture—also reflects the versatility of UniProt's resources (e.g., Peirats-Llobet, 2023). Proteins are central to agricultural research, particularly in understanding the genetics of crop improvement, livestock health, and the development of biofortified foods to combat malnutrition. Studies aiming to improve crop resilience to climate change, enhance the nutritional content of staple foods, or develop pest-resistant plant varieties rely heavily on protein data to analyse the molecular mechanisms that drive these traits. The Swiss-Prot database, known for its high-quality annotations, is particularly useful for research involving genetic modification and biotechnological innovations in agriculture, where precision is key to ensuring successful and safe interventions. As an illustrative example, Baburam and Feto (2021) used UniProtKB and Swiss-Prot data to identify enzymes to treat soils contaminated with pollutants.

⁴⁷ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

⁴⁸ Hereafter ‘SDGs-related publications referencing UniProt and its datasets’

⁴⁹ The identification of SDGs-related publication was made using the SciNoBo classification algorithm. Further details are available at: <http://scinobo.ilsp.gr:1997/toolkit>

Figure 31 Distribution of SDGs-related publications by UniProt resources used and SDGs

Source: Authors' elaboration

4.2. Patent analysis

4.2.1. Findings from narrowed patents' analysis

This section presents findings from the narrowed patent analysis focused on identifying UniProt-related keywords **within patents' titles and abstracts**.

Between 2002 and 2021, **a total of 164 patent applications** were filed that explicitly referenced UniProt or one of its resources in the title or abstract.⁵⁰ These patent applications belong to 78 distinct patent families (see Box 4 below the definition). To avoid double-counting, the analysis considers the priority claim of each patent family, i.e., the first patent application ever filed among those belonging to the same patent family. Out of the 78 patent applications under analysis, 33 patents were successfully granted, reflecting the growing importance of UniProt in scientific innovation.

⁵⁰ Patents referencing UniProt or one of its resources were retrieved implementing the following steps: 1) download from PATSTAT all patents that mentioned UniProt or its resources in the title or abstract, 2) restrict to patents first filed between 2002 and 2021, 3) collapse the resulting database using the earliest filing within the DOCDB patent family.

Box 4 Patent applications, families, publication

A **patent application** is a formal submission an applicant makes to a patent office to request legal protection for an invention, which includes detailed technical information, claims, and any necessary drawings. This application initiates the patent examination process, which assesses the invention's novelty and utility before determining whether to grant a patent. Each patent application belongs to a patent DOCDB family.

A **patent DOCDB family** organises related patent applications from different countries that protect the same invention based on a shared "priority" application, often the first filed. This family structure allows patent offices and researchers to track all versions of an invention globally under a unified group. A patent DOCDB family groups one or more patent applications.

A **patent publication** is the official disclosure of the patent application or granted patent, typically made public 18 months after the initial filing. This publication allows the public to access detailed information about the invention and its legal status, even if the application is still under examination.

The patent application publication is distinct from a granted patent; it refers to a patent application that has been made public but has not yet received approval. **Not every patent application results in a granted patent,** which is the official approval that provides legal protection and exclusive rights to the inventor over their invention. In essence, the publication of a patent application indicates that the application is under review, but it does not confer any legal rights or protection until the patent is granted.

Source: Authors

One could argue that the keyword search limited to the title and abstract of patent applications yields a significantly smaller set of patents compared to a search extended to the full text, e.g., including the description and claims. However, while this narrower approach identifies fewer patents, the results are arguably more relevant: patents identified through this method tend to place higher value on UniProt resources, as evidenced by their explicit citation within the title or abstract. Thus, this focus on the title and abstract ensures that only patents directly emphasising UniProt or its resources are captured, which may enhance the relevance of the findings despite the reduced number of patents.

Based on the analysis of title and abstracts of patent documents, the number of patents remained relatively stable for most of this period, but starting in 2019, there was a noticeable surge in patent filing (see Figure below).

Figure 32 Number of citing patents over time (2002-2021)

Source: Authors' elaboration

Among UniProt's various databases,⁵¹ UniProt as a whole and Swiss-Prot were the most frequently mentioned in patent applications, appearing in 45 and 27 filings, respectively (Figure 32). Additionally, UniProtKB was mentioned in 5 patents, while UniRef and UniRef90 were referenced only once each. No patents during the analysed period (2002–2021) mentioned TrEMBL, UniParc, UniRef50, or UniRef100.

Figure 33 Distribution of patents by resource and year

Source: Authors' elaboration **Note:** Patents referencing more than one resource are fractionalised.

The majority of **patent filings referencing UniProt resources** were concentrated in three major intellectual property (IP) jurisdictions: China (CN), Europe (EP, European Patent Office), and the United States (US) (Figure 33). China led the way with 29 filings, reflecting the country's growing investment in biotechnology, bioinformatics, and related fields. Most patent

⁵¹ UniProt, UniProtKB, Swiss-Prot, TrEMBL, UniParc, UniRef, UniRef50, UniRef90, UniRef100.

applications at the IP jurisdictions in China were filed by universities (21), such as the Zhejiang University of Technology and only to a smaller extent by companies (6).

Europe (EP) followed with 11 patent filings, indicating the strong presence of advanced research institutions and biotech companies across the continent, particularly in countries like Germany, e.g., Roche Diagnostics GMBH, and Switzerland, e.g., Nestec SA. The European market has historically been a hub for pharmaceutical research, biotechnology, and the life sciences, where resources like UniProt play a crucial role in driving innovation. The United States accounted for 10 filings, emphasising its continued leadership in biotechnology and bioinformatics. The U.S. patent filings reflect the robust research ecosystem supported by leading academic institutions, private industry, and governmental research programs.

Figure 34 Patent document jurisdiction

Source: Authors' elaboration **Note:** AU: Australia, CN: China, DE: Germany, EP: European, FR: France, GB: United Kingdom, GR: Greece, IT: Italy, JP: Japan, PL: Poland, RU: Russia, US: United States, WO: World.

UniProt resources have made significant contributions to patents across various technological fields (see Figure 34), with the majority of patents concentrated in Chemistry, followed by Instruments and Electrical Engineering. More specifically, patents citing UniProt resources have largely focused on innovations in Biotechnology. A smaller yet important share of patents citing UniProt data were related to Organic Fine Chemistry, Pharmaceuticals, and Analysis of Biological Materials. Computer Technology is another field in which UniProt data plays a crucial role. Interestingly, the patent data reveals that only a small portion of patents pertained to Food Chemistry. Similarly, there has been limited use of UniProt data in the field of Medical Technology.

Figure 35 Patents' technological fields citing UniProt resource

Source: Authors' elaboration

Beyond the immediate technological fields, **UniProt has had a considerable indirect impact by contributing to additional knowledge creation through patent citations.** Out of the 78 patents citing UniProt resources, 58 were later mentioned by other subsequent patents, creating a patent citation network that reflects UniProt's ongoing influence on innovation (see Figure 10 UniProt Impact Pathways). As depicted in Figure 35, most patents that referenced UniProt resources were mentioned by only one (17 patents, or 29.3%) or two subsequent patents (8 patents, or 13.8%). However, some patents had a far-reaching impact, as illustrated by a 2008 patent filed by Pfizer and Rinat Neuroscience Corp.⁵² This patent, which disclosed various isolated antibodies, has been mentioned by 187 distinct subsequent patents, highlighting how UniProt-enabled innovations can serve as critical building blocks for future developments.

⁵² <https://patents.google.com/patent/NZ591541A/en?q=NZ+59154109+A+20090911>

Figure 36 Network of patent citations

Source: Authors' elaboration **Note:** Each circle represents a patent. Orange circles are the patents that mentioned a UniProt resource, and the blue circles are patents that mentioned the patents citing UniProt. The size of the orange circles is proportional to the number of mentions it received. The direction of the arrows from patents that mentioned a UniProt resource to patents that mentioned the patents citing UniProt show the knowledge flow. Orange arrows highlight that a patent citing a UniProt resource was mentioned by another patent that also mentioned a UniProt resource. Purple arrows highlight that a patent citing a UniProt resource was mentioned by another patent that did not mention a UniProt resource.

The downstream impact of patents citing UniProt resources also reveals an expansion in technological fields over time. While the patents directly mentioning UniProt or its resources focused largely on Biotechnology, Pharmaceuticals, and the Analysis of Biological Materials, evidence shows that in the later stages, they were cited by a growing number of patents that focused on Medical Technologies. This trend, as shown in the figure below, indicates that **knowledge originating from UniProt-related patents has started to influence areas beyond their original technological scope, fostering innovation in a wider range of fields.** Such spillover effects demonstrate the transformative potential of foundational biological data

resources like UniProt in driving long-term technological growth and cross-disciplinary innovation.

Figure 37 Evolution of knowledge creation from UniProt to patents

Source: Authors' elaboration

4.2.2. Findings from extended patents' analysis

This section presents findings from the extended patent analysis focused on identifying UniProt-related keywords **within patent documents, including descriptions and claims.**⁵³

Between 1988 and 2022, **over 183 thousand patent publications** were filed that explicitly mentioned UniProt or one of its resources in the title, abstract, description, or claims. These patent publications belong to 44,747 distinct patent families (see Box 5). To avoid double-counting, the analysis considers the priority claim of each patent family, i.e., the first patent application ever filed among the patent publications belonging to the same patent family. Out of the 44,747 patent applications under analysis, 43.3% of patents were successfully granted, whereas the remaining 56.7% are still pending.

⁵³ Patents referencing UniProt or one of its resources were retrieved implementing the following steps: 1) download from ORBIS IP all patents that mentioned UniProt or its resources in the title, abstract, description, or claims, 2) collapse the resulting database using the earliest filing within the DOCDB patent family.

Over time, the number of patents has steadily increased (see Figure below). This increase can be attributed to a growing recognition of the value of UniProt in fields such as bioinformatics, drug discovery, and biotechnology, where access to comprehensive protein data has become crucial for advancing research and product development. As a matter of fact, UniProt was recognised as one of the GBC Biodata resources.⁵⁴

The slower rate of filings earlier on can be explained by the typically lengthy and complex patenting process, which involves extensive research, legal reviews, and regulatory considerations. Additionally, it may have taken time for industries to fully grasp the potential of UniProt’s resources and incorporate them into commercial applications. The fact that over 19 thousand patents were granted suggests that, over time, innovators were able to demonstrate the novelty and industrial applicability of their inventions, meeting the stringent criteria for patent approval.

Figure 38 Number of patents over time (1988-2022)

a) Number of patents filed by earliest filing year

b) Cumulative number of patents ever published

Source: Authors' elaboration

⁵⁴ SIB news: <https://www.sib.swiss/news/three-sib-knowledge-bases-recognized-as-critical-for-life-science-worldwide>

Among UniProt’s various databases,⁵⁵ Swiss-Prot is the most frequently mentioned in patent applications, appearing in 24,118 patent applications (53.9%). While Swiss-Prot is historically the most mentioned resource, starting from 2016, the number of patent applications mentioning the UniProt database as a whole has exceeded those mentioning Swiss-Prot. As a result, in 2022, 1,980 (46%) mentioned UniProt as a whole, whereas 901 (21%) mentioned Swiss-Prot. This prominence highlights their central role in scientific research, as both databases provide high-quality, manually curated protein information that is essential for scientific and commercial innovation. Additionally, UniProtKB was mentioned in 7,228 patents (16.2%), reflecting its growing importance as a resource for understanding protein sequence and functional data.

In contrast, TrEMBL, UniRef and UniParc were referenced, respectively, in 985 (2.2%), 270 (0.6%), and 121 (0.3%) patent applications (see Figure 38), indicating that their use in patentable innovations may be more specialised or less well-established in this context, possibly due to the specific functions these databases serve. For instance, TrEMBL is automatically annotated and does not offer the same level of manual curation as Swiss-Prot, making it less appealing for patent applications, which typically require highly accurate, curated data. Similarly, UniParc, which serves as a comprehensive protein sequence archive, and UniRef databases, which focus on sequence clustering, might not yet be recognised as critical tools in innovation-heavy industries, or their utility may not translate as directly to patentable inventions. This trend suggests that while some UniProt resources are invaluable to innovation, others may still be in the early stages of being fully integrated into commercially viable research.

Figure 39 Evolution of patents by resource and year

⁵⁵ UniProt, UniProtKB, Swiss-Prot, TrEMBL, UniParc, UniRef, UniRef50, UniRef90, UniRef100.

Source: Authors' elaboration **Note:** Patents referencing more than one resource are fractionalised.

The majority of **patent filings referencing UniProt resources** were concentrated in three major intellectual property (IP) jurisdictions: the United States IP (32.1%), the World Patent IP (20.5%) and the European IP (10.8%) (Figure 39). These filings in the United States, the World Patent IP and Europe highlight the **global scope of UniProt's influence**, as well as the importance of protecting intellectual property in regions that have heavily invested in biotechnology, pharmaceutical research, and bioinformatics.

Figure 40 Patent document jurisdiction

Source: Authors' elaboration **Note:** AR: Armenia, AU: Australia, BR: Brasil, CA: Canada, CN: China, DE: Germany, EA: Eurasian Patent organization, EP: European, ES: Spain, IN: India, JP: Japan, KR: South Korea, MX: Mexico, US: United States, WO: World.

UniProt resources have made significant contributions to patents across various technological fields (see Figure 40), with the vast majority of patents concentrated in Chemistry (95%), followed by Instruments and Electrical Engineering. More specifically, patents mentioning UniProt resources have largely focused on innovations in Biotechnology and Pharmaceuticals. This highlights the pivotal role of **UniProt in advancing cutting-edge biotechnology applications**, such as genetic engineering, protein therapeutics, and diagnostics. These areas form the backbone of modern biomedical research, where reliable, curated protein information is critical for developing new therapies, diagnostic tools, and biotechnological processes.

A smaller yet important share of patents citing UniProt data were related to Organic Fine Chemistry, Food Chemistry, and Analysis of Biological Materials. These fields leverage UniProt's

protein data for applications such as drug development, molecular analysis, and chemical synthesis. While they represent more niche areas compared to Biotechnology, their reliance on accurate protein data underscores **UniProt’s value in experimental and laboratory-based research across a diverse array of scientific domains.**

Computer Technology is another field in which UniProt data starts playing a role. The growing integration of bioinformatics tools and databases like UniProt into computational models demonstrates how essential protein data has become for computational biology and systems biology. These fields often rely on large datasets and sophisticated algorithms to analyse biological information, making resources like UniProt indispensable for innovations in data-driven biological research.

Figure 41 Technological fields of patents mentioning UniProt resource

Source: Authors’ elaboration

Overall, patents were filed by over 10 thousand entities, including mainly companies and universities. The number of patents filed per applicant widely varies across filing organisations, and the number ranges from 1 to 960. The top five applicants (i.e., filing organisations) are Genentech Inc. (US,960), F. Hoffmann-La Roche AG (CH, 948), Novozymes A/S (DK, 705), Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Medicale (FR, 589), and Novartis AG (574)

Beyond the immediate technological fields, **UniProt has had a considerable indirect impact by contributing to additional knowledge creation through patent citations.** Out of the 44,747 patents citing UniProt resources, 17,459 were later mentioned by other subsequent

137,363 patent publications that belong to 76,082 patent families, creating a patent citation network that reflects UniProt's ongoing influence on innovation (see Figure 10 UniProt Impact Pathways). Interestingly, only 5,264 out of the 76,082 (6.9%) citing patent families also mentioned UniProt or its resources, whereas the remaining 70,818 mentioned patent families that mentioned UniProt without mentioning UniProt themselves.

As in the narrower patent analysis, **the downstream effects of patents referencing UniProt resources highlight a broadening of technological domains over time.** Patents mentioning UniProt or its resources are concentrated in Biotechnology, Pharmaceuticals, and the Analysis of Biological Materials. However, among subsequent citing patents, there was a notable increase in patents related to Medical Technologies and Computer Technology. As illustrated in the figure below, this trend suggests that knowledge derived from UniProt-related patents is extending beyond its original technological boundaries, fostering innovation across diverse fields. These spillover effects underscore the significant role of foundational biological data resources like UniProt in promoting long-term technological advancement and interdisciplinary innovation.

Figure 42 Evolution of knowledge creation from UniProt to patents

Source: Authors' elaboration

4.3. Other enablement benefits

Qualitative evidence from user surveys and interviews suggests that UniProt contributes to innovation by supporting the development of new products, services, processes, and ideas that improve upon existing solutions. However, these contributions are not always captured by traditional outputs such as publications or patents (as discussed in previous sections). Survey respondents noted that UniProt facilitates collaboration between industry and academia. While a small percentage of users reported they could not have proceeded without UniProt, a larger share indicated they would have experienced significant delays in their work. Similar feedback emerged regarding the drafting of research publications and the development of processes, products, and services, pointing to UniProt’s practical relevance in these contexts (see Figure 42). Box 5 provides specific examples of products or services developed using UniProt data.

Figure 43 What if UniProt did not exist?

Source: Authors’ elaboration on UniProt users’ survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents and excludes undergraduate and graduate students. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: *In a scenario without UniProt, how would you be able to carry out the following activities within your organisation?* Percentage labels are displayed only for values above 3% to enhance readability.

A significant aspect to consider is the role of UniProt in supporting the emergence of spin-offs and start-ups within the life sciences sector. This sector is typically characterised by an ecosystem of SMEs and start-ups focused on knowledge production, many of which exist primarily to provide services to other companies. These firms often face constraints in

accessing highly skilled researchers capable of advanced knowledge production and thus rely on collaborations with other SMEs to support innovation or to carry out analysis and modelling based on complex research data. Unlike patents or academic publications, these contributions are difficult to trace and are often considered "silent" inputs to innovation. Nonetheless, both interview evidence and survey feedback suggest that UniProt plays a meaningful role for several of these organisations. Many report a substantial reliance on Open Data, with UniProt representing an estimated 5–10% of their overall data pool. In a few cases, companies have indicated that their services are heavily reliant on UniProt, and in some instances, its data has been central to the business model from the outset.

Box 5 Examples of products and services developed using UniProt data

We conducted a text analysis of the open-ended responses to the users' survey question: 'Please provide an example of product or service development for which having access to UniProt was crucial' in order to identify and present a few examples of the most common products and services developed by the respondents (in the IPL, *long-term outcomes* not otherwise identifiable). The results were as follows:

Proteomics tools and services (e.g. mass spectrometry platforms, protein identification tools)

Bioinformatics software and algorithms (e.g. functional annotation tools, protein structure prediction, machine learning models)

Specialised databases (e.g. UniProt-integrated resources, domain-specific protein databases)

Drug discovery tools (e.g. target identification platforms, structure-based design tools)

Functional and structural protein analysis (e.g. target selection tools, protein processing analysis)

Genomic and genetic research tools (e.g. gene expression analysis platforms, variant interpretation tools)

Educational and scientific outputs (e.g. training materials, scientific publications)

Biotechnological applications (e.g. recombinant protein expression systems, antibody production)

Data integration and interoperability services (e.g. identifier mapping, data harmonisation tools)

Web-based applications (e.g. online portals offering protein-related data)

Research support tools (e.g. experimental planning aids, workflow management tools)

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey.

5. Conclusions and lessons learnt

5.1. Conclusions

This case study aimed to test the cost-benefit analysis framework tailored by Delugas et al. (2023) to assess Open Science projects and practices. To carry out this analysis, we relied on a comprehensive set of qualitative and quantitative methods for data collection and analysis. Primary data on costs and usage were obtained from the UniProt Consortium, while information on users was gathered through a user survey. Additional qualitative insights emerged from numerous interviews and focus groups conducted throughout the analysis, which helped validate our findings.

The analysis started with the construction of the impact pathways framework - based on Dekker, Karasz et al. (2023)—to illustrate how the funding and resources provided to UniProt (inputs) lead to direct user benefits (outputs and outcomes) and drive advancements (impacts) in science, the economy, and society. This allowed us to identify both short- and long-term outcomes, as well as wider socio-economic impacts, associated with UniProt and sketch the main UniProt Impact Pathways Logic.

The CBA was employed specifically to evaluate the short-term outcomes UniProt provides to its users, such as time and cost savings. However, a broader causal pathways analysis was used to assess long-term outcomes, acknowledging that these outcomes often involve multiple contributing factors, making it difficult to establish a direct causal link to UniProt. Specifically, UniProt's long-term outcomes were tracked through patent and publication analyses, while other outcomes—such as the emergence of startups—were identified using more qualitative evidence sources, including interviews and user surveys.

It was not possible to carry out a full-fledged CBA for UniProt due to challenges in reconstructing setup and operational costs prior to 2017. Nonetheless, we applied the CBA approach to assess whether UniProt's benefits outweighed its operational costs over the 2017–2023 period. **This comparison revealed the 'net' benefits that UniProt delivers to its users. Key findings from this analysis can be summarised** as follows:

- **Highly labour-intensive initiative:** while it avoids the expenses related to constructing physical facilities, UniProt demands a larger investment in personnel. Indeed, personnel costs incurred by the UniProt consortium account for a significant share (70.91%) of the expenses required to operate this resource.
- **User Community Costs for know-how development:** UniProt entails certain costs for the user community. First, users invest time in learning the platform, which represents a training cost that can take various forms. Additionally, they spend time using the

resources and efforts in community contributions, such as submitting corrections, updates, and new protein sequences to enhance the UniProt database.

- **Significant efficiency gains for the users community:** The primary short-term benefits of UniProt use consist of efficiency gains, which translate into time and cost savings. Three main types of efficiency gains were identified: (i) reduced time spent in negotiating access to alternative data sources (transaction costs savings); (ii) more efficient access methods provided by UniProt compared to multiple, fragmented resources (access cost savings); (iii) time saved in work and research activities (labour costs savings), enabling significantly more efficient processes than alternative options. Labour cost savings represent the most significant of the three efficiency gains examined in this analysis. These savings arise from the continuous efforts of the UniProt Consortium to improve the accessibility of UniProt data, enhance interoperability, and manually annotate the sequences included in Swiss-Prot.
- **Positive Net Benefit:** The results of the cost-benefit analysis indicate that UniProt's net benefit far exceeds the annual investment required to maintain the resource. Specifically, each user experiences a net benefit ranging from 3,513 EUR (based on the lower bound estimation) to 5,475 EUR (upper bound estimation) in a year.

Beyond the short-term outcomes, UniProt plays an **important role in accelerating scientific research and innovation in various forms, thereby contributing to the creation of new knowledge**. To explore the long-term outcomes of knowledge generation associated with UniProt, we complemented the CBA findings with a publication and a patent analysis. These analyses evaluated how the knowledge enabled by UniProt's data contributes to the production of new publications and innovations. **These analyses examined how data provided by UniProt supports the development of new research outputs and innovations.** The results indicate a positive contribution: UniProt and its resources have been cited in over 15,200 scientific publications and referenced in more than 183,000 patent documents across 44,747 distinct patent families. Furthermore, 164 patent applications explicitly mention UniProt or its resources in the title or abstract, suggesting a central role in certain patented innovations. Additional long-term effects—such as the facilitation of collaborations between academia and industry, and the emergence of new entrepreneurial ventures (including spin-offs and start-ups)—were also reported through user surveys and interviews, even if these impacts are not directly captured in publications or patent records.

Overall, employing the CBA approach to estimate the net value generated by UniProt for society—capturing its short-term outcomes—enabled the measurement of user efficiency gains that are typically intangible and difficult to quantify directly, such as the time researchers save thanks to expert curation and integrated data management. In this respect, the estimated value highlights that the true worth of Open Resources lies not merely in their openness, but also in their structure and meticulous curation. These features enhance data usability, reduce

research duplication, and ultimately accelerate scientific discovery, thereby justifying continued investment and reinforcing the socio-economic relevance of UniProt.

5.2. Lessons learnt

This case study has also necessarily shed light on the methodological and conceptual challenges inherent in evaluating Open Resources. While the issues encountered are grounded in the specific context of UniProt, they are representative of a broader set of difficulties relevant to similar open infrastructures embedded in comparable ecosystems. These insights are summarised below:

1. **While estimating individual users of Open Resources presents challenges, meaningful progress is possible with thoughtful approaches beyond simply improving data access.**

Open Resources like UniProt do not typically monitor individual usage. Demand must be inferred from web metrics such as unique IP visits. Yet these metrics are inherently flawed: a single IP may represent multiple users, and a single user may generate multiple IP addresses. Automated traffic further distorts figures. Addressing this requires robust correction mechanisms that must be adapted to each resource's specific features.

→ *OS resources that want to implement CBA assessment protocols should incorporate standardised for adjusting web traffic data, drawing on established benchmarks, and considering collaborative arrangements with infrastructure providers to improve the granularity and accuracy of usage metrics.*

2. **Secondary users of Open Resources are diverse and not always directly traceable, yet they play a critical role in the broader research ecosystem.** Two distinct categories emerge:

- *Cross-reference beneficiaries*, such as those using Gene Ontology annotations supplied by UniProt, form part of an interdependent ecosystem. This reciprocal exchange of data is crucial for the advancement of biomedical science, as the entire ecosystem depends on data sharing and reuse. For cost-benefit analysis purposes, these secondary users will be considered balanced or "cancelled out" since they are present on both sides of the equation.
 - *Indirect beneficiaries* of services built on UniProt data cannot be ignored, as their gains are additive. Although these users are difficult to identify comprehensively, partial tracing is achievable through data collection from direct users. In practice, this results in a conservative, lower-bound estimate of the Open Resource's total user base.
- *When multiple layers of users are present, and it is considered relevant, OS resources that want to implement CBA assessment protocols should invest in mapping value chains of data*

reuse and encourage data intermediaries to collect and share metadata on downstream use, which can help capture secondary impact layers more systematically.

3. Establishing an appropriate counterfactual is not straightforward but essential.

Estimating the incremental value of openness requires a clear counterfactual scenario. For UniProt, this meant rejecting a universal “closed” counterfactual, which lacks empirical grounding, in favour of scenario-based comparisons. Rather than estimating the value of openness per se, the analysis compares integrated Open Resources to fragmented, siloed alternatives. However, the door remains open to future studies applying more targeted closed-open comparisons for specific UniProt data types.

→ *When feasible, evaluators' efforts undertaking a CBA assessment of an OS resource should build modular counterfactual frameworks, allowing tailored comparisons across data types, access models, and user contexts to improve the relevance and credibility of valuation results.*

4. Attributing costs to open bioscience resources demands a nuanced, structured approach. Two key characteristics must be accounted for:

- *The value-added dimension:* Open Resources like UniProt incorporate extensive curation and annotation, often relying on distributed user contributions. These contributions must be monetised where relevant for CBA.
 - *Collaborative production models:* Most open bioscience resources emerge from extensive collaboration. To ensure a balance between costs and benefits, the analysis must account for these collaborations and the types of contributions provided without double-counting historical or sunk costs. Financial and in-kind contributions related to the ongoing operation of the resource are within scope; historical and routine expenditures unrelated to data sharing are not.
- *To improve cost estimation, funders and operators of OS resources that want to implement CBA assessment protocols should carefully keep track of the financial flows related to the open project from the very beginning of the project, also maintaining disaggregated cost reporting structures overtime that distinguish between operational and in-kind contributions—facilitating more accurate impact assessments.*

The publication and patent analysis of UniProt also yielded critical operational lessons:

5. Tracking usage in scientific literature and patents is indispensable and presents an opportunity to harness AI-powered tools for more effective, scalable analysis.

Drawing on the UniProt publication and patent analysis, key lessons have emerged that should inform and improve future applications of these methods—especially as AI capabilities continue to advance.

- Since internal usage tracking is not available, a dual-method strategy combining surveys and keyword-based searches is essential. While surveys provide valuable direct insights, they have limitations such as incompleteness and self-reporting bias. Conversely,

carefully designed and refined keyword searches enable broader coverage and scalability, especially when enhanced by AI-driven text mining and natural language processing techniques. Meticulous keyword selection is critical to minimise false positives and maintain relevance.

- Similarly, search parameter choices materially affect the quality and breadth of results. Full-text searches maximise coverage but risk including marginal references; abstract/title searches yield fewer but more relevant results. Combining both approaches might be preferred to strike a balance between breadth and depth, ensuring that both frequent and significant uses are captured.
 - ➔ *To facilitate this type of analysis, OS resources should put effort into developing a harmonised keyword system and exploring automated tools for continuous tracking of citations across publications and patent databases. At the same time, evaluators conducting patent analysis should always report the sensitivity of their findings to search strategies and adopt layered search techniques to distinguish between different degrees of use cases.*

6. Quantifying causal impact requires more than citation counts but bring robustness in the analysis.

While usage statistics provide evidence of reach, they fall short of demonstrating UniProt's contribution to innovation. Causal inference requires user feedback via surveys and interviews to contextualise usage and understand how critical UniProt data were to scientific and technological outputs. Without this, the value attributed to UniProt risks being overstated or mischaracterised.

- ➔ *OS resources aiming to implement impact assessment protocols should integrate causal evaluation tools into project cycles. This includes using tailored surveys to gather both quantitative and qualitative data for building causal inference models, as well as incorporating case studies and user narratives as standard elements of performance assessments.*

7. The selection of the unit of analysis in patent analysis critically shapes conclusions.

Whether one counts patent applications, publications, families, or priority claims alters the inferred magnitude of impact. Broader units, like applications, can exaggerate influence, narrower ones, like families, risk underrepresenting dissemination. The choice must be justified and aligned with the analysis objective, ensuring analytical rigour and interpretive clarity.

- ➔ *Evaluators conducting patent analysis should predefine units of analysis based on the policy question at hand and, where feasible, triangulate results across units to validate findings and reduce bias.*

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Annexes

1. Methodological toolkit

The assessment presented in this deliverable draws upon a comprehensive and multi-dimensional methodological approach that integrates both primary and secondary data sources, as well as qualitative and quantitative analytical techniques. The objective was to produce a robust, evidence-based evaluation of UniProt's value and impact. The methodological toolkit comprises a set of interconnected components, each offering distinct but complementary insights. Desk research provided the foundation for mapping impact pathways, stakeholder groups, and evaluation approaches. Web traffic data were used to estimate the scale of the user base to be used in the CBA model. The user survey offered detailed information on usage patterns, perceived value, user benefits that are not otherwise quantifiable, and scenarios without UniProt. Time monetisation enabled the quantification of short-term benefits and user-incurred costs for the CBA. Semi-structured interviews and focus groups added qualitative depth and served to validate the findings, while citation and patent analyses offered insight into the longer-term scientific and innovation-related impacts.

The sections that follow present each methodological component in more detail.

A.1.1 DESK RESEARCH

Desk research was the first step of the assessment and was conducted by using academic paper, policy reports, and other grey literature. It pursued a manifold objective and focused on three different strands of literature to inform the assessment:

- 1. Historical and performance analysis.** It related to the history, gradual development, usage, and performance of the resources under assessment, along with their individual components. This review was essential for identifying the impact pathways associated with these resources, mapping the diverse types of stakeholders that potentially benefit (e.g., the scientific community, PhD students, private sector, funding agencies, and government bodies) and outlining all stakeholders involved in the financing and operation of these resources.
- 2. Impact evidence.** This component reviewed the publicly available evidence regarding the impacts of UniProt, including prior evaluation studies and internal materials (e.g., survey results). The objective was to take stock of existing evidence and build upon it to inform the current assessment.
- 3. Methodological framework.** The literature related to the evaluation of similar Open Resources was consulted to refine and enhance the methodological framework employed for assessing UniProt, ensuring that best practices and lessons learned from similar evaluations were incorporated into the analysis. Some examples of relevant literature consulted in this phase include: Beagrie and Houghton 2021; 2016, 2014;

Koudouri et al. 2021; Sweeny et al. 2017; Sullivan et al. 2017; Lauer et al., 2021; Garcia et al., 2018 Klebel et al 2024; Fell, 2019.

A.1.2 ANALYSIS OF THE WEB TRAFFIC DATA.

In general, Open Resources—such as UniProt—do not monitor individual users directly. As a result, any estimation of user demand must be inferred from web traffic data, specifically by counting the number of unique visitors identified through IP addresses accessing the resource. However, as widely acknowledged in the literature (e.g. Ross et al., 2024; Beagrie and Houghton, 2021, 2016; Fomitchev, 2010), there are important limitations to this approach. Unique visitor counts may not correspond accurately to actual user numbers, as multiple individuals (e.g. researchers from the same institution) may share a single IP address, while a single user may appear under several IP addresses (e.g. due to access from different locations, multiple devices, or dynamic IP allocation by internet service providers). Moreover, such counts may include automated visits by bots or web crawlers. It is therefore necessary to apply appropriate methods to estimate the number of actual users from raw web traffic data.

To estimate the number of users, we relied on statistics from browser and programmatic access provided by UniProt consortium (reported in Figure 2, Section 1), as these provide a more complete and accurate estimation of the user base. Following the methodology proposed by Beagrie and Houghton (2021), the following steps were adopted:

1. *Adjustment for COVID-19 Effect for the year 2020.* The browser and programmatic access data are available for the period from 2019 to 2023 due to legal requirements (see Figure 2). This five-year trend reveals a significant peak in 2020, likely attributable to the increased use of multiple devices for accessing UniProt. To account for this COVID effect, we followed the approach suggested by Beagrie and Houghton (2021), allowing the 2019 figure to grow by only half (7.5%) of the registered increase (15%).
2. *Reduction for Overestimation.* Fomitchev (2010) reports that unique IP addresses and unique cookie counts overestimate unique visitors by a constant factor that increases linearly with the duration of sampling. This overestimation can reach up to 80 times within a year. As a result, our second adjustment involved conservatively reducing the annual count of unique visitors by a factor of 80.
3. *Adjustment for Unregistered Access.* A very small fraction of users accesses UniProt in ways that are not registered by data logs, such as via FTP or certain APIs.⁵⁶ Following Beagrie and Houghton (2021), we applied a correction factor of 2.5% per year to represent this proportion of users.
4. *Estimating the number of users for 2018 and 2017 years.* Since our analysis covered the period from 2017 to 2023 and browser and programmatic access data was only available

⁵⁶ FTP refers to File Transfer Protocol and is a method for moving files between computers on a network, while API indicates Application Programming Interface that is a set of rules or protocols that enables software applications to communicate with each other.

from 2019, we needed to estimate the number of users for the years 2017 and 2018. This estimation was conducted by applying the growth rate derived from the browser access data, which was available for the period 2017-2023, to the browser and programmatic access data.

Our calculations yield an average of approximately 107,000 users per year over the period 2017–2023. We have also compared our estimates to external sources to triangulate the reliability of our results, following the comprehensive approach of Beagrie and Houghton (2021, 2016). The 2021 UNESCO Science Report estimates that, by 2018, there were 8.854 million full-time equivalent (FTE) researchers worldwide. Beagrie and Houghton (2021) applied a factor of 25% to estimate the number of FTE researchers in the life sciences, based on Australian R&D expenditure data disaggregated by field of science. Using this method, the potential number of FTE researchers in the life sciences globally is approximately 2.2 million. This figure represents the maximum potential user base of UniProt, bearing in mind that not all of these researchers focus on protein-related topics. Our user estimate thus represents around 5% of this potential base, and should be interpreted as a lower-bound estimate.

A.1.3 USER SURVEY

It was addressed to gather deeper insights into user profiles (i.e. age, professional background, etc.), the purposes for which they use the resources (including any other sources used in conjunction), existing alternatives (if any), and primary data on the perceived value of these resources. The survey was implemented using the EUSurvey tool.

The questionnaire was structured in four sections: Section A – General Information: it investigated respondents' profile (e.g. country of work, professional status, sector of activity, research fields/job details, etc); Section B – Experience with the resources: it investigated on the usage of the resources (e.g. frequency, combination with other sources, etc); Section C – the value of the resource: it included questions investigating the time spent in accessing the resource, processing and work with it as well as the additional time that it would have required to manage agreement, access, process and work with alternatives; Section D – Overall opinion: it collected views on the importance of the resource and examples of innovations developed.

The survey was disseminated through UniProt, EMBL-EBI, SIB, and ELIXIR websites, social media, newsletters, and industry programmes. A few pilot tests (5-6) were conducted with selected users to gather feedback on the questionnaire's clarity. Overall, 558 responses⁵⁷ were collected between 26th March and 6th May 2024.

Since the characteristics of the user base population are entirely unknown—apart from the global geographical distribution of users inferred from web traffic data—it was decided not to adopt a probability sampling approach. Instead, a thorough ex-post analysis was carried out,

⁵⁷ Out of 558 respondents, 38 never used UniProt and 10 are former users. Additionally, one respondent abandoned the survey. Therefore, the final sample considered to support this assessment includes 509 complete responses.

comparing the distribution of respondents by country with that of web traffic data, alongside a comparison of respondents' sectors of activity and primary research fields with statistics from desk research based on publications and patents.

Given the close alignment between the country-level composition of survey responses and that of the web access data, as well as the consistency in terms of research fields and economic activities and supported by constructive discussions with the UniProt consortium to validate the comparison, we consider the survey sample to be sufficiently reliable for use in the subsequent cost-benefit analysis, including with respect to other user characteristics.

Nonetheless, certain limitations of the approach should be acknowledged. First, the absence of a defined sampling frame and the reliance on voluntary participation introduce potential self-selection bias, as those more actively engaged with the resource may have been more inclined to respond. Moreover, given the dissemination channels used, the sample is likely to be more representative of users based in Europe, the United States, and other countries where UniProt is most widely used. Second, although efforts were made to validate the representativeness of the sample through comparisons with web traffic data and desk research, unobservable differences may still limit the generalisability of the findings.

A.1.4. ESTIMATING THE VALUE OF TIME

The monetisation of time represents the core methodological approach adopted to quantify the short-term outcomes associated with the use of UniProt resources, specifically in terms of cost savings. The monetary value of time was estimated using data from the user survey on reported time savings, combined with hourly wage estimates by professional role and country. These wage estimates were drawn from a combination of sources, including Payscale, Glassdoor, and the Economic Research Institute—three commercial databases offering publicly accessible benchmarks for a wide range of job titles. In addition, Eurostat and OECD statistics on average weekly hours worked by sector were used to convert annual salary figures into hourly rates.

The approach adopted to monetise the value of time—from both cost and benefit perspectives is the following.

The first step involved **quantifying the average time per person for each benefit or cost** as follows:

Let f_{iq} be the absolute user frequency for each time range i of the question q .

Let v_{iq} be the central value of each time range i of the question q .

Let N_q be the total number of non-missing answers for the question q .

The total weighted hours T_q used or saved can be calculated as:

$$T_q = \sum_i f_{iq} \times v_{iq}$$

The average hours saved or used per respondent \bar{t}_q is then:

$$(1) \quad \bar{t}_q = \frac{T_q}{N_q} = \frac{\sum_i f_{iq} \times v_{iq}}{N_q}$$

The second step involved **quantifying the most conservative hourly salary** associated with each \bar{t}_q .

Once obtained the hourly salary by role⁵⁸ and country by means the salary benchmarks, we computed a country-weighted hourly salary by role as follows:

Let C be the set of countries of survey respondents.

Let $S_{j,c}$ be the average hourly salary for role j in country c

Let f_c be the 2019-2023 average relative frequency of unique visitors by country c .⁵⁹

Let R be the set of roles proposed by questions A2.1 and A2.2.

The average weighted hourly salary by role \bar{S}_j can be calculated as:

$$\bar{S}_j = \frac{\sum_{j \in R} \sum_{c \in C} S_{j,c} \cdot f_c}{\sum_{c \in C} f_c}$$

The average weighted hourly salary by role \bar{S}_j has then been used to obtain the value of each \bar{t}_q . Instead of computing the median or average hourly salary across the roles to monetise all the different costs and benefits, we allow the value of time to vary based on the user's frequency distribution. This approach takes into account that different job profiles may use UniProt with varying intensity and frequency of time, thus causing the time to have a different value.

For each question q :

Let \bar{S}_j be the weighted salary mean for role j .

Let $f_{j,tq}$ be the role frequency for a range of time t for the question q .

Let T_q be the set of time ranges for the question q .

For each question q , the weighted salary means by range of time \bar{S}_{tq} is:

$$\bar{S}_{tq} = \frac{\sum_{j \in R} \bar{S}_j f_{j,tq}}{\sum_{j \in R} f_{j,tq}} \text{ with } t = 1, 2, \dots, T$$

The final hourly salary for each question q is the more conservative figure between the median \bar{S}_q or the average \bar{S}_q of the \bar{S}_{tq} previously calculated for any of the T_q range of time.

$$(2) \quad S_{bq} = \min(\bar{S}_q, \bar{S}_q)$$

$$(3) \quad S_{cq} = \max(\bar{S}_q, \bar{S}_q)$$

Completed the steps, the value of time for each cost and benefit is computed by combining equations (1) and (2) for the benefits and (1) and (3) for the costs.

$$V_b = S_{bq} \times \bar{t}_q$$

$$V_c = S_{cq} \times \bar{t}_q$$

A.1.5 INTERVIEWS

To complement the information gathered through the user survey, a total of 13 interviews were conducted. The interviews were conducted with selected users from both industry and academia to gather evidence on (i) the purposes for which UniProt is used; (ii) the sources with which data from UniProt are typically combined; (iii) the practices used for the storage of data (locally/ cloud services/open repositories, for how long, etc.); (iv) challenges faced by users in accessing or integrating UniProt; (v) the perceived impact of UniProt on users' research

⁵⁸ The main roles covered by users from academia include: research assistant / postdoc, research fellow / associate, assistant professor / lecturer, associate professor / reader, professor, other. in the private sector, the roles covered by users include: principal investigator, wet lab researcher, computational biologist / bioinformatician, director / manager, analyst, clinician, database curator, consultant, software developer and other.

⁵⁹ Country absolute frequencies are retrieved by UniProt web traffic as explained in Section 1.3

outcomes. The insights gained from these discussions proved valuable in interpreting the survey results and further clarifying and explaining the impact pathways of UniProt.

A.1.6 FOCUS GROUPS

Two focus groups were also conducted to validate and enhance the robustness of the assessment. The first focus group, held on 6th September 2024, aimed to validate the survey results. The second focus group, held on 16th September 2024, focused on eliciting participants' willingness to pay for UniProt through a contingent evaluation survey designed in accordance with the 'NOAA Panel' (Arrow et al., 1993) and the 'Contemporary Guidance for Stated Preference Studies' (Johnston, 2017). The selection of participants relied on contacts provided by survey respondents (a total of 243 contacts) as well as direct contacts from the UniProt consortium and should be understood as qualitative evidence, given the non-random selection of participants.

A.1.7 CITATION AND PATENTS ANALYSES

These analyses were conducted to complement the findings from the CBA and to explore the long-term impacts associated with UniProt. It examined the extent to which the knowledge facilitated by the data provided by UniProt is reflected in new publications and innovations.

It was assessed the extent to which the knowledge facilitated by the data provided by UniProt is reflected in new publications and innovations by analysing references to UniProt and its resources in titles and abstracts of patents and academic publications. To achieve this, mentions of UniProt-related terms—such as UniProt, UniProtKB, UniParc, UniRef (including UniRef50, UniRef90, UniRef100), SwissProt, Swiss-Prot, and TrEMBL — were retrieved for academic publications and patent data. Specifically, for the publication analysis, a search was performed in the titles and abstracts of scientific publications from 2003 to 2022. Data were sourced from OpenAIRE. For the patent analysis, two approaches were adopted. The narrow approach focused on identifying patent applications filed between 2002 and 2021 that mention the same set of keywords in their titles or abstracts, with data sourced from PATSTAT. The extended approach broadened the scope to include mentions in titles, abstracts, descriptions, or claims of patent publications filed since the creation of Swiss-Prot, thus covering the period from 1988 to 2022, using Orbis IP as the data source.

2. Interviews carried out

The following Table reports the round, date, and affiliation of interviewed for each interview carried out.

Table 11: List of interviews

INTERVIEW ROUND	ORGANISATION	DATE
Scoping Interviews	Ontoforce	30/11/2023
Scoping Interviews	Eagle Genomics	05/12/2023
Scoping Interviews	EMBL-EBI	15/12/2023
Scoping Interviews	EMBL-EBI	19/12/2023
Scoping Interviews	Roche	19/12/2023
Value and Impacts	Knowing01	29/04/2024
Value and Impacts	Saphetor	29/04/2024
Value and Impacts	Gencoverly	07/05/2024
Value and Impacts	General Bioinformatics	22/05/2024
Value and Impacts	Datavisyn	06/06/2024
Value and Impacts	University Hospital of Bern	08/07/2024
Value and Impacts	BullFrogAI	15/07/2024
Value and Impacts	Expert Systems	15/07/2024

Pathos

Open Science Impact Pathways

Deliverable D4.4_ANNEX I

Cost Benefit analysis of Open Science: RCAAP case study

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	24/05/2025	Peer review	Simon Apartis (CNRS) and Vincent Traag (ULEI)
	11/06/2025	Revised Version	Louis Colnot, Gelsomina Catalano, Silvia Vignetti
2.0	11/06/2025	Approval by coordinator	Ioanna Grypari (Athena RC)

Table 1: Document Revision History

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Authors' contributions:

Louis Colnot (CSIL) carried out the report's overarching analysis, data collection, and draft. Gelsomina Catalano (CSIL) provided overall methodological guidance, contributed to structuring the draft, content, and revision, and ensured alignment with the overall CBA methodological framework and UniProt case study. Silvia Vignetti (CSIL) provided methodological guidance and comments on the drafting to improve quality. Paulo Lopes (FCCN) collected and provided in-depth information on the quantitative data related to RCAAP. Antonia Correia and Pedro Principe provided context for the use case, contributed to the development, translation, testing, and dissemination of the questionnaire, contributed to the impact pathway drafting, supported the interviews and provided additional data on the potential impacts of RCAAP beyond the scope of the CBA. Elisa Seminaroti (Technopolis Group) contributed to the design of the Impact Pathway of RCAAP.

Table of Contents

Disclaimer	8
Abbreviations	9
Executive Summary	10
Introduction	11
1. RCAAP: A single-entry point to Portuguese scientific content 12	
1.1 The architecture of RCAAP	12
1.2 Development of RCAAP	19
1.3 Using RCAAP: how, who, and for what	21
2. Impact Pathway for RCAAP.....	33
3. CBA analysis.....	39
3.1 Setting the analysis	40
3.1.1 Scope of the analysis	41
3.1.2 Counterfactual scenario	42
3.1.3 Users' population.....	44
3.2 Costs.....	45
Provider costs.....	48
Users' costs.....	52
Overview of total costs	58
3.3 Benefits	59
Labour cost savings	61
Data storage cost savings.....	62
Overview of total benefits	63
3.4 Overall results.....	64
4. Benefits beyond CBA.....	67
5. Conclusions and lessons learned	70

5.1 Conclusions.....	70
5.2 Lessons learned	71
References	74
Annexes.....	76
Annex 1: Methodological toolkit.....	76
Annex 2: Interviews carried out.....	80
Annex 3: Focus Group's Composition.....	81

List of Tables

Table 1: Document Revision History	2
Table 2 Costs related to RCAAP	46
Table 3 Overview of results for RCAAP	66

List of Figures

Figure 1. RCAAP Overall Architecture.....	15
Figure 2. Number of repositories aggregated by RCAAP by type (2003-2024).....	16
Figure 3. Number of institutions covered by repositories aggregated by RCAAP by type (2003-2024)	17
Figure 4. Number of documents aggregated by the RCAAP Portal by type of repository (2008-2024)	18
Figure 5. Main milestones of the RCAAP project.....	19
Figure 6. Example of a document made available on the RepositoriUM (aggregated by RCAAP)	21
Figure 7. Organisations of work/study of RCAAP respondents	22
Figure 8. Main functions of RCAAP respondents	23
Figure 9. Academic positions of respondents with a research role	24
Figure 10. Activities performed by RCAAP users.....	25
Figure 11. Number of unique RCAAP Portal users (2008-2024).....	26
Figure 12. Frequency of use of RCAAP for search and download	27
Figure 13. Contribution of content downloaded on RCAAP for the following outputs	28
Figure 14. Modalities of deposit of content to the repositories aggregated by RCAAP.....	29
Figure 15. Responsibilities for uploads in the organisations of respondents	30
Figure 16. Frequency of use of RCAAP for upload	31
Figure 17. Number of deposits to IR aggregated by RCAAP (2008-2024)	32
Figure 18. RCAAP Impact Pathway	38
Figure 19. Costs and benefits covered by the CBA	40
Figure 20. Hypothetical counterfactuals of RCAAP for searching and downloading content....	43

Figure 21. Estimated set-up costs (including reinvestments) by provider in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)49

Figure 22. Operational Costs profile for LOCAL Repositories – Administrative and Management costs by age of repository50

Figure 23. Estimated operational costs by provider in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)51

Figure 24. Comparison of time spent by users to make a deposit on RCAAP-aggregated IR in first use and typical use53

Figure 25. Time spent to upload a piece of content to the IR by function55

Figure 26. Estimated deposit costs by type of users in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)55

Figure 27. Time spent by RCAAP users to search and download content by access modality ..57

Figure 28. Estimated access costs in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026).....58

Figure 29. Overview of total costs in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026).....59

Figure 30. Labour costs savings for providers (2006-2026)62

Figure 31. Data storage costs savings for providers (2006-2026).....63

Figure 32. Overview of total benefits for providers (2006-2026).....64

Figure 33. Net benefits over time (2006-2026).....65

Figure 34. Number of Portuguese scientific documents by presence on RCAAP (2015-2024) ..68

Figure 35. Mean Citations per Document depending on presence on RCAAP (2015-2024).....68

Figure 36. Share of Portuguese scientific documents with industry-academia collaboration by presence on RCAAP (2015-2024)69

List of Boxes

Box 1 What if RCAAP did not exist?42

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Abbreviations

CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CRIS	Current Research Information System
CRUP	Conselho de Reitores das Universidades Portuguesas (Council of Rectors of Portuguese Universities)
EUR	Euro
FCCN	Fundação para a Computação Científica Nacional (Foundation for National Scientific Computing)
FCT	Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (Foundation for Science and Technology)
FTE	Full-Time Equivalent
IPL	Impact Pathway Logic
IR	Institutional Repository
OA	Open Access
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OJS	Open Journal System
OS	Open Science
PathOS	Open Science Impact Pathways (Horizon Europe Project)
RCAAP	Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal (Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal)
RCOMUM	Repositório Comum (Common Repository)
SaaS	Software as a Service
SARC	Serviço de Alojamento de Revistas Científicas (Scientific Journals Hosting Service)
SARDC	Serviço de Alojamento de Repositório de Dados Científicos (Scientific Data Repositories Hosting Service)
SARI	Serviço de Alojamento de Repositórios Institucionais (Institutional Repositories Hosting Service)
SCEUR	Serviço Centralizado de Estatísticas de Utilização de Repositórios (Centralised Service of Statistics on the Use of Repositories)
SDR	Social Discount Rate

Executive Summary

This document summarises the assessment of RCAAP—the Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal. The evaluation combined a tailored Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) to measure short-term, quantifiable impacts with an impact pathway approach to capture RCAAP broader scientific and societal contributions over time.

The CBA focuses on a 20-year period (2006-2026) in order to capture the full lifecycle of RCAAP. On the cost side, the analysis considers the operational and set-up costs borne by RCAAP at the central level, as well as by the different institutions for their repositories. The identified benefits are primarily costs savings due to the pooling of resources allowed by RCAAP. By providing hosting services free of charge to voluntary organisations, RCAAP unlocks labour costs savings (i.e., a single team at the central level can manage several repositories more efficiently than having multiple teams across all the institutions) and data storage costs savings (by sharing servers). RCAAP also probably leads to access costs savings, by making the content of RCAAP more easily searchable and accessible to users, though this was not possible to fully integrate this benefit in the analysis. Overall, the CBA shows a net benefit of EUR 1.1 million for RCAAP over the 2006-2026 period. This implies that the benefits of RCAAP are 32% higher than its costs. This estimate is conservative, meaning that the ratio would probably be better by integrating access costs savings.

Beyond short-term benefits captured by the CBA, RCAAP can support long-term improvements in the academic sector, especially at the national level. At this stage, only a minority (about 40%) of Portuguese scientific publications are available on RCAAP Repositories, but this could improve in the future. Anecdotes from the interviewees suggested that the wider society could benefit from RCAAP in the form of increase knowledge or culture. For instance, patients with specific medical conditions would find relevant content on their diseases on the repositories and even contact the researchers on that basis.

This assessment highlights the complexity of evaluating the impact of Open Science resources like RCAAP. Key lessons include the difficulty to estimate the number of users from web analytics or internal monitoring tools, the challenges to define a credible and robust counterfactual scenario and the difficulties to attribute costs and benefits when the project involves multiple layers of stakeholders. Despite these issues, the analysis confirmed that RCAAP provided some significant benefits to its institutional users (through costs savings). Beyond these core gains, RCAAP has the potential to strengthen the academic ecosystem of Portugal in the longer run, notably if it increases its share of covered publications.

Introduction

The focus of the case study is **RCAAP (Repositórios Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal), i.e., the Portugal Open Access Science Repository**. This Open Science (OS) initiative is designed to enhance the visibility, accessibility, and dissemination of Portuguese research. RCAAP is a network of Institutional Repositories (IR) of several Portuguese institutions aggregated by a single Portal. RCAAP also provides several additional services at the central level to the participant institutions and users. Consequently, RCAAP acts as a single-entry point to Portuguese scientific evidence, including documents and, to a lesser extent, journals and data. It is operated at the central level by the University of Minho and the Foundation for National Scientific Computing (FCCN) – the digital unit of Portugal's national research funding agency (FCT).

The CBA assesses the costs and benefits of RCAAP, compared to a hypothetical situation where the resource would not have developed.

The analysis draws on various data collection and analytical approaches, including:

- Documentary review
- Quantitative data analysis (e.g., traffic, budget...)
- Users' online survey
- Interviews
- Focus group
- Additional data from other work packages of the PathOS project

The methodological approach is described in greater details in annexe 1.

The findings of this report are structured as follows: Section 1 introduces the RCAAP system, including its overarching architecture, users, and content. Section 2 outlines the impact pathways identified in association with RCAAP. Section 3 presents the complete findings from the Cost-Benefit Analysis (including costs and benefits). Section 4 explores potential additional impacts that could be discussed outside the CBA framework. Lastly, Section 5 offers conclusions and highlights the main challenges encountered during the assessment.

1. RCAAP: A single-entry point to Portuguese scientific content

RCAAP (Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal), i.e., the Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal, is the central system to discover, locate, and retrieve scientific content (including hundreds of thousands of publications, theses, conference proceedings, journal articles, and data) hosted in Portuguese Institutional Repositories (IR).

Overall, **RCAAP targets three primary objectives** that have remained stable since its establishment (Donato, 2010). They include (i) increasing the visibility, accessibility, and dissemination of Portuguese research results, (ii) facilitating access to information regarding these outputs; and (iii) integrating Portugal in the range of international initiatives for Open Access (OA).

1.1 The architecture of RCAAP

Launched in 2008, the RCAAP system consists of various interconnected components that have developed over time (for more details on the history, see Section 1.2). The backbones of the system are the network of IR and the Search Portal, which aggregates their content. They are supported by a technical infrastructure (e.g., for the exchange of metadata). Other additional and supporting services are also provided by RCAAP (see the Figure below for an overview of the architecture).

The backbone of the RCAAP system consists of systems and services that aggregate the metadata of different Portuguese repositories (documents, data) and journals¹. These systems are also used to check the quality of this metadata. The **backbone elements of RCAAP**, present since its inception, thus include:

The **RCAAP Portal** (since 2008) is the single-entry point for all the content related to RCAAP. The Portal collects the metadata on all the aggregated repositories daily, allowing users to search the universe of documents and data (Carvalho et al., 2014).

Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) Validator (since 2009): This module uses a standard protocol (OAI-PMH) to ensure metadata quality and interoperability with other systems and (Carvalho, 2013).

As mentioned previously, RCAAP covers different types of scientific content, but the main one is overwhelmingly (about 85-90% according to interviewees) documents. IR host these

¹ RCAAP does not harvest individual files but scans the content of all aggregated repositories to get their metadata. It should be noted that some repositories are hosted by RCAAP (see below).

documents and mainly use different versions of DSpace². RCAAP has a flexible architecture, allowing it to aggregate different types of repositories. These **types of repositories** allow different modalities of involvement of the institutions:

LOCAL - Local Repositories (since 2008): These IR are directly managed by institutions such as universities or institutes. They retain a very high level of control over their repositories, including hosting, version updates, and technical maintenance. RCAAP aggregates the content of these repositories.

- **SARI - Institutional Repository Hosting Service** (since 2008): This repository type is operated through a service provided by RCAAP at the central level. Any Portuguese institution in the Research and Higher Education system can host its repository with its own individualised brand identity. In addition to customising the visual aspects of the repository, each institution can also define and implement the configuration and parameterisation it considers appropriate to its organisational structure and its policies for self-archiving publications and managing the repository. Repositories made available under this scheme rely on the RCAAP infrastructures (hardware, hosting, connectivity, base systems, applications, security, backup service...). Still, their operation and administration remain the member institutions' responsibility. Applications for the SARI service are opened periodically and publicised on the RCAAP's social networks³. RCAAP provides this service free of charge.
- **RCOMUM - Common Repository** (since 2009-2011): This service is similar to SARI and centrally provided by RCAAP. It targets individual institutions, learned societies, or other bodies that are too small or lack resources to operate their dedicated repositories. Instead, they can upload their scientific content to a collection (i.e., a sub-section) of a "common repository" involving many different organisations.

Members of their institutions use repositories to upload scientific content, which is then made available on the internet to the broader public, typically in Open Access (some content may be closed or under embargo for a specific time, such as theses). In addition to its core repositories, RCAAP also provides **additional hosting services** related to quantitative data hosting (data repositories) and journals hosting, such as:

- **SARDC - Scientific Data Repository Hosting Service** (since 2010): It aims to provide a platform to store and deliver data created and used within the scope of research work of national institutions.
- **SARC - Scientific Journals Hosting Service**⁴ (since 2011): It was created to develop the online publication of scientific journals in Portugal, facilitating the management of

² DSPACE focuses on digital archiving and preservation, with a dedicated administration interface. See <https://dspace.lyrasis.org/>. Several versions of DSpace have been used under RCAAP, with recent updates to DSpace 7/8 ongoing as of October 2024. Specific addons were developed and implemented to complement the classical DSpace service, e.g., to track statistics.

³ As of 2024, there was a short queue for institutions to be able to join SARI.

⁴ The portal for journals hosted on the service is available at: <http://revistas.rcaap.pt>

scientific journals and supporting best practices. The service is based on the Open Journal System (OJS) publishing and management platform. This service is provided under the RCAAP project as a Software as a Service (SaaS), and all the updating, monitoring, backup, and security activities are carried out. In addition to the technical aspects, the service also provides a support service for the journal editor and the training needed to use the system.

Lastly, RCAAP also includes **horizontal services favouring the good functioning of the repositories**, such as statistics and support:

- **SCEUR - Centralised Service of Statistics on the Use of Repositories** (since 2011, now discontinued): It was created to centralise and consolidate usage statistics from the different sources aggregated by RCAAP (Silva, Ramalho, and Ferreira, 2011). This service is not accessible anymore as of 2024.
- **Helpdesk Service** (since 2008): It is accessible via email and telephone. It mainly targets repository managers to ensure the adequate maintenance of their repositories and the resolution of technical issues. It also allows the standardisation of practices between the participating institutions.
- **Training services** (since 2008): They are designed to help users learn how to utilise RCAAP services. This includes training opportunities organised centrally by RCAAP⁵, primarily targeting administrative staff and repository managers of institutions. However, some of the training provided by RCAAP is also relevant for other users, such as academics willing to upload content on their repositories. Additionally, institutions involved in RCAAP can also organise specific training sessions (under various modalities) for their own academic communities. These sessions may cover topics like using the repositories (for searching, downloading, and uploading content) and understanding the organisation's Open Science policy.

⁵ For example, online at <https://elearning.rcaap.pt/>

Figure 1. RCAAP Overall Architecture

Source: Authors

As implied by its architecture, different stakeholders are involved in managing the RCAAP system. It includes (Donato, 2010; Carvalho et al., 2014):

- **National Foundation for Scientific Computation (FCCN / FCT):** It is a private non-profit association of public utility tasked with various operations regarding the network of national research and education in Portugal. It manages the overall coordination and the infrastructures of RCAAP.
- **University of Minho:** It is a Portuguese university and a forerunner of online scientific repositories in the country. It ensures the scientific and technical coordination of RCAAP.
- **Individual institutions (e.g., universities, polytechnical institutes, hospitals, etc.):** They are responsible for the customisation, management, and use of their respective repositories (e.g., definition of the content of the repository, definition of upload policies, etc.). They can choose the type of repository they want to operate (LOCAL, SARI, RCOMUM). The RCAAP Portal aggregates all of them, but they entail different levels of commitment (resources, technical expertise...) and customisation possibilities. Larger institutions tend to opt for LOCAL repositories, while smaller ones often benefit from the shared hosting service provided by RCAAP (SARI or RCOMUM).

Over time, both the number of repositories and the content they contain have grown substantially, with a solid expansion phase in the 2010s. The number of repositories then stabilised in the 2020s. By 2024, a total of 52 individual repositories were thus active and aggregated by RCAAP, encompassing 27 SARI, 24 LOCAL, and 1 RCOMUM.

Figure 2. Number of repositories aggregated by RCAAP by type (2003-2024)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data. **Note:** The Figure shows the number of active repositories aggregated by the RCAAP Portal. RCAAP was created in 2008 (see vertical line). Repositories appearing before 2008 correspond to repositories that existed before RCAAP and then were aggregated by the system (e.g., the repository of the University of Minho). Since the RCOMUM covers multiple institutions (they have their own “collections” within this common

repository), the number of aggregated repositories does not directly correspond to the number of organisations RCAAP covers. Work on the RCOMUM started in 2009 but the first collections appeared only in 2011.

As the RCOMUM repository serves several institutions, the number of beneficiary organisations is greater than the number of repositories. By 2024, 121 organisations enjoyed a presence on RCAAP **Figure 3** below shows the evolution of the number of individual institutions benefiting from a repository aggregated by RCAAP (including those sharing the RCOMUM repository).

Figure 3. Number of institutions covered by repositories aggregated by RCAAP by type (2003-2024)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data. **Note:** The Figure shows the number of institutions benefiting from active repositories aggregated by the RCAAP Portal. RCAAP was created in 2008 (see vertical line). Institutions appearing before 2008 correspond to those with repositories that existed before RCAAP and then became aggregated by the system (e.g., University of Minho). RCOMUM institutions share the same repository.

Accordingly, the number of documents available on the repositories and through the RCAAP portal grew steadily since the creation of the system and significantly in recent years. Between 2017 and 2023, this number more than doubled, reaching **about 830,000 documents**⁶. Key documents include master’s and PhD theses, scientific articles, and other types of scientific documents⁷. The most common languages are English and Portuguese. LOCAL repositories concentrate the majority of the documents.

⁶ This figure excludes the content hosted by the scientific journal hosting services (SARC), which can be estimated at about 10-15% of the total volume of documents aggregated by the Portal.

⁷ The breakdown by type of documents is not readily available at the level of the entire RCAAP system (i.e., all repositories combined).

Figure 4. Number of documents aggregated by the RCAAP Portal by type of repository (2008-2024)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data. Estimated data for 2008 and 2009 based on a linear decay hypothesis. **Note:** The total number of documents aggregated by the RCAAP portal is shown, broken down by type of repositories. The numbers are estimates derived from the observed breakdown between the types of repositories in recent years and correction for the presence of journal articles (10-15% of the total).

RCAAP is not the only aggregator of IR in the world. It uses technologies and protocols (e.g., DSpace, OAI-PMH) that are standard among other repositories (see, e.g., Shearer et al., 2023). What distinguishes RCAAP and makes it a unique resource include the following aspects:

- **Aggregation of Portuguese scientific content:** RCAAP effectively aggregates the content of several IR from Portuguese institutions while allowing a dose of flexibility regarding their operation (e.g., SARI, RCOMUM, or LOCAL repositories). The academic community actively contributes to the system by uploading content to their own repositories. It facilitates discovering and downloading content that would be more fragmented or even hidden otherwise. It is particularly relevant for Portuguese-language documentation. Other aggregators exist, including in the EU, but RCAAP focuses explicitly on this language/geographical area.
- **Pooling of costs and expertise.** By providing several services at the central level (including hosting IR – free of charge for institutions), the RCAAP system allows the pooling of costs and technical expertise, ensuring efficiency gains. It enables institutions to have their own repositories (or a collection of RCOMUM) in ways that would not have been possible otherwise. It is particularly critical in the context of high costs researchers bear, including in Open Access initiatives (e.g., for journals: Klebel and Ross-Hellauer, 2023).

1.2 Development of RCAAP

RCAAP was launched by the University of Minho and FCCN in 2008, capitalising on early initiatives in Portugal and preparatory works in 2006-2008. RCAAP then developed in different steps, spurred by the support of academic institutions, legal developments, and continuous improvements of services (see Figure below for a detailed overview).

Figure 5. Main milestones of the RCAAP project

Source: Authors

Early initiatives promoting Open Access and universities' self-archiving scientific content began taking shape in Portugal in the early 2000s. Notably, the University of Minho led the way with the launch of its IR, RepositoriUM, in 2002-2003 (Rodrigues, Swan, and Baptista, 2013). In 2006, the Council of Rectors of Portuguese Universities (CRUP) formally supported Open Access principles by subscribing to the Berlin Declaration on the Open Access to Knowledge. It enshrined a commitment to Open Access among the relevant academic stakeholders in the country. More specifically, the CRUP paved the way for the development of RCAAP by highlighting the following points:

- It recommended that all Portuguese universities establish IR and defined institutional policies requiring the deposit of their members' publications in these repositories.
- It expressed its support for the interconnection and interoperability between the IR of Portuguese universities by creating a single portal for access to national scientific literature.

In early 2007, CRUP formed a working group dedicated to Open Access, tasked with launching a project that would promote the establishment of more repositories and the development of a national meta-repository. During the mid-2000s, other institutions beyond the University of Minho also began setting up their own repositories, such as ISCTE-IUL, the University of Coimbra, and the University of Porto, with their repositories emerging between 2006 and 2008. However, despite these efforts, the initial development of repositories in Portugal was still concentrated mainly within a small number of institutions and lacked coordinated efforts.

RCAAP was structured and launched rapidly in 2008, following initial investments in 2006-2008. It took approximately 6 to 8 months to develop the core of RCAAP, with contributions from the University of Minho (the technical partner and scientific coordinator) and the National Foundation for Scientific Computation (for infrastructural and information technology aspects). During this phase, the necessary infrastructure and services were established to support the two primary electronic services planned for the project:

- **SARI** aims to allow all Portuguese institutions to open their own repositories without having to maintain technical expertise or bear the related costs.
- **Meta-repository or RCAAP Portal** allows a search of content across all the aggregated repositories (including those hosted by SARI but also by pre-existing institutions).

During the 3rd Open Access Conference held in December 2008, the RCAAP project was publicly launched. Several factors facilitated the rapid emergence and subsequent development of RCAAP. First, the existence of early repositories, particularly that of the University of Minho, provided valuable experience for the development of RCAAP. Second, a consensus among key Portuguese stakeholders regarding Open Science and the use of repositories began to take shape in the mid-2000s.

In the period 2009-2011, several new services were launched by RCAAP to complement the base offer, including quality control (OAI-PMH validator), hosting services (RCOMUM, SARDC, SARC) and horizontal services (SCEUR).

A series of legislative and policy changes at both the national and institutional levels also backed the development of the RCAAP system. Indeed, in 2013, a legal mandate for the deposit of PhD theses on RCAAP repositories was established⁸. It was followed by a similar 2015 law on research benefiting from FCT funding⁹. In parallel, several institutions also introduced formal or informal OS policies and guidelines for their repositories, including incentives for researchers to deposit their documents (e.g., in career evaluations).

From the mid-2010s, the RCAAP system mostly entered into an exploitation and maintenance phase, with the central team concentrating on upgrading the repositories and

⁸ Decreto-Lei n. 115/2023 de 07/08 [Decree-Law no. 115/2023]

⁹ Portaria n. 285/2015 de 15/09 [Ordinance no. 285/2015]

Portal (e.g., shifts to new versions of DSpace) and resolving technical issues. New functionalities were less common, though a significant uphaul of the RCAAP portal is planned for 2025.

1.3 Using RCAAP: how, who, and for what

RCAAP content is accessible through a web browser, either through the RCAAP Portal or directly through the individual repositories. Content is freely downloadable¹⁰ without user registration and typically under Open Access modalities. However, some documents may be under more restrictive access. In particular, the theses (e.g., PhD) or journals articles can face standardised embargo periods of 12 months typically, and up to 36 months in some cases (FCT, 2014; FCT, 2025). After this period, the files become available to RCAAP users. Individual organisations participating in the RCAAP system can define their own OS policies, typically including guidelines on what to upload, under which conditions, and by whom. The documents generally are recorded as PDF files, as shown in the Figure below.

Figure 6. Example of a document made available on the RepositoriUM (aggregated by RCAAP)

Citação: Baptista, S. L., Soares, P. O., Romani, A., Alonso, J. L., & Domingues, L. (2024, December). Engineering arabinose-to-arabitol conversion in industrial *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* for sugar beet pulp valorization. *Industrial Crops and Products*. Elsevier BV. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2024.119718>

Resumo(s): Arabitol, a promising low-calorie sweetener for the food industry, faces production challenges due to the high costs and the environmental impact of conventional chemical methods, as well as the inefficiency of biological approaches using native arabitol-producing yeasts. The *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* GRE3 gene encodes an NADPH-dependent aldose reductase, capable of converting various aldoses to their respective sugar alcohols. By leveraging the enzymes broad substrate specificity, the simultaneous conversion of xylose and arabinose into xylitol and arabitol, respectively, was achieved. This study showcases the feasibility of using engineered industrial yeast strains, overexpressing the native GRE3 gene, for the one-step conversion of arabinose to arabitol. Engineered strains (PE22-pGRE3, PE22-pGRE3-XII5, CA11-pGRE3, CA11-pGRE3-XII5, CAT1-pGRE3 and CAT1-pGRE3-XII5) exhibited successful arabinose-to-arabitol conversion, with a 3.5-fold variation in arabitol concentrations across strains. Further enhancement of the best-performing strain through overexpression of the GAL2 gene significantly improved arabinose transport, resulting in a 1.95-fold increase in arabitol productivity. This engineered strain, free of heterologous genes, also demonstrated its potential by converting arabinose-rich sugar-beet pulp hydrolysate into arabitol, reaching a titer of 15g/L with a yield of 1g/g. This study represents the first example of arabitol production from agro-food waste using genome-edited *S. cerevisiae* strains, which contain no foreign genes, as a versatile and efficient host.

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Ficheiros deste registo:

Ficheiro	Descrição	Tamanho	Formato
document_58007_1.pdf		15,11 MB	Adobe PDF

[Ver/Abrir](#)

Source: Authors (extracted on 18/10/2024: <https://repositorium.sdum.uminho.pt/handle/1822/93224>)

¹⁰ Some documents may not be downloadable right away, for instance if they are under temporary embargo. In these cases, the files become available once the embargo period is over.

Primary data collection for this case study allowed a refinement of our understanding of RCAAP uses. It notably included a survey to users¹¹.

As mentioned above, the RCAAP system enables users to search and download content without requiring account creation or registration. **As a result, there is no detailed user profiling or collection of extensive personal information aside from anonymously gathered statistics.** The data collected includes Google Analytics indicators and internal metrics developed by RCAAP (particularly regarding document download counts). This information has been further supplemented by insights obtained through the users' survey.

Salient facts regarding RCAAP users emerge from the different sources, especially from the aforementioned survey. Firstly, most RCAAP users belong to the academic community (researchers or other administrative/support staff, such as librarians). Secondly, the use of RCAAP and its component IR is strongly concentrated in Portugal and Portuguese-speaking countries, which aligns with expectations. Thirdly, the RCAAP system has different types of uses, with a differential involvement of different populations.

As revealed by the above-mentioned users' survey, more than 90% of RCAAP users work or study in higher education institutions/universities (88%) or research centres (3%). Other organisations, especially those in the private sector, were much more marginal (see **Figure 7**).

Figure 7. Organisations of work/study of RCAAP respondents

¹¹ The survey sample was not based on a probability sampling methodology. By comparing the survey results to data on visits, it was noted that Portugal is somewhat overrepresented. However, we were not only interested in visitors to the RCAAP Portal and Institutional Repositories, but also by internal users (e.g., librarians and researchers feeding the system by uploading content). This population is almost exclusively Portugal-based on strongly engaged with the system. There were no other sources on evidence available to describe RCAAP users at the time of the case study. We thus considered that the sample distribution was sufficiently robust to provide a meaningful description of the actual uses of RCAAP. On this basis, it is also deemed suitable for application in the cost-benefit analysis. Further details are provided in the Annex 1.

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample is composed of 190 respondents who actively use RCAAP.

Respondents thus mostly held research roles (47%), but a substantial proportion held administrative roles (e.g., librarians, at 25%). Other significant functions included students (11%, excluding PhD students, who accounted for 24% of the total – as part of the research roles). This implies that many users of the service are students performing research at an early stage. Other notable users had management (9%) or technical (e.g., lab technicians, information technology specialists, 5%) roles.

Figure 8. Main functions of RCAAP respondents

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample is composed of 190 respondents with an active use of RCAAP. Admin = Administrative, Mgt. = Management, Tech. = Technical.

When zooming in on the respondents with research roles, we indeed observed a strong prominence of young PhD researchers (52% of this sub-group), while the remaining half is quite balanced in terms of seniority.

Figure 9. Academic positions of respondents with a research role

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample comprises 86 respondents with a research role and an active use of RCAAP.

RCAAP users can perform different actions depending on their positions and interests.

The main use of RCAAP concerns searching and downloading scientific content via the Portal or the repositories. Some users (almost exclusively Portuguese researchers and librarians¹²) can also deposit scientific content in their repositories, fuelling the RCAAP system. Other more horizontal or occasional uses include training/support measures and benefits linked to the internal life of institutions (e.g., career evaluation internal reporting using RCAAP statistics...). The interviews with repository managers confirmed the existence of these internal uses. Still, their extent/relevance depended strongly on the actual commitment to perform deposits and remained occasional (e.g., yearly reports...).

The RCAAP survey provides some insights regarding the extent of these usages.

As expected, using RCAAP to search and download content is the dominant activity, with 95% of them doing so. Uploading content was less common (45%), which can also be explained by the fact that it can only be performed by academic users with a scientific production or with deposit responsibility. Other activities linked to RCAAP are far less common.

¹² A Brazilian repository (OasisBR) is also aggregated by the RCAAP Portal, and is thus fed by Brazil-based workers.

Figure 10. Activities performed by RCAAP users

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the activities linked to RCAAP performed by the respondents. The sample is composed of 190 respondents who actively use RCAAP. Multiple answers were possible so that the total could be above 100%.

SEARCH AND DOWNLOAD FROM RCAAP

The primary use of the RCAAP system is thus to search and download scientific content from the aggregated IR. Consequently, the primary users hail from the academic community, especially from Portuguese-speaking countries, but also from a worldwide audience and non-academic users.

Estimating the exact volume of users searching and downloading content thanks to RCAAP is challenging due to multiple factors, including the central RCAAP team's loss of access to Google Analytics and the fragmentation of statistics between the different repositories¹³. However, in recent years, the number of unique users accessing the central RCAAP portal to search and download documents can be estimated at about 160,000 on a yearly basis (average for 2017-2024), with a peak in 2020, likely from a COVID effect (see Figure below).

¹³ In particular, the LOCAL repositories do not always provide their use statistics.

Figure 11. Number of unique RCAAP Portal users (2008-2024)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP Google Analytics data. **Note:** Values for 2008-2010 and 2023-2024 were estimated using data on downloads as a proxy. Most users access resources stored in RCAAP IR through other means than the portal, so these figures shall be considered as a lower-bound conservative estimate.

As users can also access content directly through the IR (or via Google Scholar, Google, or other referral sources), **this Figure should be considered as a lower bound.** There are no overarching statistics, but interviews with repository managers and data from the Sapiientia Repository (Google Analytics) suggest that a substantial majority of users arrive at the content through other means. The RCAAP team typically computes the **upper bound of potential users** of the system by aggregating the different members of the Portuguese scientific and academic communities (i.e., students, higher education teachers and researchers), leading to an estimate **of about 531,000 potential users**¹⁴. Even if this figure does not include foreign users, it is likely inflated. It implies that the **number of yearly users likely fall in the 160,000 – 531,000 range.**

Beyond the uncertainties regarding the number of users, it is still possible to monitor activity quite closely. Indeed, the number of downloads by year is well captured by the existing data, with an **estimated 31.8 million downloads per year** (2017-2023 average)¹⁵.

Users that search and download content on the RCAAP Portal primarily stem from Portugal and Portuguese-speaking countries. Indeed, according to the RCAAP survey, 96%

¹⁴ Based on <https://www.pordata.pt/pt/>

¹⁵ Estimate based on data for 39 repositories, extrapolated to the total number of repositories using data on the distribution of documents by repository.

of users using RCAAP to download content hailed from Portugal, 1.7% from Brazil, 0.6% from Angola/Cabo Verde (each), and 1.1% from Spain. This mirrors the situation for the entire sample of users (i.e., including users performing only deposits) and is confirmed by other lines of evidence from the interviews, repository-level data, and RCAAP portal data.

Search and download behaviours are pretty heterogeneous among users. Less than half were frequent users, with either daily (13%) or weekly (33%) use. Conversely, some respondents only had a very occasional approach to the system, with 28% using it monthly and 22% even less (quarterly or 1-2 times a year). The data and interviews suggested that administrative staff (e.g., librarians repository managers) frequently used RCAAP for search and download (26% daily use, 36% weekly use). By contrast, researchers had a notable but slightly less frequent use of the system (daily use 10%, weekly use 29%). Moreover, use among academics was driven by PhD students (14% daily use, 30% weekly use) and research fellows/associate professors (14% daily use, 29% weekly use), while more senior staff relied on it less frequently.

Figure 12. Frequency of use of RCAAP for search and download

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample comprises 180 respondents who actively use RCAAP for search and download.

RCAAP users collected various types of documents on the IR or the Portal. Among users accessing RCAAP for downloads, theses and dissertations were the primary type of collected content, with 85% of respondents. Scientific articles closely followed it at 81.11%. Other types of content were less commonly downloaded, though it reached significant figures for books (45%) and reports (28.89%). Conference-related items were less popular (15.56%). Other types of content (e.g., videos, etc.) were very marginal (2.22%).

Interviews suggest that the users download content for several of their activities, including feeding their research or study activities (e.g., the realisation of theses or scientific articles). The survey essentially confirms these use cases. Indeed, 64% of users noting a contribution of the downloaded content to their theses/dissertations asserted it as strong. It was 51% for scientific documents. Additionally, ten respondents reported that access to RCAAP for search and download was crucial to their work by providing concrete examples. For instance, one

respondent noted that RCAAP enabled him to collect several materials to prepare his thesis in the field of auditing. Other respondents pointed out that the RCAAP access fed specific research projects, including quantitative (e.g., a survey on music in early childhood education) and qualitative ones.

Figure 13. Contribution of content downloaded on RCAAP for the following outputs

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample comprises 180 respondents who actively use RCAAP for search and download. For theses and dissertations, 161 users reported a contribution. It was 159 for scientific documents and 78 for other outputs.

Anecdotal evidence from interviews suggests that users outside academia can use the RCAAP content in their daily activities. For instance, it includes access to information by companies for their economic activities, journalists, or the wider public (e.g., to look for information regarding their medical conditions). However, these other uses appear much less common than academic ones and are very difficult to substantiate.

UPLOAD/DEPOSITS TO RCAAP REPOSITORIES

The second large type of use of RCAAP consists of upload/deposits to its component repositories. Consequently, only individuals involved in Portuguese institutions (e.g., universities, research centres, research hospitals, etc.) can perform this task. All types of documents can be uploaded, including theses, scientific articles, conference documents, etc.

The modalities of upload are very diversified. According to the RCAAP survey, the great majority of respondents uploaded content to their repositories manually (77%), i.e., through the repository interface (typically DSpace). A significant minority (37-38%) imported existing data on documents from other sources, such as CIENCIAVITAE (curriculum service for

Portuguese researchers¹⁶) or ORCID. However, other sources were possible (9% of respondents). It included repositories that were connected to a Current Research Information System (CRIS) or similar information systems. In these cases, users typically did not have to go to the repositories' interface to perform the uploads, but documents were automatically imported from these other systems. It was, for instance, allowed in the case of the University of Porto and its SIGARRA system. It implies different relationships to the RCAAP systems and potential differences in time savings.

Figure 14. Modalities of deposit of content to the repositories aggregated by RCAAP

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the modalities of upload to RCAAP Repositories used by the respondents. The sample is composed of 86 respondents who actively use RCAAP for uploads. Multiple answers were possible so that the total could be above 100%.

On the upload side, both librarians and researchers perform most of the uploads to the repositories. Responsibilities for uploads are set at the level of individual institutions, with different policies ranging from full self-archiving by researchers to complete delegation of deposits to librarians. This diversity of situations is clearly visible among the respondents to the survey performing uploads. Indeed, almost an equal number reported that administrative staff (including librarians) were responsible for uploads (64%) followed by researchers for their own work (59%). Other modalities were less common (e.g., researchers doing uploads for other researchers). Overall, the evidence from interviews points out that a significant share of deposits is performed or checked extensively by the librarians (50-90%). In particular, librarians are always responsible for uploading theses and dissertations and are expected to check the

¹⁶ It should be noted that it is also possible for researchers to upload content from RCAAP repositories towards their CIENCIAVITAE profile. As of December 2024, it accounted for 338,000 records present on CIENCIAVITAE (see <https://www.cienciavitae.pt/cv-em-numeros/?lang=en>). According to FCCN analyses, it implies that RCAAP IR generates time savings on behalf of CIENCIAVITAE users (about 3 minutes per record). However, it is not clear whether these types of imports could be performed or not under the counterfactual, given that IR would still exist without RCAAP.

deposits made by researchers in any case (though actual practices depend on available resources).

Figure 15. Responsibilities for uploads in the organisations of respondents

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the responsibilities for upload in the organisations of the respondents. The sample is composed of 86 respondents who actively use RCAAP for uploads. Multiple answers were possible so that the total could be above 100%.

The frequency of uploading to the RCAAP repositories is highly variable and depends on the individual institution. This activity also tends to be cyclical, for instance, when these are defended or when researchers face career evaluations¹⁷. The survey confirms these trends by identifying two main user groups based on their upload frequency. The first group (47% of respondents) uploads content to the repositories quite regularly, i.e., at least monthly or even weekly/daily. This group has a substantial proportion of non-researchers (e.g., administrators, librarians...), which can be explained by their responsibilities to upload some content on behalf of researchers (at least in some institutions). The second group (53% of respondents) has a much less frequent upload habit, with quarterly or fewer uploads to the repositories. It includes many researchers backed by qualitative evidence from repository managers' interviews. The difficulties in mobilising researchers for deposits to IR are well documented in the literature (Ten Holter, 2020). In some repositories, the interviews indeed revealed an incomplete participation of researchers in the deposits despite existing policies.

¹⁷ In several organisations, researchers are evaluated based on their scientific output available on the RCAAP IR. It thus constitutes an incentive for them to upload their content. It leads to cyclical spikes of activity, with researchers performing uploads slightly before these evaluation periods. According to the survey, 66% of researchers performing uploads reported that they were evaluated on the basis of the content of the repositories.

Figure 16. Frequency of use of RCAAP for upload

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample is composed of 86 respondents who actively use RCAAP for uploads.

RCAAP does not collect harmonised data on the number of users performing uploads, but they are far less numerous than the users searching and gathering content. Establishing a meaningful number of users is moreover complexified by the variety of upload modalities and uneven split of responsibilities within organisations (e.g., a librarian can perform deposits on behalf of multiple researchers in one university, leading to one active user, while in another university, they would all be considered as individual users). As of 2024, the stock of users with deposit rights can nevertheless be estimated at 11,285 – though it includes users performing deposits on behalf of others and potential inactive/very infrequent users.

However, this problem can be somewhat circumvented by analysing the overall number of deposits of documents aggregated by RCAAP. Based on the number of aggregated documents (i.e., excluding journals), it can be estimated that an average of about 77,000 documents were uploaded to RCAAP aggregated IR in recent years (2017-2024).

Figure 17. Number of deposits to IR aggregated by RCAAP (2008-2024)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data. **Note:** Excluding deposits to the journals (10% of the total). Deposits are computed as the difference between total aggregated documents between two consecutive years.

OTHER USES OF RCAAP

Other uses of RCAAP are far less common than the two previously mentioned ones. It includes horizontal / support services provided by RCAAP, and also internal use cases of IR information by participating institutions.

The interviews clearly established that training and helpdesk services provided centrally by RCAAP were primarily used by repository managers and librarians to support their use of the IR and less so by end-users such as researchers. At the local level, librarians typically provide some training or information sessions related to the repositories and RCAAP, either formally or informally. This training activity was usually connected to the institution's Open Science policy (e.g., presentation of principles, other resources, and guidelines) and was not exclusively centred on RCAAP/the IR.

The survey and interviews documented other uses within participating institutions. It included using RCAAP-related statistics to monitor the institutional scientific output, generate insights on performance and trends, and draft reports (e.g., to the University Rectorate).

2. Impact Pathway for RCAAP

The RCAAP system aggregating multiple Portuguese repositories and providing additional services generates numerous effects for its users, including on the upload side (academic community, mainly researchers and librarians), the search and download side (academic community and beyond, including the general public and private sector entities), and for the management of participating institutions. These effects are expected to materialise through different channels called pathways. These pathways entail resources allowing activities, which themselves lead to outputs, outcomes, and, at a later stage, fully-fledge impact.

Following the impact pathway logic for Open Science developed in PathOS (Dekker, Karasz, and Stoy, 2023), we provide – in what follows – a description of how funding and resources made available to RCAAP (**inputs**) translate into direct benefits for users (**outputs and outcomes**)¹⁸ and advancements (**impacts**) in science, the economy, and society.

The actual materialisation of the impact pathway of RCAAP also depends on **enabling factors**, especially those linked to legal and Open Science policy trends. Enabling factors are conditions or elements that facilitate the implementation and success of the RCAAP project. These factors support the mechanisms through which the project is expected to achieve its desired outcomes.

The legislative framework can be considered an enabling factor facilitating the operation of the RCAAP project. In Portugal, the legislation indeed mandates depositing some content to repositories aggregated by the system, ensuring a steady flow of content. In particular, both Portuguese Master's and PhD theses must be uploaded since the Decreto-Lei n. 115/2023 de 07/08 [Decree-Law no. 115/2023]¹⁹. It was complemented in 2015 by another legal document (Portaria n.º 285/2015 de 15/09 [Ordinance no. 285/2015]) mandating the deposit of all outputs benefiting from FCT funding.

Similarly, **Open Science policies, guidelines, and incentives also form valuable enabling factors that** foster the system. Indeed, they act at different levels (national and institutional) to promote using RCAAP repositories, especially for deposits. They can refer to OS principles-specific guidelines or provide incentives (negative or positive) for deposits. Examples include

¹⁸ Short- and long-term outcomes specifically related to RCAAP fall within the categories of indicators developed and reported in the PathOS [Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook](#). For example, in terms of economic impact, the indicator 'cost-savings' includes short-term outcomes—such as time savings—which are also considered in the cost-benefit analysis of RCAAP. Data storage costs savings also fall under this category.

¹⁹ "1 - A digital copy of the doctoral theses (...) and master's dissertations must be deposited in a repository belonging to the Open Access Scientific Open Access Scientific Repository of Portugal, operated by the Foundation for Science and Technology, I. P.

2 - The deposit aims at the treatment and preservation of the referred scientific outputs, as well as the dissemination, in Open Access regime, of the scientific production that is not subject to restrictions or restrictions or embargoes."

the FCT Open Access Policy at the national level (mandating the deposit of FCT-funded research) or the Policy of the University of Minho, which had a financial incentive policy in 2005 for deposits. Other institutions use deposits for career evaluations, contributing to uptake.

Regarding **inputs**, the RCAAP system benefits from **funding** to support the development, maintenance, and operation of its overarching architecture and component repositories. It encapsulates investment costs at the central level and for LOCAL repositories to set up the entire system (e.g., server for the Portal and repositories...). Maintenance funding mainly targets staff costs for technical experts. Other operational costs are mostly staff-related as well, pertaining to the wages of librarians, administrators, managers, and researchers involved in the design, daily running of the repositories/RCAAP, as well as for the deposit of content to the repositories (see Section 3.2 for a detailed discussion of costs). Due to this cost structure, **technical expertise and skills from the involved staff are also critical**. It entails different types of skills, such as technical (especially IT-related), administrative/librarian, and scientific. The scarcest resource in the context of Portugal refers to technical skills, which notably entails benefits to centralisation and pooling via RCAAP. Larger institutions can typically employ some technical specialists as well, especially for LOCAL repositories, where they must act for the daily maintenance at the institutional level. RCAAP employs about 9 FTE at the central level. Individual repositories have teams of various sizes depending on their organisation, but interviews and a previous survey converge to suggest typical teams of about 1-5 FTE (Shearer, Nakano, and Rodrigues, 2023). The **governance of RCAAP**, including an organisation with different layers (i.e., RCAAP Central level, different institutions managing their repositories, etc.) is also central as an input for the project. This governance can indeed support the good maintenance and development of the system.

These inputs then lead to **different activities**, many of which have already been introduced in Section 1.3. They are often interconnected. **The Development and Maintenance of the RCAAP Central System (Portal, Hosting Services, and Support Services)** was the first activity to launch the entire system. It involved the technical work of building, updating, and maintaining the core infrastructure of RCAAP, which includes the central Portal for users and centralised repositories (SARI/RCOMUM, alongside other hosting services for journals and data) where content is stored. Ongoing maintenance and upgrading (e.g., moving to new versions of DSpace) ensure the continuity and improvement of the service. **The Customisation, Operation, and Maintenance of Individual Repositories** are necessary to feed the RCAAP system. Each institution may have specific needs (e.g., organisation of collections, rights of users, statistical monitoring, integration with other systems...), so the individual repositories are tailored accordingly. This involves ongoing operational management, technical support, and periodic updates to ensure they remain functional and secure within the overall RCAAP framework. The institutions' degree of independence/complexity depends on the type of repository they have chosen. LOCAL repositories have the most flexibility but also bear more costs and issues on their own compared to the SARI/RCOMUM options. **Definition and**

Updating of Individual Repository Policies ensure that technical and organisational aspects are well aligned. Policies regarding content curation, data protection, and document submission must be clearly defined for each repository. These policies may evolve over time based on regulatory changes, user feedback, or technological advancements, requiring regular updates. According to interviews, these policies may be formalised (e.g., repository policy as part of a broader OS policy document, specific guidelines) or more informal.

Deposit of Documents on the Repositories (Including Metadata Curation/Checks and Uploads of the Documents) is the core task of making repositories and the RCAAP system populated by actual content. Depending on the institution, this process involves different stakeholders, such as researchers, librarians, or administrative staff. Metadata is curated and checked to ensure that all documents are appropriately categorised and searchable, with varying modalities depending on the institution. **Dissemination and Training Activities** ensure the different users' awareness of the system and its good use. RCAAP performs these activities at the central level (e.g., through its e-learning portal), mainly targeting librarians and repository managers. However, institutions also train and communicate about their repositories to their communities of users, including students and researchers. RCAAP also operates the **Helpdesk**, which targets repository managers and their teams to resolve potential technical issues.

The activities above directly lead to the materialisation of several outputs. Thanks to the development of the RCAAP system and its component repositories, standard repositories (especially using DSpace) are becoming more available. They are backed by the **support of the RCAAP helpdesk** (e.g., helpdesk support tickets being answered), as well as by the **provision of training** by both the RCAAP central team (e.g., e-learning lessons viewed) and the librarians of individual institutions (e.g., awareness raising sessions in their universities). As a result of the development of these repositories and the related deposit of documents by users, **the main output of the system is increased availability, searchability** (through the repositories, the Portal, and other external tools such as Google Scholar), **and visibility of Portuguese research outputs.** Some outputs of the activities are also related to the inner workings of institutions. Indeed, the operation of repositories and the connected horizontal services (especially statistics) link to benefits of this nature. It includes allowing **improved monitoring and tracking of research outputs** (e.g., through statistics) and **facilitating different management issues** (e.g., career evaluation, internal reporting...).

These outputs are fairly easily measurable or assessed qualitatively. **In turn, they translate into outcomes either in the short or longer terms.** Outcomes notably include some of the critical benefits of the RCAAP system, with the direct ones (especially the academic-oriented outcomes) being integrated into the CBA. Other outcomes, corresponding in particular to more indirect or non-core benefits (e.g., cultural benefits), will not be directly covered by the CBA (see Section 3 below for a complete discussion of the scope of the CBA). Evidence suggests that, due to its nature and peculiarity, cultural or economic benefits linked to RCAAP are relatively small

(e.g., anecdotes about the public using RCAAP to retrieve information on their medical conditions) while academic ones rather prevail. Complex interactions exist between these outcomes; only the main ones will be briefly discussed here.

Academic outcomes include reduced **costs by pooling resources for the repositories allowed by RCAAP** (i.e., shared hosting services provided free of charge to institutions, as compared to each institution operating their repositories independently). The system can also help to **secure time savings related to accessing Portuguese research outputs**. The mechanisms for such savings include the availability of resources on the RCAAP portal, i.e., through a single interface. However, interviewees also pointed out that RCAAP allow an aggregation of information through its back-end, that can be exploited by other services (e.g., Google Scholar). As a consequence, access is facilitated even if users do not directly use the Portal. In theory, the RCAAP system may also lead to time savings for uploading/submitting scientific content, but alternatives to RCAAP may use similar systems (or even DSPACE), so these savings are likely small if existent at all. The **increased audience of Portuguese research outputs** will also be a core academic outcome allowed by the Portal and the repositories, leading to increased readings/downloads of content. Lastly, **the system may reduce direct costs for institutions and researchers to access research by making PDFs freely available**. **However**, in Portugal, a strong pooling effort (e.g., through the B-ON service) has already been achieved so the specific gains of RCAAP may only be a marginal improvement. These short-term academic outcomes could potentially lead to **enhanced productivity, for both administrators and researchers**, mainly through the channel of saved time and the pooling of resources.

Besides pure academic benefits, **RCAAP could also promote the development of new research and, with a much lower probability, entrepreneurial ideas by making the materials more visible and accessible**. This could take the form of greater industry-academia collaboration, though the preliminary evidence from Work Package 3 and interviews suggests that these linkages are infrequent, and not necessarily linked to RCAAP. The **internal management of educational institutions** such as universities would also be improved by **securing time gains**. For instance, tracking the universities' scientific output and the facilitation of managerial tasks allowed by RCAAP would indeed lead to time savings, securing economic gains. Lastly, the increased availability and searchability/visibility of Portuguese research outputs could secure **increased learning and awareness opportunities** for both academic and other users. Indeed, this entails a curiosity-driven perspective, as documented by some anecdotes during the interviews (for instance, people with medical conditions can learn more about their diseases by reading materials freely available on the RCAAP repositories. In the longer term, it can lead to **increased knowledge and cultural benefits at the societal level**, though the scope of this benefit is challenging to estimate.

In the long-run, **the long-term outcomes from RCAAP could translate into even broader impacts**. As such, these impacts are more difficult to capture analytically and are outside the

scope of the CBA. Assessing causality is also challenging. For instance, collaborations between industry and academia were detected thanks to the repository content in the case of the University of Minho (Rodrigues et al., 2023). Still, the origins of this collaboration can be difficult to track. It is expected that the core impacts will be academic. In contrast, the others are more speculative/uncertain and likely limited in magnitude (see Section 4. on benefits beyond CBA for further details).

This case study seeks to measure some of RCAAP's impacts by integrating a CBA perspective²⁰ with an impact pathways framework. The CBA was employed to precisely assess the impacts clearly and directly attributable to RCAAP, focusing on the short-term outcomes it generates for its users, such as cost savings due to pooling or facilitated access to research outputs (Section 3). In contrast, the long-term outcomes are explored within a broader causal pathways analysis, recognising that such outcomes are more marginal and often involve multiple influencing factors, and a direct causal link to RCAAP cannot always be established. Specifically, the long-term outcomes of RCAAP are discussed using qualitative and quantitative evidence.

²⁰ The cost-benefit analysis adopts a micro-economical perspective. This means that indirect (i.e. on secondary markets) and wider effects (e.g. induced impacts or effects on other categories of stakeholders, or economies) are often excluded from the analysis. The choice is to avoid that the analysis relies on assumptions whose reliability is difficult to check as well as any risk of double-counting.

Figure 18. RCAAP Impact Pathway

Source: Authors' elaboration based on primary data (interviews, survey...) and desk research

Note: While certain elements of this Impact Pathway Logic (IPL) - such as inputs, activities, and outputs – may be directly controlled by the stakeholders involved in RCAAP (sphere of control), others fall outside its direct control (sphere of influence and sphere of interest). The sphere of influence is an intermediate category regarding the degree of control of stakeholders involved in RCAAP (notably depending on the performance and engagement of potential users). The final stage (impacts) remains beyond both the direct control and influence of RCAAP stakeholders. However, impacts are certainly of high interest to funders, policy makers, and hence, the RCAAP community. The scope of the CBA is highlighted in red to mark a difference between the benefits entirely triggered by using RCAAP and benefits beyond those captured by the CBA, such as the long-term outcomes highlighted in blue.

3. CBA analysis

The cost-benefit analysis (CBA) has been used to assess the **short-term outcomes** – as illustrated in the IPL for RCAAP (Section 2) – generated by exploiting RCAAP, focusing particularly on effects directly attributable to the system on the functioning of the academic sector. These impacts primarily apply to the **higher education and research institutions** involved in RCAAP and their users (e.g., researchers, administrative and technical staff, students, etc.).

The analysis was guided by the CBA framework specifically tailored to the assessment of open science by Delugas et al. (2023). Accordingly, data on costs associated with the setup and operations of RCAAP were collected and compared to the benefits. A net present value²¹ was then estimated.

In terms of scope, the CBA focuses on the **document repositories, the RCAAP Portal, and the core supporting components of the project** (e.g., training by RCAAP). In particular, the data repositories and the journals hosting service are out of scope (see Section 3.1. below).

Data for the CBA analysis was collected thanks to the support of the RCAAP team (University of Minho and FCCN), a review of the relevant literature, and interviews with repository managers. When necessary, specific assumptions were made and justified. The analysis was guided by the CBA framework for open science, as described in Delugas, Catalano, and Vignetti, 2023.

During our analysis of RCAAP, we identified different costs and benefits that could be attributed to its functioning. We provided a comprehensive look at the costs sustained by the different stakeholders involved in the system, including the provider costs borne by the different levels involved in RCAAP (RCAAP central level, participating institutions) and the users. On the benefits side, our analysis focused on the cost savings enabled by RCAAP, mainly thanks to the pooling of staff and resources generated by RCAAP. We acknowledge that some other types of benefits exist, notably facilitated access to scientific resources leading to time savings for users searching and downloading content. However, essential uncertainties in the collected data

²¹ Net Present Value (NPV) is a financial metric that calculates the difference between the costs and benefits for a project or investment, adjusted so that flows that happen at different points of time are comparable. A positive NPV indicates that the project is expected to be beneficial, while a negative NPV suggests it may not be worth pursuing.

preclude us from integrating this benefit into the analysis. As a result, we present findings that are quite conservative, though focusing on what we understand as the primary outcomes of RCCAP. Moreover, we also investigated other potential benefits such as time savings when uploading scientific content and training costs, but they cancel out between the counterfactual and real-world scenarios.

The following figure briefly presents the different types of costs and benefits, which will be discussed in the following sections. The costs mostly relate to the “Funding” input of the IPL (see section 2 above) and the benefits consist of cost savings identified as short-term outcomes in the IPL.

Figure 19. Costs and benefits covered by the CBA

Source: Authors. **Note:** Green: costs evaluated and cancelling out in the real-world and counterfactual scenarios; orange: costs confirmed as present but left out of the CBA due to uncertainties about savings.

3.1 Setting the analysis

The elements of the causal chain illustrated in the IPL require a thorough discussion in order to be translated into CBA elements. To ensure a comprehensive and relevant analysis of the costs and benefits of RCAAP, discussions of the following aspects were needed:

- Legal and functional boundaries of RCAAP
- Counterfactual scenario (What if RCAAP did not exist?),
- Population of users affected by the costs and benefits associated with RCAAP

Although these are common issues in a CBA analysis, their treatment is not straightforward when assessing an open science resource like RCAAP. In particular, the network and collaborative nature of the system, with several aggregated repositories and different

stakeholders contributing to its operations, implies a fragmentation of the available data. Some methodological assumptions were needed to frame the analysis effectively, drawing on discussions with the RCAAP team (University of Minho and FCCN) and insights gathered from the users' survey, interviews with repository managers and the focus group. These assumptions are briefly outlined in what follows.

3.1.1 Scope of the analysis

As mentioned above, the scope of the analysis will focus on the **core of the RCAAP initiative, i.e., its network of IR and supporting infrastructures and services** (RCAAP Portal, horizontal and support services such as statistics, training, and Helpdesk). The functional unit is thus the storage and diffusion of scientific documents, which aligns with the primary objectives of RCAAP. It implies considering the costs and benefits of operating, managing, and maintaining RCAAP, including depositing documents. Benefits are mainly linked to avoiding duplication of costs and the greater visibility of Portuguese research allowed by RCAAP.

Data and journal hosting services are excluded from the scope for three main reasons. Firstly, they are at an earlier stage of development. Secondly, they target an entirely distinct purpose compared with the IR. In particular, the journal hosting service aims to provide a platform for peer-reviewing articles. In contrast, the IR can host materials already present in other journals to improve access and preservation. The functional unit is, therefore, quite different. Thirdly, the IR benefit from a specific legislative framework (i.e., mandatory deposit) in Portugal. The data hosting and journal hosting services do not benefit from such an approach, which alters researchers' upload incentives.

Regarding the timeframe of the analysis, setting adequate boundaries is also essential. The RCAAP project started quickly in 2006-2008, with set-up investments in that period. Interviews suggest rapid preparatory activities (mainly in 2008) to launch the system. The RCAAP project aggregated some early repositories that existed before 2008, but they would have been implemented without the project.

As an Information Technology project in the field of Research and Innovation, standards regarding the reference period are not fully set in the existing literature. Given its underlying characteristics (i.e., small investment costs, research-orientation...), it was chosen to apply the time horizon of research projects, as defined in the European Commission benchmark table²². Consequently, the considered period for the RCAAP CBA was set at 2006-2026, i.e., a standard 20-year period. A side benefit is that it implies a very short forecast period, as data could typically be collected up to 2023-2024. Usually, forecasts for 2025 and 2026 were computed to

²² See https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/studies/cba_guide.pdf

reflect stability in real costs and benefits. These two years allow a comprehensive assessment of the costs and benefits alongside the lifecycle for this type of project.

3.1.2 Counterfactual scenario

Following the CBA approach, the analysis was performed to compare the benefits obtained from exploiting RCAAP with its costs using an incremental approach. This approach entailed comparing two scenarios: the actual, real-world scenario with RCAAP that we can directly observe against the counterfactual scenario where RCAAP does not exist. This approach enabled us to pinpoint the hypothetical 'net' benefits generated by RCAAP.

This task is not straightforward in the context of RCAAP. It requires assumptions regarding the likely development and use of IR in Portugal without RCAAP and potential alternatives for both deposits and search/download of Portuguese scientific content. Given the fact that several types of documents are uploaded to the IR aggregated by RCAAP, it is likely that users would shift not to a single alternative but to a combination of different ones. Respondents in various contexts (e.g., interviews, focus group, informal exchanges) also had different views on the likely breadth and pace of development of IR in Portugal without RCAAP, especially for smaller institutions that may have had important resource constraints.

As a result, the retained counterfactual was built on the assumption that the objective would have been to maintain a similar level of service (digitalisation of scientific resources through IR even in the absence of RCAAP). This choice allows our analysis to focus on the specific benefits of RCAAP (especially pooling of resources) to achieve a minimal level of service in digitalising scientific resources. The development of IR, even in the absence of RCAAP, can moreover be justified on several grounds, including the development of open science policies and mandates and international comparisons. However, it should be noted that some institutions (especially the smallest ones) could have faced significant challenges to reach that end without RCAAP (see Box below for details). This specific counterfactual thus face limitations, and alternative ones may be developed in the future to assess RCAAP. In particular, the counterfactual focuses on institutions, and assumes a similar pace of development of repositories, which may be challenged.

Box 1 What if RCAAP did not exist?

RCAAP is a national-level initiative supported by a legislative framework for its development and uptake. However, some repositories existed before the RCAAP project (e.g., the University of Minho's repository). According to the interviewees and the general trends observed in the literature, it is credible (though debatable) that Portuguese institutions would have developed their IR even without RCAAP²³. However, it could have higher costs (no pooling of infrastructure, no free

²³ The case of smaller institutions is the most uncertain, as they would probably have lacked the resources to roll out the IR.

hosting service) and potentially fewer functionalities (though DSPACE would probably still have been the chosen technical solution for most repositories, as observed in other countries). Critically, without RCAAP, the Portuguese research hosted on these repositories would be less visible due to the lack of a Portal for aggregation. Implications in terms of costs and benefits notably concern the IR's creation and operation. Without RCAAP, Portuguese institutions would have had to dedicate their own resources to run servers and design, maintain and upgrade their IR. Significant savings due to pooling would have been lost.

Regarding the search and download of documents, a plurality of situations would have to be considered. As documented by the survey, other open-source means to access the targeted scientific content would likely have been dominant in the absence of RCAAP. However, paid platforms and other means (e.g., exchanges with colleagues via email requests) were also considered popular alternatives. The variety of the content accessible through RCAAP may explain this observed diversity, and the counterfactual cannot assume a single alternative but rather a blend of these options. A particular benefit of the RCAAP system is its compilation of all Portuguese Master's and PhD theses, which are not accessible easily in other alternatives. For this particular content, it is expected that the lack of RCAAP would result in a significant drop in the number of views, with potential consequences, for instance lower visibility for early career researchers, less efficiency for students completing their work, etc. For different outputs, the decline in visibility may be more moderate. This complexity makes it challenging to assess this benefit in the CBA quantitatively, so it will be discussed qualitatively.

Figure 20. Hypothetical counterfactuals of RCAAP for searching and downloading content

Source: Authors' elaboration on RCAAP user survey.

For the users making deposits, the implications of the counterfactual scenario are smaller. Indeed, the time spent by stakeholders to make these deposits would have been similar, as the deployed solutions (DSPACE or alternatives) would not have been significantly different. It is corroborated by the small/uncertain time savings identified in the survey).

Note: The Figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The alternatives were not presented as mutually exclusive. The sample size is 180.

Source: Authors based on survey results, interviews, and literature

3.1.3 Users' population

While the IPL treats the RCAAP user population as an implicit component of the causal chain, it is a key element in the CBA, as users are directly affected by the impacts arising from the use of this resource. The IPL primarily highlights the various types of impact—academic, economic, and societal—within which RCAAP users operate. In this section, we derive best estimates of the RCAAP users, taking into consideration the specific challenges of an open resource.

As documented above, the RCAAP system (including its Portal and component IR) is an open resource involving different types of users: people using it to search and download content and those performing deposits to the repositories. While depositing files requires creating an account, searching and downloading content can be performed by any Internet user on the go. Moreover, the information is fragmented between multiple different Institutional Repositories.

This situation makes the estimation of the users' population challenging. In practice, it relies on different sources of information, including Google Analytics (volume of web traffic for people searching and downloading content) and internal DSpace statistics (number of downloads, numbers of accounts with deposit rights). Additionally, the recorded data may have specific limitations (e.g., risk of double-counting, robot activity), even though Google and RCAAP have already applied corrections to address these issues.

Consequently, the users' population can be assessed with margins of uncertainty (see Section 1.3. above for a full discussion of this issue). **For users searching and downloading content**, our best estimate uses Google Analytics data from the RCAAP Portal, leading to about **160,000 unique users on a yearly basis in recent years** (average for 2017-2024).

Besides using RCAAP and its IR to search and download content, the Portuguese academic community is also mobilised to perform the deposits. Given the wide range of modalities for upload across the different institutions (see Section 1), obtaining a precise number of the relevant population is challenging. In theory, all active researchers and librarians may be candidates for deposits. In practice, interviews suggest that only a much smaller number should be considered. Based on data provided by FCCN, it can be estimated **that about 11,300 accounts held deposit rights in 2024**²⁴, though not all of them may actively engage in deposits.

²⁴ Data was provided for RCOMUM and 27 SARI Repositories. Data for other repositories was estimated using a simple linear regression using the number of hosted documents as the Independent variable.

3.2 Costs

Identifying the costs associated with RCAAP necessitates careful consideration due to the involvement of multiple stakeholders. The RCAAP system includes not only the central level (University of Minho / FCCN) but also the individual institutions (that face “provider” costs) and the community of users that perform various tasks, most notably the deposits to the IR (“user” costs).

In line with the methodological framework described by Delugas, Catalano, and Vignetti, 2023, we considered both the costs incurred by the providers (RCAAP and individual institutions operating the IR) and those incurred by the users (e.g., librarians, research support staff, scientists or the broader public).

As in any traditional CBA, we categorised the **provider costs** into set-up and operational costs. They are largely covered by the “funding” input of the IPL:

- **Set-up costs** refer to the initial expenses associated with planning, designing, and launching RCAAP—essentially everything required to get it off the ground (i.e., investments and operational expenditures linked to the project launch). These set-up costs are relevant for launching the RCAAP system and for aggregating individual repositories. LOCAL repositories face higher set-up costs than other types of repositories since they have to manage their own technical equipment. In contrast, SARI and RCOMUM repositories delegate these aspects to RCAAP. They also cover reinvestment costs during the life of the project.
- **Operational costs** encompass all expenditures connected to activities such as managing the repositories, performing training, and performing other support activities for researchers.

The **costs incurred by users** encompass the time spent acquiring the necessary skills to use RCAAP, contributing to its content by depositing files, sending related metadata, and accessing the content (searching and downloading the files). They include costs under the “funding” input of the IPL (notably those linked to the wages of librarians performing deposits) but not only (e.g., access costs borne by external users). To account for these costs, we assigned a monetary value to the time users invested in using RCAAP based on the users’ survey, data on the volume of activity, and interviews.

- In practice, the **training and deposit costs** cancel out in the scenario with RCAAP when compared to the counterfactual. Indeed, we consider that users would have had to

experience a similar training process and that deposit times would have been identical even in the absence of RCAAP²⁵.

- For the **access costs**, we could model the costs borne by users in real-world conditions but not estimate the counterfactual due to uncertainties in the data (i.e., survey data could not be exploited to that end). Consequently, we do not integrate these costs into the CBA; instead, we discuss the findings. It should be noted that this choice is conservative, given that access costs are expected to decline thanks to RCAAP. In summary, our CBA will bias downwards the results of RCAAP.

The Table below provides an overview of the different types of costs attributed to the RCAAP providers (i.e., RCAAP and the other institutions, with differences depending on the types of repositories) and users. More details about these costs and the approach used to measure them are provided below.

Table 2 Costs related to RCAAP

STAKEHOLDER INVOLVED	COST TYPE	CATEGORY
Provider – RCAAP Central level	Set-up costs (RCAAP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments and reinvestments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Intangible fixed assets ◦ Computer equipment and software • Staff costs and other expenditure
	Operational costs (RCAAP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff costs and related expenditure • Training costs • Travel costs • Dissemination • Funding to partner institutions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Memberships (fees paid by FCT to institutions to which it participates for RCAAP, such as DSpace, the DOI agency, or the Confederation of Open Access Repositories) • Other expenses
Provider – Institutional level	Set-up costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments and reinvestments (only for LOCAL repositories) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Computer equipment and related costs • Staff costs and other expenditures (for all types of repositories) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Technical staff costs ◦ Administrative and management staff costs

²⁵ This can be justified by the fact that DSpace would probably have been used in most cases for repositories even in the absence of RCAAP. In the 2023 Survey by COAR (Shearer et al., 2023), DSpace was indeed the most commonly used solution across European repositories (41%). Moreover, alternatives to DSpace are likely to generate similar time spent for training and performing deposits. This interpretation is strengthened by the interviews and the results of the survey showing no to small time savings for deposits.

	Operational costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Maintenance and technical support staff costs (only LOCAL repositories) ○ Administration and management staff costs (all types of repositories) ○ Librarian curation and checks costs (all types of repositories)
Users	Training costs	<p>It refers to the time spent learning to use RCAAP and become an efficient user (specifically to perform deposits).</p> <p>Interviews and the survey suggest that training costs are marginal, especially those specific to RCAAP/IR (and not to, e.g., Open Science policies or generic guidelines to follow). In practice, these costs cancel out when compared to the counterfactual since they would occur also in absence of RCAAP.</p>
	Deposit costs	<p>It refers to the time spent uploading content to RCAAP (borne by researchers and librarians). Again, these costs cancel out when compared to the counterfactual.</p>
	Access costs	<p>It refers to the time spent accessing and downloading the content available on RCAAP. These costs were evaluated for the real-world scenario but could not be estimated for the counterfactual due to uncertainties regarding time savings. As a result, they are not integrated into the CBA model but are nevertheless discussed for contextualisation.</p>

Source: Authors

As described in Section 1, RCAAP is fed by researchers and librarians based on documents produced in different contexts (e.g., scientific publications, theses, conference proceedings, etc.).

For the purpose of our analysis, we adopted methodological choices to assess the costs based on this reality:

- (i) Past costs related to creating documents hosted by RCAAP IR are considered sunk costs²⁶. These costs represent investments that would have been made regardless of the existence of RCAAP (e.g., drafting of research papers). This choice has a significant implication on the final result but it is justified because the focus of the RCAAP initiative is not the creation of scientific content per se, but rather the provision of a facilitated access to this content.
- (ii) The current costs incurred by researchers and institutions to carry out and publish scientific studies and other documents – then uploaded to RCAAP IR - are considered

²⁶ A sunk cost is an expense that has already been incurred and cannot be recovered or altered by current or future actions.

sunk costs. While these costs are essential for creating the content available on RCAAP, they are not part of RCAAP's direct financial responsibilities. Researchers would still conduct their studies independently of RCAAP, meaning these costs would have been incurred regardless of the existence of RCAAP itself.

Therefore, the costs included in the CBA analysis are limited to those explicitly recorded in the RCAAP budget, the costs borne by other providers (i.e., institutions managing their IR aggregated by RCAAP), and the costs faced by the user community contributing to RCAAP, mainly through the deposit of documents.

Provider costs

Providers (RCAAP and institutions operating the IR) incur two types of costs: set-up and operational costs, described below.

SET-UP COSTS

Set-up costs refer to the expenses associated with establishing RCAAP and its component IR (including the SARI hosting service). It also covers **necessary reinvestments during the lifetime of the project**. It refers mainly to equipment, infrastructure, and software expenditure (for RCAAP and LOCAL repositories). Set-up costs also include staff costs needed to launch the system and the different repositories. Indeed, specific actions are required to design the repositories (including, e.g., their governance, scope and content, interaction with open science/access policies, and when it applies technical considerations).

The approach to model the provider set-up costs in the real-world scenario was differentiated depending on the considered level: RCAAP (central level) or individual institutions operating the repositories.

At the RCAAP central level, high-quality budgetary data has been available from the FCCN RCAAP unit since the project's launch in 2008. It was complemented with additional data related to preparatory works in 2006-2008, which was obtained following interviews with FCCN staff. This raw data was analysed and filtered to focus on costs within the scope of the CBA. Moreover, some reinvestment costs (e.g., server and related equipment) were not present in the FCCN RCAAP unit budget after 2012 since they were shifted to another RCAAP unit. In order not to neglect these costs (which would bias the estimates), we modelled reinvestments as 1/8th of the initial investments from that year onwards, increasing in line with inflation. This approach was based on assumed depreciation rates and server investment cycles and was validated based on exchanges with FCCN staff.

Set-up costs are also borne by institutions having IR, primarily if they choose to operate their repositories independently, i.e., without joining the SARI or RCOMUM hosting services proposed by RCAAP. In that case, institutions with LOCAL repositories face set-up costs related to servers and related expenditures, as well as technical staff. Some set-up costs are related to

the administration and management of the repositories during their launch year, and all types of repositories face these costs.

These set-up costs were estimated based on interviews with repository managers and the literature, especially on the experience of the University of Minho (Swan, Picarra, and Rodrigues, 2016). It included modelling based on reinvestment cycles for servers for local repositories and staff costs for all repositories (based on their time spent and wages). These costs occurred at different times depending on the creation dates of the repositories. These dates are considered to model the costs highlighted in the Figure below.

The graph below presents an overview of RCAAP's provider set-up costs, distinguishing the types of providers (RCAAP Central level and Institutional level). We estimate that **during the entire timeframe of the CBA (2006-2026), set-up costs - including reinvestments - amounted to a total of about EUR₂₀₂₄ 3 million**. These costs were borne principally by the institutions (about 66%) and then by RCAAP itself (about 33%). As expected, the costs are concentrated in the project's early years (more than half in 2006-2010). Peaks in later years correspond to the massive entry of new repositories (e.g., RCOMUM collections in 2013) or reinvestment cycles for servers (e.g., 2020).

Figure 21. Estimated set-up costs (including reinvestments) by provider in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data, interviews with repository managers, and additional sources from the literature. **Note:** All data in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values. The figures correspond to the real-world scenario with RCAAP. Reinvestment costs are included.

In the scenario without RCAAP, the provider costs related to RCAAP obviously do not occur. By contrast, we model the development of the different repositories using the cost structure of LOCAL repositories (with some adjustments for small institutions that would have been part of RCOMUM collections). It leads to total set-up costs of about **EUR₂₀₂₄ 3.8 million for 2006-2026**.

OPERATIONAL COSTS

Operational costs encompass all expenditures required to run and maintain RCAAP and its IR after the initial set-up phase. The primary categories of these costs include salaries/wages, but they also consist of travel expenses, equipment, consumables, external work purchases, etc.

As for the set-up costs, we must distinguish between the operational costs borne by the RCAAP at the central level and by the institutions to operate their IR.

At the RCAAP level, data is available in a consolidated form since the project’s inception until 2023. It mainly consists of staff costs but also funding for specific activities, such as dissemination, support to partner organisations, etc. By convention, the operational costs begin in 2009. Prior costs (including staff ones) were assessed as linked to the design and launch of the system and thus counted as set-up costs.

There was no unified dataset for the operational costs at the institutional level. Moreover, institutions typically do not record a dedicated budget for their repositories. As a result, their costs were reconstructed based on interviews and survey data (Shearer, Nakano, and Rodrigues, 2023). Components of operational costs at this level include administrative and management costs, technical and maintenance costs (only for LOCAL repositories having their own servers) and librarian curation and checks costs (reviewing metadata and upload quality). All these costs are basically staff costs, which were estimated based on the time spent by workers fulfilling these tasks during the development of the different repositories. Cost profiles were derived for every type of repository (LOCAL, SARI, RCOMUM) to ensure that their specificities were considered. These cost profiles use the number of FTE and related wages of workers involved in the different tasks, with a gradual rise to account for the development of repositories over time. For instance, the figure below outlines the cost profile of administrative and management staff for LOCAL repositories by age of the repository.

Figure 22. Operational Costs profile for LOCAL Repositories – Administrative and Management costs by age of repository

Source: Authors based on interviews with repository managers and wage data (Payscale). **Note:** All data in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values. Graph starts from second year (since the first year of the repository is considered set-up).

The Figure below provides an overview of the total computed operational costs²⁷. We estimate that during the entire timeframe of the CBA (2006-2026), **operational provider costs amounted to a total of about EUR₂₀₂₄ 34.5 million**. The vast majority (91%) occurred at the institutional level. In 2024, operational costs reached a yearly value of about EUR₂₀₂₄ 2.5 million. These costs rose substantially over time due to the development of the repositories (increasing number over time) and the maturity of the repositories, implying more resource use.

Figure 23. Estimated operational costs by provider in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data, interviews with repository managers, and additional sources from the literature. **Note:** For the RCAAP level, all operational expenditures were collected from the budget, aggregating the relevant categories (see Table 2 above). For the institutions' level, expenditure was estimated based on the time spent by the staff involved in administrative/management, curation/checks and maintenance activities. Time spent is calculated based on interviews and external data. Time spent was valorised using the gross wages of university librarians/staff in Portugal (Payscale data). Data does not include deposit costs. All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

In the scenario without RCAAP, the operational costs related to RCAAP obviously do not occur, similarly to the set-up costs. For the LOCAL repositories, the operational costs do not change. However, institutions that choose SARI or RCOMUM hosting services would have to operate their own repositories and thus face a similar cost structure to the LOCAL ones. We model this

²⁷ This estimate does not include deposit costs, even if they are borne by librarians. These costs are part of users' costs. However, the operational costs cover the checks and curation work performed by librarians to ensure the quality of the content of their IR.

process (with some adjustments for small institutions that would have been part of RCOMUM collections). It leads to total operational costs of about **EUR₂₀₂₄ 35.5 million for 2006-2026** (slightly higher than with RCAAP), or about **EUR₂₀₂₄ 2.8 million in 2024**.

Users' costs

Users' costs refer to the expenses incurred when dealing with different RCAAP-related actions, such as learning to use the system (and its component IR), performing deposits or searching and accessing content indexed on RCAAP. Including these costs in the model is crucial to avoid overestimating the benefits users derive from the system. These costs can be divided into three main categories:

- A. **Training costs:** Time spent learning how to use RCAAP. It refers to the time spent by people attending these training sessions in individual institutions to perform deposits on the IR (mainly researchers). According to the survey and qualitative evidence, these costs are minimal as the complex issues are linked to overarching principles (e.g., metadata guidelines and legal considerations...) rather than the RCAAP system itself. They are modelled but cancel out in the real-world and counterfactual scenarios.
- B. **Deposit costs:** Time dedicated to actively uploading content to the repositories aggregated by RCAAP. Portuguese researchers or librarians performing the upload on their behalf (depending on the practices and policies of each institution) bear these costs. As for the training costs, deposit costs are cancelling out in the counterfactual scenario when compared to the real-world scenario because we expect that the alternative system would use the same (or similar) software, leading to insignificant changes in time spent by users for that end.
- C. **Accessing costs:** Time spent accessing RCAAP resources through the Portal, the IR, or other channels. They are borne by all the users using RCAAP to search and download content (academic users and beyond). These costs are modelled in the real-world scenario with RCAAP, but they could not be assessed for the counterfactual scenario. Indeed, time gains were too challenging for users to estimate, leading to survey data inconsistencies. As a result, these costs are not included in the CBA results but are still discussed. As mentioned above, we clearly expect time savings for access costs, so excluding them is a conservative approach to assessing the project.

From a cost-benefit analysis perspective, the time invested in these activities represents an opportunity cost. While it does not involve direct financial expenditure, it reflects the value of time that could have been devoted to alternative tasks. The following sections detail how these costs were collected and how their monetary value was estimated and incorporated into the CBA (excluding access costs).

A. TRAINING COSTS

The first type of user cost relates to the time spent learning to navigate and use the repositories aggregated by RCAAP, focusing on making deposits to the IR²⁸. Evidence from the interviews and the survey suggests overall that it is relatively straightforward to grasp the system, as highlighted by small differences in time spent for first use of the system compared to typical use (see Figure below). Indeed, the median user spends about 5-10 minutes in both cases, but higher values are overrepresented for the first user (e.g., 6% for 30 min – 1h. against 4% for typical use). This pattern suggests a relatively small need for training sessions.

Figure 24. Comparison of time spent by users to make a deposit on RCAAP-aggregated IR in first use and typical use

Source: Authors based on RCAAP survey. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample comprises 82 respondents performing deposits on one (or more) IR aggregated by RCAAP.

However, advanced users, especially librarians and related staff tend to point out that there is a learning curve to absorb the different rules related to the uploads. The more complex rules are mainly associated with the various policies and procedures related to the uploads rather than to the act of performing the deposits themselves.

Even if using DSpace to perform deposits is usually not considered complex²⁹, the different institutions operating the IR can propose training sessions, targeting users such as students and researchers. These sessions are typically organised by librarians and often bundle issues related to RCAAP and the IR with broader considerations about open science, specific resources, etc.

²⁸ Training opportunities are also proposed by the RCAAP central level, though this offer mainly targets librarians and repository managers. These costs are thus counted in the operational costs of the system, rather than as user costs.

²⁹ Though there are differences depending on the IT skills of researchers, especially for older generations.

The costs for the institutions are covered in the provider costs (under operational expenditure). Still, there is also a cost for users, i.e., the value of the time they spend attending these training sessions.

As discussed above, the training costs will cancel out in the counterfactual scenario instead of the real-world scenario. Thus, they do not impact the net benefit brought by RCAAP. However, we still provide an estimate of these costs for reference. It should be noted that these costs are minimal but with some uncertainties due to the critical variable of the number of persons benefiting from training sessions each year. Indeed, no data is directly available for the number of attendees. We thus rely on an estimate based on the number of accounts with deposit rights and a correction factor (25%, arbitrary). We know from interviews with repository managers and librarians that typical training sessions last about 1 hour. Based on wage estimates of the attendees (weighted by their roles observed in the RCAAP survey), we can estimate the value of one hour of their time. **The cost of training one user is evaluated at about EUR₂₀₂₄ 12.** By multiplying this value by the number of attendees (about 280 per year in the last years), we derive the total training costs on a yearly basis. **This calculation implies that the total user cost for training is, at most, in the thousands of euros, with a preferred yearly estimate of EUR₂₀₂₄ 3,500 in 2024.**

B. DEPOSIT COSTS

Deposit costs refer to the time and effort users invest in uploading content to the IR aggregated by RCAAP. These include time to transfer the files, compile the metadata, and check the information. From a CBA perspective, deposits require a certain level of effort, expertise, and user resources that could have been allocated to other tasks. Therefore, these costs are considered an opportunity cost. They are not limited to the initial phase of using RCAAP, as they occur on a rolling basis throughout its usage. Consequently, they are part of the operating costs.

Both researchers and librarians perform deposits on their behalf. According to interviews and the evidence from the survey, librarians make a substantial share of deposits (20-50%, depending on the context). For these deposits, the costs are evaluated based on the time librarians dedicate to them, valorised using their gross wages (similar to other operational costs, see above). For deposits performed by researchers, the cost is estimated based on the number of deposits, the time spent by the researcher per deposit (based on the survey – see Figure below), and the gross wage of Portuguese researchers (Payscale data). The time needed to perform a single deposit is relatively small, **with the median user falling in the 5-10 minutes range** (see Figure below). Researchers typically spend less time on deposits than librarians.

Figure 25. Time spent to upload a piece of content to the IR by function

Source: Authors based on RCAAP survey (sample size: administrators = 33, researchers = 36). **Note:** The Figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The sample is composed of users making deposits on one or more IR aggregated by RCAAP. Its size is 33 (administrators) or 36 (researchers).

Based on these assumptions, we can estimate the deposit costs the users (librarians and researchers) bear. **The cost of a deposit by librarians is estimated at EUR₂₀₂₄ 1,9; for a researcher, this figure reaches EUR₂₀₂₄ 3.2.** By multiplying these unit costs by the number of yearly deposits (for each type of users), we obtain the total deposit costs induced by the network of RCAAP repositories. As the number of deposits grows over time, so does the cost (see Figure below).

Figure 26. Estimated deposit costs by type of users in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data, Payscale data, interviews with repository managers, and RCAAP survey.

Note: Costs were derived using the number of deposits to RCAAP and the unit costs of a single deposit. The number of deposits was estimated from RCAAP data on the number of aggregated documents on the system (corrected for journal articles). Time spent for a single deposit was calculated based on interviews and RCAAP survey data. Time spent was valorised using the gross wages of university librarians/researchers in Portugal (Payscale data). All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

We estimate that **during the entire timeframe of the CBA (2006-2026), deposit costs amounted to a total of about EUR₂₀₂₄ 3.2 million.** The majority (82%) was borne by researchers due to a higher share of total deposits and higher average wages when compared to librarians. In 2024, operational costs reached a yearly value of about **EUR₂₀₂₄ 270,000.** These costs rose substantially over time due to the development of the repositories (increasing number over time) and the maturity of the repositories, implying more resource use.

However, as for the training costs, **these costs are expected to cancel out since the counterfactual scenario implies a similar development and burden for users when compared to the real-world scenario with RCAAP.** Thus, deposit costs do not drive RCAAP's net benefits.

C. ACCESS COSTS

The last type of user cost relates to the time spent accessing and downloading documents from the IR aggregated by RCAAP in various ways (directly through the IR, through the RCAAP Portal or through other search engines, for instance). As mentioned above, these costs were evaluated for the real-world scenario with RCAAP. Still, they could not be assessed for the counterfactual scenario due to the difficulties respondents/interviewees had in imagining this situation and the potential consequences it would have had for their work. As a consequence, we present the figures for the total access costs for the scenario with RCAAP (to show that they are significant) but do not include them in the CBA. This choice is conservative, as it is expected that RCAAP lowers these costs relative to the counterfactual.

The time invested in accessing documents was collected during the RCAAP user survey. The data gathered indicates that user responses are predominantly concentrated in the shortest time ranges, with less than 10 minutes typically required to access the documents, regardless of the access method (See Figure below).

Figure 27. Time spent by RCAAP users to search and download content by access modality

Source: Authors based on RCAAP survey **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample comprises 101 respondents searching and downloading content through the RCAAP Portal, and 87 through Institutional Repositories.

We use this time spent as well as the frequency of use (also collected during the survey) to derive the total time spent by users accessing RCAAP documents. To express the value of the time invested in accessing RCAAP documents in monetary terms, we then used the GDP per capita equivalent for the time spent as a proxy. GDP per capita was used because the occupational composition of people who search and read content is not robustly known. We weighted the GDP per capita by the countries of origin of readers, which are known thanks to RCAAP Google Analytics statistics.

Overall, these costs were estimated to be less than EUR₂₀₂₄ 330 million for the entire considered period (2006-2026). **This is a significant cost that rises in line with the development of the system. In recent years, access costs amounted to about EUR₂₀₂₄ 20 million (e.g., in 2024).**

This should be considered as a lower bound estimate, given that it relies on the assumption of about 160,000 yearly users.

Figure 28. Estimated access costs in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data, RCAAP survey, OECD, IMF and ECB. **Note:** The number of accesses to search and download content was first estimated using the number of yearly unique users and their frequency of uses. This number was then converted to time spent accessing content using the relevant question of the survey. Once this total time spent was obtained, it was converted to monetary values by multiplying by the value of time. This value of time was derived from the weighted GDP per capita of the countries of users. Data in US dollars was converted to EUR. All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

In the RCAAP survey, we explored the additional time that users would have spent accessing documents without RCAAP. However, the difficulties in imagining this scenario, as well as the structure of the question (asking for time savings on a weekly basis), resulted in inconsistent and implausible findings. There was a major risk of misestimating the access cost savings of RCAAP, which is why we decided to adopt the conservative decision to exclude access costs from the CBA model. Indeed, since we expect access costs to be reduced thanks to RCAAP compared to the counterfactual, the exclusion of access costs (and related net savings) from the model means that RCAAP's benefits are a lower bound in our CBA.

Overview of total costs

By combining all the available costs to run the system in the real-world scenario (except for users' access costs), we reached **about EUR₂₀₂₄ 41 million (2006-2026)**. Costs rise with time due to the development of the different IR, and in the final years, **the yearly costs amount to about EUR₂₀₂₄ 2.8 million (2024)**.

Figure 29. Overview of total costs in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on previous graphs (multiple sources). **Note:** Total costs include all providers (RCAAP Central level and Institutional level), as well as the users. Access costs are excluded. All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

Providers' operational costs constitute the great majority of the total costs to ensure the service (85%). The central level accounts for about 9% of these operational costs, while institutions bear the bulk of them.

3.3 Benefits

As discussed in Section 2, the short-term benefits of RCAAP primarily consist of costs saved thanks to the pooling of resources allowed by the system to reach a similar level of service without RCAAP³⁰. Institutions would face higher costs, particularly regarding infrastructure/equipment and personnel. In line with the CBA open science framework described by Delugas et al. (2023), we identified two types of benefits associated with RCAAP that could be incorporated into the entire CBA:

- (i) The time saved in streamlining and pooling resources for the launch and operation of the different repositories. It includes savings regarding administration/management and technical aspects (**labour cost savings**).

³⁰ These cost savings are benefits because they correspond to the gains for institutions allowed by RCAAP. By contrast, the costs of RCAAP refer to the additional costs linked to the emergence and operation of the system (at the central level). This presentation ensures that no double-counting is performed.

- (ii) The time saved in pooling resources for the technical infrastructures of the IR, in particular, the use of shared servers provided by RCAAP to the institutions. (***data storage costs savings***)

Some benefits highlighted in the IPL were investigated but not integrated into the CBA for different motives:

- **Some benefits were either too uncertain or too small to be integrated into the model.**
 - They notably included the internal benefits of having access to RCAAP from the point of view of institutions. For instance, RCAAP provides statistics through a dedicated add-on for librarians. These statistics can be used for different purposes, such as monitoring scientific activity and drafting internal reports.
 - Similarly, the evidence from IR can be used to evaluate researchers (e.g., career evaluation based on the deposited documents). However, additional interviews with the repository managers suggested that the efficiency gains from these possibilities were small and difficult to attribute solely to RCAAP (as opposed to having an IR, which would happen under the counterfactual scenario).
 - As explained above, costs were considered equal under the real-world and counterfactual scenarios for training and deposit costs. As a result, they do not produce any savings and are not included in this section on benefits.
- **Some benefits were clearly present but not assessable with the available evidence.**
 - It included the benefits connected to the effects of RCAAP on access to documents (e.g., a higher number of downloads, reduced access costs in terms of time spent – for instance, for PhD theses...). The difficulty of having a clear counterfactual in mind for the respondents (of the survey and interviews) and to model these trends made the inclusion of these benefits too uncertain. This can bring valuable lessons for future research (see below).
 - In particular, we investigated access cost savings (in terms of potential time savings), but as outlined in the previous section, we could not integrate them robustly into the model. Benefits from access cost savings are expected to be significant, so our results should be analysed with that methodological choice in consideration, i.e., as a lower bound of the true benefits of RCAAP.

The cost savings forming the benefits of RCAAP are relevant for SARI repositories and RCOMUM collections. Indeed, LOCAL repositories face significant labour and equipment costs to store their data, since they do not join the shared hosting services RCAAP provides. Consequently, to incorporate the savings in the cost-benefit analysis, we applied the cost structure of LOCAL repositories (e.g., equipment costs, personnel costs) to institutions that chose SARI or RCOMUM under the real-world scenario. To consider that RCOMUM institutions are smaller, we applied a correction ratio (25% based on observed downloads when compared to LOCAL repositories,

i.e., a proxy of activity) to not overstate the potential benefits. The cost structure of LOCAL repositories was retrieved thanks to interviews with repository managers and findings from the literature.

RCAAP allows cost savings for the institutions adopting SARI or RCOMUM repositories. It implies that the difference in costs for institutional providers between the counterfactual and RCAAP scenario are counted as benefits in the results section (i.e., the difference in costs is net savings). This allows the analysis to avoid double-counting issues (see Section 3.4. for further details).

In the subsections below, we provide a more detailed explanation of the rationale for including these provider cost savings in our analysis, along with their estimation results. They are composed of labour cost savings and data storage cost savings.

Labour cost savings

Labour cost savings occur for SARI and RCOMUM repositories. From the perspective of institutions having SARI/RCOMUM repositories, labour cost savings arise from two distinct channels:

- Some tasks simply do not exist for them in this arrangement, as compared to the counterfactual of operating its own repositories (LOCAL cost structure). In particular, technical and maintenance staff do not have to be employed (or contracted as external providers) by institutions joining SARI/RCOMUM. Instead, technical staff managing their repositories is pooled and shared at the RCAAP central level. By splitting their time across several repositories, RCAAP employees at the central level are more efficient than several workers in each institution.
- Some other tasks are simplified in this arrangement, as compared to the counterfactual of operating its own repositories (LOCAL cost structure). It includes simplified management and administrative tasks (since the process is standardised through the service provided by RCAAP), librarians' checks and curation, etc.

The savings were estimated based on the working time (in full-time equivalent) for these different activities between LOCAL and other types of repositories. For instance, managing and administrating a mature SARI repository is estimated at 1.35 FTE against 1.5 FTE for a LOCAL repository (i.e., a yearly saving of 0.15 FTE). The FTE were then monetised using wages for the different occupations (based on Payscale data) to compute the savings.

The following Figure outlines the evolution of labour cost savings over time. The savings only materialise after introducing operational SARI (and RCOMUM) repositories, i.e., from 2009 onwards. The savings rise with the development of these repositories.

Figure 30. Labour costs savings for providers (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on multiple data sources, and interviews with repository managers. **Note:** Labour cost savings correspond to savings for institutions with SARI/RCOMUM repositories compared to the counterfactual with the LOCAL repositories' cost structure. These labour cost savings notably include technical/maintenance, administrative/management, and curation/check staff. Costs are scaled for repositories of the RCOMUM type due to their small size (25%). All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

Overall, **labour cost savings can be estimated at about EUR₂₀₂₄ 5 million for 2006-2026. In recent years, they have reached about EUR₂₀₂₄ 365,000 on a yearly basis.** These savings must obviously be balanced against the costs borne at the RCAAP central level to provide the shared hosting services.

Data storage cost savings

Data storage cost savings associated with RCAAP refer to the costs avoided by providers due to the existence of hosting services (SARI/RCOMUM), eliminating the need to store data locally or on other systems. While these costs are relatively small compared to labour costs, they are still significant, particularly because regular updates are needed. The literature and interviews suggest that replacement cycles every 5-10 years are credible for the IR servers hosting scientific documents.

Since institutions using SARI/RCOMUM do not have servers at all under their arrangement, the savings simply correspond to the avoided costs of the servers (initial investments and reinvestments). We thus modelled these costs in the same way as we did for the LOCAL repositories. As for the labour costs, we applied a corrective factor (25%, based on the observed number of downloads) to the RCOMUM institutions since their small scope would probably require small servers as well. This approach is considered conservative, i.e., it probably leads to lower RCAAP benefits than in reality.

The following Figure shows the trend in data storage cost savings over time. The savings feature significant year-on-year variations, which are due to the different creation dates of the repositories, and to the length of the reinvestment cycles.

Figure 31. Data storage costs savings for providers (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on multiple data sources, and interviews with repository managers. **Note:** Data storage cost savings are estimated based on the costs of servers observed for LOCAL repositories (initial investments, reinvestments). Costs are scaled for repositories of the RCOMUM type due to their small size (25%). All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

Overall, **data storage cost savings can be estimated at about EUR₂₀₂₄ 940,000 for 2006-2026.** As for labour cost savings, these savings must be contrasted with the costs borne by RCAAP at the central level to store documents on behalf of beneficiary institutions.

Overview of total benefits

Combining the two different types of benefits, we observe that we reach an undiscounted value³¹ of almost **EUR₂₀₂₄ 6 million for 2006-2026.** The Figure below shows these benefits materialised a few years after RCAAP and its component repositories were launched. Moreover, the savings in labour costs are much higher than the savings in data storage costs, though the latter are still significant (about 15% of the total). In recent years, **benefits amount to about EUR₂₀₂₄ 470,000 yearly (2024).**

³¹ Undiscounted value does not account for the fact that the same amount of costs and benefits can be worth less in the future when compared to today. It simply aggregates all expected benefits and costs over a period, without applying any correction. To account for the fact that benefits and costs are worth more today than in the future, we can apply a Social Discount Rate (SDR) to undiscounted values. Thanks to the SDR, we can convert all costs and benefits to make sure their values are comparable, as of today.

Figure 32. Overview of total benefits for providers (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on multiple data sources, and interviews with repository managers. **Note:** Total benefits for providers include labour cost savings and data storage cost savings. As noted above, access cost savings are not considered. All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

The following section compiles costs and benefits consistently to avoid double-counting and deliver a final judgment on the performance of RCAAP.

3.4 Overall results

This section combines the different costs and benefits consistently analysed in the CBA model. More precisely, it compares the costs and benefits of the real-world scenario with RCAAP against the counterfactual scenario without RCAAP but with an emerging IR network sharing the same cost structure as LOCAL repositories.

As we have retrieved and modelled investment costs, it is possible to derive key metrics of performance for the CBA, including the Net Present Value and the project's benefit-cost ratio³².

The costs presented in this section correspond to the costs borne by RCAAP at the central level. Indeed, these costs do not exist in the scenario without RCAAP, so the difference with the counterfactual is the actual costs. Institutional provider costs are not included since they cancel out for LOCAL repositories (same situation with and without RCAAP), and they are counted as

³² As noted above, Net Present Value (NPV) is a financial metric that calculates the difference between the costs and benefits for a project or investment, adjusted so that flows that happen at different points of time are comparable. A positive NPV indicates that the project is expected to be beneficial, while a negative NPV suggests it may not be worth pursuing.

A benefit-cost ratio is simply Net Benefits divided by Net Costs. A ratio greater than 1 implies that benefits outweigh costs. A ratio lower than 1 implies the contrary.

cost savings and, hence, as benefits for SARI/RCOMUM. This choice ensures that we do not experience double-counting problems. Finally, the users' costs are not included since they cancel out for deposits and training costs and could not be included for access costs (see below). Symmetrically, no access cost savings are included as benefits.

As a result, the benefits include the cost savings described in Section 3.3. Since we do not include access cost savings (which are likely significant), we provide a very conservative estimate for RCAAP benefits. As we will show, the project is a net social gain even under these unfavourable assumptions.

The benefits and costs do not materialise simultaneously, given the preparatory activities and the set-up of both RCAAP and its aggregated repositories. Accordingly, we can observe that the net benefit is negative until 2014 (benefits appear by 2009 but do not offset the costs until 2014). At the end of the period (2020s onwards), we reach yearly net benefits in the realm of EUR₂₀₂₄ 300,000.

Figure 33. Net benefits over time (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on multiple data sources. **Note:** All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

To adequately take into consideration the fact that benefits and costs do not occur at the same time, we apply a social discount rate to all values. Indeed, the value of one euro is not the same across time. This discount rate results in higher weight being given to the project's early years (as opposed to later years). **The Table below summarises the estimated costs and running benefits for RCAAP over the entire reference period (2006-2026).** We discount the values from different years using a standard rate obtained from the literature (Catalano et al., 2022).

A few important considerations arise from these results:

- Personnel costs incurred by the RCAAP central level account for a significant share (about 56%) of the expenses required to launch and operate this resource. This category

also accounts for the personnel providing the benefits to participating institutions (which do not have to employ, e.g., IT technicians to run their own repositories)

- Labour cost savings are the most substantial benefits considered in this analysis, while data storage costs are much less marginal. Labour cost savings derive from the greater efficiency of sharing experienced personnel, resulting in economies of scale.
- By comparing the estimated costs and benefits associated with RCAAP, it is evident that the benefits significantly outweigh the costs under this counterfactual. **Specifically, the net present value of the entire system amounts to EUR₂₀₂₄ 1.1 million. More intuitively, it means that the system results in benefits that are at least 32% larger than costs (focusing on the cost savings due to the pooling of resources).**
- Moreover, this estimate does not include access cost savings, i.e., the fact that users spend less time searching and downloading content with RCAAP as opposed to the counterfactual. **If we considered this benefit, the results of RCAAP would be even higher.**

Table 3 Overview of results for RCAAP

results (EUR 2024)	DISCOUNTED VALUE (2006-2026)	UNDISCOUNTED VALUE (2006-2026)
<i>TOTAL COSTS (A)</i>	3,559,370	4,206,054
<i>Total set-up costs (RCAAP central level), of which:</i>	930,517	1,041,018
<i>Intangible fixed assets</i>	1,581	1,797
<i>Computer equipment and software</i>	592,102	696,344
<i>Operational costs for set-up</i>	336,833	342,877
<i>Total operational costs (RCAAP central level), of which:</i>	2,628,853	3,165,037
<i>Staff costs and related expenditure</i>	1,675,444	2,005,700
<i>Training costs</i>	6,145	7,538
<i>Travel costs</i>	40,553	50,041
<i>Dissemination</i>	29,115	31,062
<i>Funding to partner institutions</i>	142,334	186,023
<i>Other expenses</i>	735,262	884,672
<i>Total USER costs (EUR), of which:</i>	N/A	N/A
<i>Training costs</i>	N/A	N/A
<i>Deposits costs</i>	N/A	N/A
<i>Access costs</i>	Not included	
<i>TOTAL BENEFITS (B), of which</i>	4,689,963	5,992,536
<i>Labor costs savings</i>	3,937,893	5,053,289
<i>Data storage cost savings</i>	752,070	939,247
<i>Access costs savings</i>	Not included	
NET PRESENT VALUE (B - A)	1,130,594	
BENEFIT COST RATIO (B / A)	1.32	

Source: Authors' elaboration on multiple sources (see previous sections). **Note:** The Table reports the values for the 2006-2026 period. All values are expressed in real (2024 euros) values. Discounted values used the baseline estimate of Catalano et al. for Portugal (1.97%).

It is challenging to compare our results to the broader scientific literature since a fully-fledged CBA of IR / networks of IR was not available to the best of our knowledge. Previous studies (e.g., Burns et al., 2013) tended to confirm our results regarding costs borne by individual repositories, but the evidence on the benefits side (e.g., access costs savings) remains scarce. Evidence from the focus group and the interviews contributed to validating the results, albeit qualitatively. In particular, the contributors stressed the importance of RCAAP in pooling resources and allowing the development of IR in Portugal, especially for smaller institutions³³. They also noted that easy access to resources was an advantage, which we could not include in the CBA but could be highlighted in further research.

4. Benefits beyond CBA

As shown in the RCAAP IPL (see Section 2), the benefits of RCAAP go beyond short-term outcomes, such as cost savings measured through the cost-benefit analysis. Instead, these benefits reach further, encompassing what we have identified in the IPL as long-term outcomes. Although these outcomes are linked to the use of RCAAP, their occurrence also depends on additional user effort and resources, making it challenging to attribute them solely to RCAAP, unlike the short-term outcomes. It includes cultural, economic or organisational benefits (e.g., creating new entrepreneurial ideas and cultural diffusion). The common feature of these benefits is that they are challenging to observe.

Overall, the evidence on these benefits is limited, and the data points towards relatively modest effects at this stage.

Anecdotes from the interviewees suggested that the wider society could benefit from RCAAP in the form of increase knowledge or culture. For instance, a repository manager noted that there were some recorded cases where patients with specific medical conditions would find relevant content on their diseases on the IR and even contact the researchers on that basis. However, these long-term outcomes remained rare (even if probably under-counted) and the causal attribution to RCAAP uncertain.

When it comes to improved research productivity in Portugal, data from the University of Minho (Work Package 3) shows that the total output of Portuguese scientific documents hosted on RCAAP IR forms a significant share of the total Portuguese scientific outputs. Indeed, about 40% of the total number of Portuguese scientific documents is hosted on RCAAP IR (see Figure).

³³ In some cases, they mentioned that they believed that without RCAAP, IR would maybe not have developed, or at the same pace in Portugal. In our counterfactual, we hypothesised that this development occurred in order to compare similar levels of services.

Figure 34. Number of Portuguese scientific documents by presence on RCAAP (2015-2024)

Source: Authors based on WP3 (University of Minho). **Note:** RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents hosted on RCAAP IR. Non-RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents not hosted on RCAAP IR.

However, documents hosted on RCAAP IR receive much less citations than those non-hosted on RCAAP, about half as much in the mid-2010s (citations tend to be less reliable in the most recent years due to the time lag between publications and citations). Moreover, the ratio of RCAAP to non-RCAAP citations tends to decline, casting doubts on the ability of RCAAP to boost visibility of research.

Figure 35. Mean Citations per Document depending on presence on RCAAP (2015-2024)

Source: Authors based on WP3 (University of Minho). **Note:** RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents hosted on RCAAP IR. Non-RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents not hosted on RCAAP IR.

However, this data is purely correlational and does not allow a direct attribution of causality to RCAAP (in particular, because non-RCAAP documents may be positively selected, e.g., more represented in prestigious journals under paywalls). A boost of visibility may still be present

thanks to RCAAP, and we can hypothesise that it may notably be relevant for documents published in less visible journals, or other types of documents that would not benefit from significant exposure otherwise (e.g., theses).

Industry-academia collaborations are another form of long-term potential outcome of RCAAP. In this realm, data from Work Package 3 / University of Minho can also be used. Indeed, it is possible to track the number of documents involving both academic and industrial stakeholders over time, distinguishing RCAAP and non-RCAAP documents. As shown in the Figure below, few documents (on RCAAP or on other venues) refer to industry-academia collaborations in Portugal.

Figure 36. Share of Portuguese scientific documents with industry-academia collaboration by presence on RCAAP (2015-2024)

Source: Authors based on WP3 (University of Minho). **Note:** RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents hosted on RCAAP IR. Non-RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents not hosted on RCAAP IR.

More critically, documents hosted on RCAAP are less linked to industry-academia collaborations than those not hosted on RCAAP (about 3 times less chance). Due to differences in composition of the RCAAP and non-RCAAP sample, we cannot exclude that RCAAP may promote some industry-academia collaborations, but there is no firm evidence to support that view. Regardless, the absolute effect would be very small, confirming that the core of RCAAP’s benefits is not economic, but rather academic.

5. Conclusions and lessons learned

5.1 Conclusions

This case study aimed to test the cost-benefit analysis framework described by Delugas et al. (2023) to assess open science projects and practices. We relied on a comprehensive set of qualitative and quantitative methods for data collection and analysis to carry out this analysis. Primary data on costs and usage were obtained from the RCAAP team, repository managers and researchers, while user information was gathered through a user survey. Additional qualitative insights emerged from numerous interviews and a focus group conducted throughout the analysis, which helped validate our findings.

The analysis started with the construction of the impact pathways framework of RCAAP - based on Dekker, Karasz et al. (2023)—to illustrate how the funding and resources provided to RCAAP (inputs) lead to direct benefits (outputs and outcomes) and drive advancements (impacts) in science, (and to a much lesser extent) the economy, and society. This allowed us to identify both short- and long-term outcomes, as well as broader socio-economic impacts, associated with RCAAP and sketch the main RCAAP Impact Pathways.

The CBA was explicitly applied to evaluate the short-term outcomes RCAAP provides – especially to its participating institutions. However, a broader causal pathways analysis was used to assess long-term outcomes, acknowledging that these outcomes often involve multiple contributing factors, making it difficult to establish a direct causal link to RCAAP. Precisely, RCAAP's long-term outcomes were tracked through qualitative evidence sources, including interviews and user surveys.

It was possible to carry out a full assessment of set-up and operational costs for RCAAP, and thus to derive its Net Present Value. However, it was not possible to integrate all relevant costs/benefits into the model, with the significant case being access costs (savings). This fact should be taken into consideration when reviewing the results. Critically, this issue biases the analysis downwards. **Our baseline estimate suggests that the benefits of RCAAP are 32% higher than its costs, and these benefits would likely significantly rise by considering access cost savings. Our analysis also considers a counterfactual that is not a closed science alternative, but rather an unintegrated approach to open science (i.e., development of IR of Portuguese stakeholders without networking and pooling of resources).** Alternative scenarios would have produced different estimates.

With these caveats highlighted, the following findings shall be stressed:

- **Structure of providers' costs:** The network of IR organised around RCAAP is characterised by the importance of labour costs and the prominence of costs at the level of individual institutions (as opposed to the RCAAP central level). This particular cost structure can be contrasted to several projects in the field of R&D but is consistent with ICT-based projects and the existing literature on IR (see, e.g., Burns et al., 2013).
- **User Costs:** The functioning of RCAAP is based upon actions realized by its users, either to deposit or to search for content in its different IR. These costs include training, deposit and access costs. It is clear that the dominant cost is related to access, given the volume and time spent on this aspect. However, it is also challenging to evaluate, especially when it comes to assessing the counterfactual.
- **Cost savings:** The primary short-term benefits of RCAAP consist of cost savings to the institutions benefiting from shared hosting services. These savings included personnel costs (i.e., less time spent for workers to manage the IR) and infrastructure/equipment (data storage savings). Labour cost savings were the most significant. These savings originate from the greater efficiency in pooling some resources at the central level (e.g., economies of scale...) compared to each institution operating independently.
- **Net Benefit Justification:** The cost-benefit analysis results indicate that RCAAP's net benefit exceeds the expenditure required to launch, maintain and operate it. Specifically, benefits are at least 32% higher than costs, and this ratio would favourably improve if access cost savings were integrated into the model.

Beyond the short-term outcomes, RCAAP may have a positive role in accelerating scientific research, especially in Portugal but also abroad. By facilitating access to scientific resources, further research, results uptake and diffusion could be boosted. However, the scale of these benefits is difficult to assess, given the potential alternative routes to access the content stored on RCAAP IR. Other types of benefits, such as industry-academia collaboration, may happen, but the qualitative and quantitative evidence suggests that these effects are rare and difficult to attribute to RCAAP alone. More credible are benefits for institutions and academia in terms of internal efficiency, but substantial disparities between them are likely.

This case study has also highlighted the challenges in conducting such analyses for open science resources (see the following section on lessons learned). While some difficulties encountered were specific to RCAAP (e.g., complex governance with multiple layers and types of stakeholders), this experience likely provides insights transferable to other open science projects.

5.2 Lessons learned

From carrying out the cost-benefit analysis of RCAAP, several key lessons emerge that can inform future applications and similar studies. These insights are summarised below:

- **Identifying and estimating the number of users of open science projects is very challenging due to both conceptual and practical considerations (e.g., data accessibility and quality).**

There are different types of users of open science projects, ranging from people accessing the open content (without any need for registration) to people contributing to the system (e.g., by making deposits to the IR). In both cases, describing and quantifying the users may be challenging.

- Typically, open science projects—such as RCAAP—do not track individual users directly. Any estimation of users must be derived from external (e.g., Google Analytics) or internal tools (e.g., statistics plug-in for DSpace). However, this data can be imperfect due to the collection method (based on IP address) but also to the fragmentation of the IR. Indeed, the existence of different repositories (especially LOCAL ones) implies that the consolidation and aggregation of all statistics can be a challenge.
- It also implies that users' profiles are typically only tangentially known, beyond basic information such as geographical origin (subject to limitations as well). Collecting this granular information with surveys (e.g., occupation, age...) is a way forward, but it can be biased by differential participation.
- **Attributing costs for open science projects is not trivial, especially when multiple layers of institutions and users are involved, as is the case for RCAAP:**
 - Institutions do not always keep ad-hoc budgetary records of the resources they spend to run their open resources. While the data was well consolidated at the RCAAP central level, specific institutions do not keep a dedicated budget to track their IR expenses. Typically, this budget is diluted in the broader library or university budget. It implies a granular work of reconstruction of the costs, which can be done thanks to insights from in-depth interviews, external data and the scientific literature.
 - Time spent by users is a flexible approach to approximate the costs they face when carrying out activities related to open resources. However, collecting credible information regarding this time spent can be challenging. In particular, there is a strong anchoring effect due to the provided options in closed questions of a survey. Backing the estimates with multiple sources of evidence (e.g., interviews, focus group) is paramount to ensure quality.
- **Defining the counterfactual for open science projects is not straightforward – especially in the broader context of the development of initiatives such as IR. This has implications for the ability to measure costs and benefits.**

To estimate the net value provided by open science projects, it is crucial to choose an appropriate counterfactual, such as what the alternative would have been without the project. This is a core principle of CBA, as it allows an incremental comparison.

However, defining the counterfactual for RCAAP was very challenging. Indeed, several resources could have been open even without RCAAP, and alternatives were numerous. Similarly, IR could have been developed even without RCAAP, though at higher costs (and perhaps at a different pace). In addition, the case study compared two scenarios of open repositories: one with integration/pooling of resources (RCAAP) and the other without (institutions managing their IR on their own). Indeed, it was not meaningful in this case to have a comparison against a fully closed alternative, which may be relevant for other types of open science resources.

Overall, it was difficult for respondents (survey, interviews...) to imagine the counterfactual, leading to issues (e.g., in identifying access cost savings).

This issue was resolved by setting the counterfactual as the development of IR in Portugal without RCAAP, which excludes the pooling benefits provided by centralisation. However, this necessitates some assumptions which can be challenged under different grounds (e.g., the ability of small institutions to run IR without support).

- **Identifying the long-term or indirect effects of open science projects is challenging, and qualitative methods may be more flexible in some cases.**

Considering the long-term or indirect effects of RCAAP was complexified by the uncertainties around the counterfactual and the limitations of methods to reach that end. Quantitative methods (such as analysis of industry-academia collaborations using publication data) can be used but pose methodological challenges (e.g., causality). Preliminary evidence suggests minor economic effects. Qualitative methods (notably interviews and survey open-ended questions) proved more valuable in collecting insights on potential indirect/long-term effects but with limitations regarding generalizability.

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Annexes

Annex 1: Methodological toolkit

The assessment presented in this deliverable draws upon a comprehensive and multi-dimensional methodological approach that integrates both primary and secondary data sources, as well as qualitative and quantitative analytical techniques. The objective was to produce a robust, evidence-based evaluation of RCAAP's value and impact. The methodological toolkit comprises a set of interconnected components, each offering distinct but complementary insights.

Desk research provided the foundation for designing the CBA, including methodological insights from previous studies, functioning of Institutional Repositories, specificities of RCAAP (e.g., impact pathways, governance and user groups...).

Quantitative data was used to describe and forecast the users of RCAAP, as well as the budgetary aspects.

The user survey offered detailed information on usage patterns, perceived value, user benefits that are not otherwise quantifiable, and scenarios without RCAAP. Time monetisation enabled the translation of these elements into costs and benefits integrable to the CBA.

Semi-structured interviews and focus groups added qualitative depth and served to refine our understanding of the system, collect additional data (notably on costs at the institutional level) and to validate the findings.

Other work packages of PathOS (notably Work Package 3) provided additional data to describe the impacts not directly captured by the CBA.

The sections that follow present each methodological component in more detail.

A.1.1 DESK RESEARCH

Desk research was the first step of the assessment and was conducted by using academic papers, policy reports, and other documents from the grey literature. It pursued several objectives and was organised into three major strands:

- **RCAAP project:** Materials (e.g., project documents, guidelines...) related to the history, gradual development, uses, and performance of the RCAAP project and its individual components (see, for instance, Moreira et al., 2017; Carvalho et al., 2018). The scientific literature focusing on RCAAP and/or its usage was also explored, though it remained limited at the time of the writing.
- **Institutional Repositories and related issues** (e.g., Current Research Information System – CRIS): Documents related to the experience of other IR and

associated information systems, providing insights on typical organisation, procedures, policies, users' experience and costs and benefits (e.g., Angelo, 2014; Bryant et al., 2018; Esse and Haliso, 2024; Knowledge E, 2020; Lipinski, 2011; Rodrigues et al., 2024; Shearer et al., 2023). It allows contextualisation of the Portuguese case, the definition of the likely impact pathways, and data collection for potential extrapolations.

- **Methodological insights:** Potential methodological feedback related to the assessment of IR and similar initiatives were also collected. It includes CBA and other assessment methodologies (e.g., Bluh, 2009; Burns, Lana, and Budd, 2013; White and Crawford, 1998; Swan, Picarra, and Rodrigues, 2016).

A.1.2 ANALYSIS OF QUANTITATIVE DATA

In the context of the RCAAP case study, quantitative data was retrieved primarily from the RCAAP central level. This data fed the analysis for the historical period as well as for the two years of the forecast (2025 and 2026). It contributed to two aspects:

- **Budgetary data:** Data from the RCAAP central level allowed a mapping of expenditure borne by the overall functioning of the system, excluding its component institutions. It was provided by FCCN/FCT and discussed on several iterations to interpret it and complete missing information (e.g., first years prior to the launch, additional expenditure not covered in the initial budget, etc.). Budgetary data at the institutional level was mostly derived from interviews (see below) and from the secondary literature.
- **Use data:** As an open resource, RCAAP does not require registration for users searching and downloading content. As a result, use data can be monitored indirectly, through web traffic and downloads data. This information was retrieved from RCAAP at the central level (Google Analytics for views/traffic, internal statistical module for downloads). This data has some limitations (e.g. Ross et al., 2024; Beagrie and Houghton, 2021, 2016; Fomitchev, 2010), but some corrections were already applied (e.g., to remove duplicates) in the received data, and it was used directly as inputs for the CBA. Missing data (e.g., for some years) was extrapolated using proxy information (e.g., use of data on downloads to reconstruct estimates for the number of users in some years, etc.).

A.1.3 USER SURVEY

This tool was used to collect descriptive information on the users of RCAAP (e.g., age, professional background, uses of RCAAP, etc.) and primary data on the perceived value of the project.

The questionnaire was structured in three sections: Section A – General Information: it investigated respondents' profile (e.g. country of work, professional status, research fields/job details, etc); Section B – Experience with RCAAP: it investigated on the usage of the resources (e.g. frequency, combination with other sources, time used, overall satisfaction etc); Section C –

Assessment of the value of RCAAP: it included questions investigating time savings, potential alternatives if RCAAP did not exist.

The questionnaire was developed in subsequent rounds of consultation between the team, the University of Minho, and six scoping interviews with different users of the RCAAP Portal and repositories. The survey was implemented using the EUSurvey tool of the European Commission in compliance with the data privacy regulations. It was disseminated with the support of the University of Minho and FCCN through different channels, including the RCAAP portal, individual repositories managed centrally by the University of Minho / FCCN, social media, and newsletters/ mailing lists.

Overall, 213³⁴ responses were collected using EUSurvey between 12 June and 16 September 2024.

Since the characteristics of the user base population are entirely unknown—apart from the global geographical distribution of users inferred from web traffic data—it was decided not to adopt a probability sampling approach. Instead, a thorough ex-post analysis was carried out, comparing the distribution of respondents by country with that of web traffic data. Users from Portugal were somewhat overrepresented in the survey results, but it aligned well with the fact that the survey also targeted researchers/librarians feeding the system, not only users searching and downloading content. The survey sample was thus used comprehensively to feed the CBA (notably on time spent for different tasks).

Nonetheless, certain limitations of the approach should be acknowledged. In particular, the absence of a defined sampling frame and the reliance on voluntary participation introduce potential self-selection bias, as those more actively engaged with the resource may have been more inclined to respond.

A.1.5 INTERVIEWS

A total of 13 interviews were conducted as of October 2024 (see the complete list in Annex 1). They aimed to understand the patterns of uses of RCAAP (Portal and IR) for different classes of users, including researchers and administrative staff from the network of institutions operating the repositories. It allowed in-depth discussions on the value and limits of RCAAP from different perspectives. A first round of interviews was carried out in parallel to the development of the questionnaire for the online survey. A total of six interviews were performed that way, collecting valuable information on RCAAP while testing the clarity of the questionnaire. A second round of interviews was conducted at a later stage with repository managers of a sample of institutions (covering the different models of repositories). These interviews focused more on the internal benefits and costs of RCAAP participation for the institutions. A total of 7 interviews

³⁴ Out of 213 responses, 15 never used RCAAP, 3 were former users and 5 had missing information.

of this type were already implemented during the project, and additional ones are under consideration to complete the sample.

A.1.6 FOCUS GROUP

A total of 8 participants were involved in a virtual focus group on 03/12/2024. This focus group was organised in the framework of WP3 and contained a section dedicated to the CBA. During this exchange, information was provided regarding key aspects of the CBA, and feedback from diverse stakeholders was retrieved in order to consolidate the model and the final draft of the case study. It included topics such as the type and depth of benefits, as well as the counterfactual scenario.

A.1.7 ADDITIONAL DATA FROM WORK PACKAGE 3

Additional data on the potential impacts of RCAAP beyond the scope of the CBA was provided by the University of Minho. This data was obtained and consolidated in the framework of Work Package 3 of the PathOS project. It mainly covers insights on RCAAP-related scientific publications (e.g., number of documents, received citations) with a particular focus on industry-academia collaborations.

Annex 2: Interviews carried out

The following Table reports the interviewees' round, date, and affiliation for each interview.

INTERVIEW ROUND	ORGANISATION	DATE
Pilot interviews (including testing of the survey)	University of Algarve	03/06/2024
	University of Minho	03/06/2024
	University of Beira Interior	04/06/2024
	University of Aveiro	04/06/2024
	University of Lisbon	04/06/2024
	CRIA	07/06/2024
Additional interviews with repository managers	NOVA University Lisbon	27/08/2024
	Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal	28/08/2024
	ISCTE – University Institute of Lisbon	29/08/2024
	University of Minho	30/08/2024
	University of Porto	08/10/2024
	University of Coimbra	09/10/2024
	ESEL - Higher School of Nursing of Lisbon	18/10/2024 (written interview)

Annex 3: Focus Group's Composition

The following Table reports the participants in the focus group co-organised with WP3.

FOCUS GROUP	ORGANISATION	DATE
Common focus group with WP3	FCT-FCCN (PTCRIS)	03/12/2024
	FCT-FCCN (RCAAP)	
	University Institute of Lisbon	
	University of Minho	
	OpenAIRE	
	Bologna University / Open Citations	
	Lisbon Nova University	